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**Expert system to determine a proper control method for certain hemipterous
(Hemiptera) insects according to site conditions**

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Abstract:

Insects that follow the hemipterous (Hemiptera) insects infest various horticultural and field crops, causing great damage and severe losses to farmers. Therefore, it was necessary to build a system to facilitate determine the appropriate control method for field conditions as soon as possible to reach satisfactory results for farmers. An expert system was built based on the opinions of specialized and experienced experts. Experience in the field and review of research and references, specialized in pest control of hemipterous insects to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the expertise system provided. The research aims to build an expert system to choose the optimal control method according to the site conditions. The expert system (ES) outcome was tested and evaluated by 9 cases studies (4 actual and 5 virtual cases). The results of testing and evaluating the case study showed the efficiency of the proposed ES in determining the optimal method for controlling insects that follow hemipterous insects according to field conditions, including abnormal and extreme conditions.

Introduction

The infestation of insects, especially the hemipterous insects belonging to Order Hemiptera and super family Coccoidea to any crops causes a various damages and loss in yield which consider a major problem for agriculture sector. It was important to detect the most appropriate control method to achieve the benefit of the successful and healthy harvest in quality and quantity.

For proper pest management, proper human experts are required. But there are too few to cover the cultivated area. To mitigate the lack of human experts and to help farmers to receive an accurate decision , an expert system

for insect pest management would be useful (Ghosh and Samanta, 2003).

Expert systems are intelligent systems that depend on inference and specific expertise of a human expert. They are employed widely to solve the complex problem in multiple domains, such as agriculture, medicine, oil exploration, etc. They are mostly suited in situations where the human expert is not readily available, The applications of expert system are rapidly increasing. Such applications are very effective in situations when the domain expert is not readily available (Negied, 2014).

Expert systems can be used as a powerful tool in this area since they can provide growers with recommendations

to efficiently manage their plantation. Expert system technology has been applied to a variety of agricultural problems since the early 1980s (El-Azhary *et al.*, 2000).

In Italy, an expert system for integrated pest management of apple orchards (POMI) (Gerevini *et al.*, 1992) has been developed. POMI addresses the first preliminary phase of the complex process of apple orchard integrated control, namely the detection of the insect population in the field and the approximate population dimension.

CUPTEX is an expert system, which has been developed for handling management of cucumber disorders (Rafea *et al.*, 1995). The main objective of this expert system was to identify the cause of an abnormal observation, and to propose the appropriate remediation. However, the user optionally can consult directly the remediation part if he/she knows the causes of the problem. In this case, the system starts by confirming these causes before giving the recommended remediation.

This paper aimed to build an expert system to facilitate the selection of the appropriate and accurate hemipterous insect control method to farmers and technical agricultural engineers.

Materials and methods

The aim of this study is to assist a proper control method selection for hemipterous insects according to field conditions. The control methods were selected according to (Awadallah *et al.* (1984), Balasubramani and Swamiappan (1994), Chen and Liu (2002), Mangoud and Abou-Setta (2012), El-Hefny *et al.* (2011), Hassan *et al.* (2012), Helmy *et al.* (2012), Buss and Dale (2016), Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2012) and El-Sahn *et al.* (2019).

1. Procedure for the selection of the proper control methods:

The decision Table (1) was developed to present prevailing

hemipterous insects control methods and qualifier conditions that prepared for the qualifiers leading to a proper control method selection for hemipterous insect according to field conditions, using methodology of Awady *et al.* (1997) and Awady *et al.* (2006 and 2016), aided with expertise, agricultural engineers members in different agricultural stations and technical workers, labors and knowledge data collected from literatures of published research, related books and review articles, to illustrate qualifier conditions.

Each case study had scores of confidences for each control method, which reflect the suitability to the circumstances. Virtual scores were allotted to different choices according to different qualifiers.

Consultations were held with domain experts to determine the qualifiers and test the outcomes of case studies, irregular outcomes were adjusted via values embedded in different rules, their effects were remarking on target and correlated choices, this procedure was iterated until obtaining satisfactory results.

Nine representation farms, including extreme cases with a wide variety of field conditions (4 actual and 5 virtual) showed in Table (2) and used to test the proposed expert system (ES) results.

The derived decision table is validated in actual and virtual case studies to test and compare and agreement with the outcomes from derived decision table for all site conditions including extreme site conditions.

2. Control methods:

The control methods were used according to expertise and literature published:

2.1. Mechanical control: Pruning and remove weeds.

2.2. Biological control: Parasitoids, predators and micro-organisms.

2.3. Chemical control: Chemical compounds, mineral oils, plant extracts, IGRs and mixtures.

3. Qualifiers:

The following qualifiers and factors were selected according to experts opinion:

1. Plant conditions:

1.1. Species : Fruit, Vegetable, ornamental plants, medicinal and aromatic plant and crops.

1.2. Age in years: more or less than 5 years.

1.3. Planting type: Organic and non-organic.

2. Field conditions :

2.1. Area in feddans: more or less than 5 feddans.

2.2. Labor: Un specialist and specialist.

2.3. Application availability: Backpack sprayer, trolley sprayer and manual sprayer.

2.4. Location: Open field and green house.

3. Pest conditions :

3.1. Species: Scale insects, mealybugs, white flies and aphids.

3.2. % infestation/plant: more or less than 5%.

3.3. Infestation intensity/field: more or less than 5%.

3.4. Infestation Season: Summer, autumn, winter and spring.

3.5. Infested plant stage: Vegetation, flowering, fruiting and dormancy.

4. Feasibility:

Cost, efficiency, initial reduction time, yield quantity and quality.

Allotted weight of each qualifier was suggested according to the experts' judgment by sorting qualifiers based on their importance and effectiveness on control methods.

Each qualifier was given a weight based on its effect on control method selection among affected qualifier. This weight was multiplied times score to get final score used to judge control methods appropriateness according to site conditions.

Case study Validation and evaluation:

Four actual cases and 5 virtual cases, including extreme cases were used to test the proposed expert system (ES) outcome. Cases were exposed to consultation with domain experts for validation of decision table results. Each of control methods was weighed under each suggested case.

The manipulation of decision table done using excel software, the highest score represented the most control method appropriateness of the case study.

The actual case outcomes were evaluated by calculate and compare insect population reduction percent rate with the recommendation according to The Accredited Agricultural Recommendations annual book (2020), after field application of control method with the /highest score gained from the proposed ES.

Figure (1) representational qualifier allotted weight percent, according to expert judgements.

Table (1): Decision table.

Qualifiers		Alloted weight	Qualifiers factors	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control				
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoid	Predator	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extract	IGRs	Mixture
Plant conditions	Species	1.5	Fruit	6	5	5	6	4	2	8	5	4	7
			Vegetable	2	7	4	6	3	2	7	4	3	5
			Ornamental plant	5	3	4	7	6	5	8	5	5	8
			Medicinal and aromatic plant	8	8	6	8	7	2	6	6	4	4
			Crops	6	8	5	5	4	7	8	4	3	7
	Age in years	1	<5	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
			>5	7	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
	Planting type	1.75	Organic	8	8	8	8	7	1	5	9	6	1
			Non organic	8	7	6	7	5	6	7	6	6	7
Field conditions	Area	1	<5	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8
			>5	6	7	6	3	2	6	7	2	2	7
	Labor	0.5	Unspecialist	7	7	2	2	2	7	8	5	5	7
			Specialist	6	6	6	7	7	7	8	6	5	8
	Application availability	1.25	Backpack sprayer	1	1	1	1	5	6	6	3	5	6
			Trolley Sprayer motor	1	1	1	1	6	7	9	5	6	7
			manual sprayer	1	1	7	8	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Location	1.25	Open field	7	9	6	7	6	7	8	6	6	7
			Green house	7	8	9	9	8	6	8	6	6	7
Pest conditions	Species	1.25	Scale insects	7	6	6	8	2	5	9	5	5	6
			mealybugs	7	6	6	8	1	5	9	5	5	6
			White flies	7	9	7	8	2	5	7	1	1	5
			Aphids	6	9	5	7	6	7	7	5	3	7

Table (1) : Continued.													
	Qualifiers	Alloted weight	Qualifiers factors	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control				
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoid	Predator	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extract	IGRs	Mixture
Pest conditions	% infestation /plant	1.75	<5	3	5	7	9	7	1	1	3	1	1
			>5	8	8	5	4	3	8	9	2	2	9
	Infestation intensity/field	1.75	<5	8	9	7	7	8	7	9	5	5	7
			>5	4	6	4	6	4	8	9	7	6	9
	Infestation Season	1	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6
			Autumn	7	9	3	3	2	6	7	5	5	7
			Winter	9	9	3	6	2	7	9	3	2	8
			Spring	3	6	4	5	2	1	1	1	1	1
	Infested Plant stage	1.25	Vegetation	5	8	6	7	6	7	9	7	6	8
			Flowering	1	7	8	9	3	1	1	1	1	1
			fruiting	1	8	8	9	2	1	1	1	1	1
			Dormancy	9	9	5	6	6	7	8	4	4	8
Feasibility		1.75	Cost	9	9	4	5	3	5	6	5	5	8
			Efficiency	8	8	5	8	4	8	8	5	5	9
			Initial reduction time	9	8	5	7	3	9	6	5	5	9
			Yield quantity	6	5	4	5	5	5	7	7	6	7
			Yield quality	5	5	4	5	5	3	7	7	4	7

Table (2): Site conditions data under investigation.

Site conditions		Case study								
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Case situation		Actual	Actual	Actual	Virtual	Virtual	Actual	Virtual	Virtual	Virtual
Plant	Species	Mandarin	Mango	Orange	Grape vine	<i>Cycas</i>	Sugar cane	Roselle	Sweet pepper	Cucumber
	Age	6	8	7	3	2	2	6 months	2 months	1 month
	Planting type	Non organic	Non organic	Non organic	Non organic	Non organic	Non organic	Non organic	Organic	Organic
Field	Area	3 feddans	2 feddans	6 feddans	1 feddans	50 m2	6 feddans	1 feddan	360 m2	360 m2
	Labor	Unspeciali-st	Unspecia-list	Specialist	Unspec-ialist	specialist	Unspec-ialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist
	Application availability	Trolley sprayer motor	Trolley sprayer motor	Trolley sprayer motor	Backpa-ck sprayer	manual sprayer	Trolley Sprayer motor	Backpack sprayer	Backpack sprayer	Manual sprayer
	Location	Open field	Open field	Open field	Open field	Green house	Open field	Open field	Green house	Green house
Pest	Species	Scale insects	Scale insects	Scale insects	Mealyb-ugs	Scale insects	Scale insects	White flies	White flies	Aphids
	% infestation/plant	40	40	30	5	60	40	5	5	3
	Infestation intensity/ field	60	60	50	20	70	50	4	40	5
	Infestation Season	Autumn	winter	Summer	Summer	Summer	Spring	Summer	Summer	Spring
	Plant phenology	Vegetation	Vegetation	Vegetation	Vegetation	Vegetation	Vegetation	Vegetation	Flowering	fruiting

Figure (1): Qualifiers weight percent used for control method selection

Results and discussion

In the following results presentation and discussion of the case study used. Figure (2) showed the total score for all hemipterous insect control methods under study, according to field conditions that presented in Table (1).

Nine case studies (4 actual and 5 virtual cases) were implemented to evaluate the efficiency of the expert system design to detect the appropriate control method according to site conditions including the extreme conditions.

The results of the proposed expert system were evaluated by calculating insect reduction percent and minimum time for the highest insect reduction percent was determined for the control method with highest score gained proposed from expert system.

1. Case (A):

Table (3) presented field conditions for the actual case (A) in Fayoum Governorate as follows: Plant conditions: The plant species were mandarin, trees were 6 years old, planting type non organic.

Field conditions, planted area 3 feddans, unspecialist labor, application availability trolley sprayer motor,

located in an the open field, insect species scale insects (*Parlatoria ziziphi*), infestation percent /plant40%, infestation intensity/field 60% infestation season was autumn, plant phenology vegetation.

The highest score gained for chemical control with mineral oil with 186 and the insect % reduction ratio was 94.8% after 15 days from the application which is considered good reduction % according to expert judgment.

2. Case (B):

Table (4) showed case B in Qaluobiya Governorate the following site conditions. Planting conditions were mango with 8 years, non organic, field conditions were mango was planted in 2 feddans with non specialist labor and trolley sprayer motor, in the open field.

Pest conditions were, the insect species were a scale insect with 40% infestation and 60% infestation intensity/field, planting season was winter plant phenology was vegetation. The highest score gained for chemical control with mixture was 178.5. The reduction percent to 89.1% after two weeks from application with summer

oil (Super misrona) mixed with organophosphorus compound (Malathion).

3. Case (C):

Table (5) represents case C in Giza Governorate, with site conditions: Plant conditions; plant species orange (7 years old), non organic. The field conditions were 6 feddans with specialist labors and the trolley sprayer motor was available in the open field.

Pest conditions, it was hard scale insects (*Lepidosaphes beckii*) with 30% Infestation/plant, Infestation intensity/field was 50%, the application season was summer and plant phenology was vegetation.

The highest score gained for chemical control with mixture was 176 The reduction percent recorded was 99.7% when summer oil (Star oil) mixed with IGR (admiral) compound were applied. The recorded reduction was 99.7%.

4. Case (D):

Table (6) represented case D (virtual case study) with site conditions; for the plant conditions the plant species were grape vine with 3 years, non organic. Field conditions where grape planted in one feddan with unspecialist labor and backpack sprayer was available.

The location was open field. Pest conditions were grape was infested with mealybugs (*Icerya seychellarum*) with 5% infestation/ plant and 20 % Infestation intensity/field in summer season and plant phenology was vegetation. The highest score gained for chemical control with mixture with 167.5.

5. Case (E):

Table (7) represented case E with of (virtual case study) site conditions; Plant conditions were; the plant was cycas palmlike with age 2 years (planted in pots), and planting type was non organic.

Field conditions: area was 50 m² with specialist labor and application availability was manual sprayer in the green house. Pest conditions where the infestation was with scale insects (*Saissetia coffeae*) % infestation/plant was 60% and infestation intensity/field 70% infestation in summer season in vegetative stage. The highest score gained for chemical control with mixture with 177.25 .

6. Case (F):

Table (8) represented case F in Qena Governorate, with site conditions: Plant conditions plant was sugar cane with 2 years , non organic plantation.

Field conditions were 6 feddans, unspecialist labor, trolley sprayer motor and location were open field. Pest conditions where the infestation was with soft scale insects (*Pulvinaria tenuivalvata*) and % infestation/ plant was 40% and infestation intensity/field 50%. The infested plant stage was vegetation in spring season.

The highest score gained for chemical control with mineral oil with 179. The actual reduction percent of mineral oil when applied was 83.4 % after a month (KZ oil) from the application.

7. Case (G):

Table (9) represented case G by (Virtual case study) with site conditions, planted with roselle with 6 months, organic, 1 feddan and specialist labor with backpack sprayer in open field infested with white flies % infestation/plant 5% and infestation intensity/field 4% in summer and infested plant stage was flowering.

The highest score gained from mechanical control with weed, remove with 166.25.

8. Case (H):

Table (10) represented case H (Virtual case study) with site conditions: Plant conditions were planted with sweet pepper with 2 months age, organic plantation, field

conditions were the area was 360 m² , specialist labor, application availability with backpack sprayer in the green house.

Pest conditions: Sweet pepper was infested with white flies with % infestation/plant 5% and infestation intensity/field 40% planted in summer on fruiting stage. The highest score gained from biological control with predators with 161.

9. Case (I):

Table (11) represents case I (Virtual case study) with site conditions: Plant conditions were the plant species were cucumber with 1-month age, organic, plantation. Field conditions were the area was 360 m² with specialist labor a manual sprayer as application availability in the green house.

Pest conditions were infested with aphids with % infestation/plant 3% and infestation intensity/field 5% . Infestation season in spring and the infested plant stage was flowering. The highest score gained from Biological control with predators with 168.25.

From the previously mentioned data it was clear that :

- Application with mineral oil as a chemical control gained the highest score of 186 and 179 for actual cases A and F for mandarin and sugar cane crop, respectively.
- Whereas, actual cases B, C, D and E showed the highest score were 178.5, 176, 167.5 and 177.75 for mixtures representing chemical control hemipterous control methods of mango, orange, grape vines and cycas palmlike , respectively and using predator as a biological control method for virtual cases I and H with sweet pepper and cucumber gained the highest score of 186.25 and 161, respectively.
- Finally, weed removing for mechanical control method gained of 166.25 the highest score in case G with roselle plants .

This paper is a pioneer, expert system (ES) for selecting the proper and accurate pest management of hemipterous insects infesting various crops according to field conditions.

The evaluation of ES revealed a successful attempt to help agricultural sector workers. However, it needs more efforts to facilitate the proposed (ES) usage to meet farmers' needs.

Table (3): Result score of case A.

	Site conditions		Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control					
			Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures	
Case A	Plant	Species	Mandarin	9	7.5	7.5	9	6	3	12	7.5	6	10.5
		Age in years	6	7	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
		Planting type	Non organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	12.25
	Field	Area	3 feddans	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8
		Labor	Unspecialist	3.5	3.5	1	1	1	3.5	4	2.5	2.5	3.5
		Application availability	Trolley Sprayer motor	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	7.5	8.75	11.25	6.25	7.5	8.75
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75
	Pest	Species	Scale insects	8.75	7.5	7.5	10	2.5	6.25	11.25	6.25	6.25	7.5
		% infestation/plant	40	14	14	8.75	7	5.25	14	15.75	3.5	3.5	15.75
		Infestation intensity/field	60	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75
		Infestation Season	Autumn	7	9	3	3	2	6	7	5	5	7
		Plant phenology	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10
	Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total			158.25	161	114	139	104	147	186	133.75	122.5	183.75

Table (4): Result score of case B.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control					
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures	
Case B	Plant	Species	Mango	9	7.5	7.5	9	6	3	12	7.5	6	10.5	
		Age in years	8	7	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6	
		Planting type	Non organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	10.5	12.25
	Field	Area	2 feddans	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8	
		Labor	Non specialist	3.5	3.5	1	1	1	3.5	4	2.5	2.5	3.5	
		Application availability	Trolley Sprayer motor	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	7.5	8.75	11.25	6.25	7.5	8.75	
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75	
	Pest	Species	Scale insects	1.25	1.25	8.75	10	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	
		% infestation/plant	40	14	14	8.75	7	5.25	14	15.75	3.5	3.5	15.75	
		Infestation intensity/field	60	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75	
		Infestation Season	winter	9	9	3	6	2	7	9	3	2	8	
		Plant phenology	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10	
	Total Feasibility				64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total				152.75	154.75	115.25	142	102.75	143	178	126.75	114.5	178.5

Table (5): Result score of case C.

	Site conditions		Case conditions		Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control			
					Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs
Case C	Plant	Species	Orange	9	7.5	7.5	9	6	3	12	7.5	6	10.5
		Age in years	7	7	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
		Planting type	Non organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	10.5
	Field	Area	6 feddans	6	7	6	3	2	6	7	2	2	7
		Labor	Specialist	3	3	3	3.5	3.5	3.5	4	3	2.5	4
		Application availability	Trolley Sprayer motor	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	7.5	8.75	11.25	6.25	7.5	8.75
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75
	Pest	Species	Scale insects	1.25	1.25	8.75	10	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
		% infestation/plant	30	14	14	8.75	7	5.25	14	15.75	3.5	3.5	15.75
		Infestation intensity/field	50	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75
		Infestation Season	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6
		Plant phenology	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10
	Total Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total			145.25	152.25	117.25	140.5	104.25	141	173	121.25	110.5	176

Table (6): Result score of case D.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control				
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures
Case D	Plant	Species	Grape vine	9	7.5	7.5	9	6	3	12	7.5	6	10.5
		Age in years	3	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
		Planting type	Non organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	12.25
	Field	Area	1 feddans	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8
		Labor	Unspecialist	3.5	3.5	1	1	1	3.5	4	2.5	2.5	3.5
		Application availability	Backpack sprayer	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	6.25	7.5	7.5	3.75	6.25	7.5
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75
	Pest	Species	mealybugs	8.75	7.5	7.5	10	1.25	6.25	11.25	6.25	6.25	7.5
		% infestation/plant	5	5.25	8.75	12.25	15.75	12.25	1.75	1.75	5.25	1.75	1.75
		Infestation intensity/field	20	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75
		Infestation Season	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6
		Plant phenology	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10
	Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total			143.5	153.75	119.5	151.75	112.5	132.5	166.25	131	117.5	167.5

Table (7): Result score of case E.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control				
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures
Case E	Plant	Species	Cycas	7.5	4.5	6	10.5	9	7.5	12	7.5	7.5	12
		Age in years	2	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
		Planting type	Non Organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	12.25
	Field	Area	50 m2	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8
		Labor	Specialist	3	3	3	3.5	3.5	3.5	4	3	2.5	4
		Application availability	manual sprayer	1.25	1.25	8.75	10	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
		Location	Green house	8.75	10	11.25	11.25	10	7.5	10	7.5	7.5	8.75
	Pest	Species	Scale insects	8.75	7.5	7.5	10	2.5	6.25	11.25	6.25	6.25	7.5
		% infestation/plant	60	14	14	8.75	7	5.25	14	15.75	3.5	3.5	15.75
		Infestation intensity/field	70	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75
		Infestation Season	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6
		Plant phenology	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10
	Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total			150.25	154.25	127.75	158.25	109.75	141.75	174	127.25	115.75	177.25

Table (8): Result score of case F.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control					
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures	
Case F	Plant conditions	Species	Sugar cane	9	12	7.5	7.5	6	10.5	12	6	4.5	10.5	
		Age in years	2	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6	
		Planting type	Non organic	14	12.25	10.5	12.25	8.75	10.5	12.25	10.5	10.5	12.25	
	Field conditions	Area	6 feddans	6	7	6	3	2	6	7	2	2	7	
		Labor	Unspecialist	3.5	3.5	1	1	1	3.5	4	2.5	2.5	3.5	
		Application availability	Trolley Sprayer motor	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	7.5	8.75	11.25	6.25	7.5	8.75	
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75	
	Pest conditions	Species	Scale insects	8.75	7.5	7.5	10	2.5	6.25	11.25	6.25	6.25	7.5	
		% infestation/plant	40	14	14	8.75	7	5.25	14	15.75	3.5	3.5	15.75	
		Infestation intensity/field	50	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75	
		Infestation Season	Spring	3	6	4	5	2	1	1	1	1	1	
		Infested Plant stage	Vegetation	6.25	10	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	11.25	8.75	7.5	10	
	Total Feasibility				64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total				151.25	162.5	113	134.5	99	149.5	179	122.25	112	176.75

Table (9): Result score of case G.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control					
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures	
Case G	Plant conditions	Species	Roselle	12	12	9	12	10.5	3	9	9	6	6	
		Age	6 months	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6	
		Planting type	Organic	14	14	14	14	12.25	1.75	15.75	15.75	10.5	1.75	
	Field conditions	Area	1 feddan	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8	
		Labor	Specialist	3	3	3	3.5	3.5	3.5	4	3	2.5	4	
		Application availability	Backpack sprayer	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	6.25	7.5	7.5	3.75	6.25	7.5	
		Location	Open field	8.75	11.25	7.5	8.75	7.5	8.75	10	7.5	7.5	8.75	
	Pest conditions	Species	White flies	8.75	11.25	8.75	10	2.5	6.25	8.75	1.25	1.25	6.25	
		% infestation/plant	5	5.25	8.75	12.25	15.75	12.25	1.75	1.75	5.25	1.75	1.75	
		Infestation intensity/field	4	14	15.75	12.25	12.25	14	12.25	15.75	8.75	8.75	12.25	
		Infestation Season	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6	
		Infested Plant stage	Flowering	1.25	8.75	10	11.25	3.75	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
	Total Feasibility				64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total				148	167.25	135.5	163.25	127.5	114.5	154.25	122.25	104.5	139.5

Table (10): Result score of case H.

	Site conditions		Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control				
				Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures
Plant conditions	Species	Sweet pepper	3	10.5	6	9	4.5	3	10.5	6	4.5	7.5	
	Age	2 months	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6	
	Planting type	Organic	14	14	14	14	12.25	1.75	15.75	15.75	10.5	1.75	
Field conditions	Area	360 m2	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8	
	Labor	Specialist	3	3	3	3.5	3.5	3.5	4	3	2.5	4	
	Application availability	Backpack sprayer	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	6.25	7.5	7.5	3.75	6.25	7.5	
	Location	Green house	8.75	10	11.25	11.25	10	7.5	10	7.5	7.5	8.75	
Pest Conditions	Species	White flies	8.75	11.25	8.75	10	2.5	6.25	8.75	1.25	1.25	6.25	
	% infestation/plant	5	5.25	8.75	12.25	15.75	12.25	1.75	1.75	5.25	1.75	1.75	
	Infestation intensity/field	40	7	10.5	7	10.5	7	14	15.75	12.25	10.5	15.75	
	Infestation Season	Summer	3	7	5	7	6	5	5	3	3	6	
	Infested Plant stage	fruiting	1.25	10	10	11.25	2.5	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	
Total Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70	
Total			132	160.5	131	161	115.75	115	155.75	122.75	104.75	144.5	

Table (11): Result score of case I.

	Site conditions	Case conditions	Mechanical control		Biological control			Chemical control					
			Pruning	Remove weeds	Parasitoids	Predators	Micro-organisms	Chemical compounds	Mineral oils	Plant extracts	IGRs	Mixtures	
Case I	Plant conditions	Species	cucumber	3	10.5	6	9	4.5	3	10.5	6	4.5	7.5
		Age	1 month	5	6	6	7	7	5	8	5	5	6
		Planting type	Organic	14	14	14	14	12.25	1.75	15.75	15.75	10.5	1.75
	Field conditions	Area	360 m2	7	7	8	8	7	6	8	8	7	8
		Labor	Specialist	3	3	3	3.5	3.5	3.5	4	3	2.5	4
		Application availability	manual sprayer	1.25	1.25	8.75	10	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
		Location	Green house	8.75	10	11.25	11.25	10	7.5	10	7.5	7.5	8.75
	Pest conditions	Species	Aphids	7.5	11.25	6.25	8.75	7.5	8.75	8.75	6.25	3.75	8.75
		% infestation/plant	3%	5.25	8.75	12.25	15.75	12.25	1.75	1.75	5.25	1.75	1.75
		Infestation intensity/field	5%	14	15.75	12.25	12.25	14	12.25	15.75	8.75	8.75	12.25
		Infestation Season	Spring	3	6	4	5	2	1	1	1	1	1
		Infested Plant stage	Flowering	1.25	8.75	10	11.25	3.75	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
	Total Feasibility			64.75	61.25	38.5	52.5	35	52.5	59.5	50.75	43.75	70
	Total			137.75	163.5	140.25	168.25	120	105.5	145.5	119.75	98.5	132.25

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Population density of certain piercing sucking insects (Hemiptera) and common predators in relation to sowing dates of soybean at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate

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Abstract:

Soybean, *Glycine max* (L.) is attacked by many insect pests in the field, among them, are piercing-sucking insects, which cause damage directly by sucking plant juice or indirectly by transmission of diseases causative agent, the current work was to study the effect of two sowing dates (15th May and 30th May) of soybean on numbers of insects and common predators at the Farm of Sakha Agric. Res. Station, Kafr El-Sheikh during of 2019 and 2020, weekly counts showed four species of insects: *Aphis gossypii* (Glov.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae); *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae); *Empoasca* spp. (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) and *Nezara viridula* L. (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) on soybean plants. *B. tabaci* was the most dominant insect species. The common predatory insects were *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph.) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae), *Coccinella undecimpunctata* (L.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Orius interruptus* (Say) (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) and *Paederus alfieri* (Koch.) (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) in addition to true spiders. Soybean sown on 30th May harbored the highest number of the considered insects, while the least population occurred on 15th May; the populations were higher in the second season than in the first one except whitefly. Plants of 15th May and 30th May harbored significantly higher population of whitefly and green stink bug in the second season, while aphid and predators induced insignificant difference between two sowing dates. Seasonal means appeared significant differences of whitefly by first and second sowing dates, but, green stink bug harbored significantly higher differences in the first date, aphid and predators induced insignificant difference among two seasons. So, the differences in the insect population from season to another may be due to the differences in the prevailing weather factors and/or the existed natural enemies. However, the gained results are of importance in the development the control measures of insect pests in integrating management program in soybean fields.

Introduction

Soybean, *Glycine max* (L.) is one of the most important legume crops all over the world, as it shares with about 30% of the total world production of oil and more than 60% of the world production of high protein meal. Also, Soybean seeds contain about 18-24% oil, 30-50% protein and a considerable amounts of main amino acids, especially lysine as well as phosphorus, calcium and vitamins (A, B1, B2, B6, B12, B19 and C) which are important for human and animal feeding (Abou-Attia and Youssef, 2007 and Netam *et al.*, 2013). Soybean can fix a considerable amount of nitrogen of the soil and enrich soil fertility (Oerke and Dehne, 2004).

Soybean fields are attacked by a large number of arthropod pest species especially piercing-sucking insects. The most important of which are *Aphis gossypii* (Glov.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae); *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae); *Empoasca* spp. (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) and *Nezara viridula* L. (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) (El-Sarand, 2013 and Eissa, 2018). They cause damage in plant quality and quantity either directly by sucking plant juice or indirectly by transmission of the diseases causative agent (Iqbal *et al.*, 2008).

In Egypt, farmers still greatly depend on the insecticide application to control insect pests in soybean fields. Through the widespread and sometimes indiscriminate use of pesticides, a number of serious problems have arisen destruction of beneficial arthropods and development of pest resistance to many pesticides and disruption of the ecological system. Therefore, extensive and intensive research efforts are invested to minimize the undesirable effects by using safe practices. Among these measures, are cultural practices and safe compounds against insect pests (Dent, 1991 and Mensah *et al.*, 2005).

It is well known that the relation between the population sizes of the most serious insect pests and those of their associated natural enemies is an essential ecological process required for the regulation of insect population (Kogan and Herzog, 1980).

Therefore, this work was carried out at Sakha Agricultural Research Station Farm, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during two successive soybean growing seasons, 2018 and 2019 to study effect of two sowing dates on piercing sucking insects and common predators to find out `an excellent opportunity for developing the integrated pest control programs.

Materials and methods

A field experiment was conducted at the Experimental Farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, (A.R.C.), Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during two successive growing seasons of soybean, *G. max* 2019 and 2020 to evaluate the effect of two sowing dates of soybean, 15th and 30th of May on the population density of four piercing-sucking insects and common predators. For every sowing date, an area of about 1200 m² was divided into four plots and sown with soybean seeds Giza 111 variety. The normal cultural practices were applied without pesticide treatments throughout the whole growing season.

To determine the populations of aphids (Nymphs and adults), leafhoppers (Nymphs and adults) and whitefly (Adults), a weekly sample of 20 leaflets representing upper, middle and lower levels of plants was selected at random from each plot for every sowing date. The number of the considered insects was directly counted in the early morning. In the field using a suitable hand lens. The same leaflets were picked up and transferred into paper bags to the laboratory for examining and counting of the nymphal

stages of the whitefly by a binocular microscope.

As for the green stink bug and the common associated predators, a weekly sample of 10 plants was randomly selected from each plot. The numbers of the considered insects were counted directly and recorded in the field by the aid of lens 8 xs. The existed predators were *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph.) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) (Larvae), *Coccinella undecimpunctata* (L.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) (Larvae and adults), *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) (Nymphs and adults), *Orius interruptus* (Say) (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) (Adults) and *Paederus alfieri* (Koch.) (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) (Adults) and true spiders. The inspection began four weeks after sowing and continued till the end of the season.

The data of the means of the considered insects and the predators were statistically analyzed using t-test to compare the differences between them.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of soybean sowing dates on the population density of certain piercing-sucking insects and the common associated predators:

Data presented in Table (1) clear effect on two sowing dates of soybean (15th and 30th May) on the population density of piercing-sucking insects and the common predators in season of 2019. It was observed four insect species: aphids, *Aphis* spp.; whitefly, *B. tabaci*; leafhoppers, *Empoasca* spp. and green stink bug, *N. viridula* on the plants sown in the two dates. Also, five predatory insects were found: *C. carnea*, *C. undecimpunctata*, *Scymnus* spp. *O. interruptus* and *P.*

alfieri in addition to true spiders. Because of very low numbers of predators it was taken in consideration as total.

With regard to aphid *A. gossypii* the population started to appear on plants of 15th May in low numbers on the 30th Jun. with a mean of 3.00 insects /20 leaflets, then population increased gradually recording a peak of 21.50 insects/20leafles on 10th Sept. In the second sowing date, aphids appeared on 21st Jun. with a mean of 5.00 insects /20 leaflets, then, fluctuated recording a peak of 23.75 insects/20 leaflets on 3rd Sept.

As for the whitefly, *B. tabaci*, the population began to appear in low number by 14th and 30th Jun. on plants of the first and second sowing dates, then, the population increased gradually forming two peaks of abundance for the first and second sowing dates by Jul. 28th and August 5th, respectively. The first peak was represented by 183.25 and 200.00 insects / 20 leaflets for the first and second sowing dates, respectively, while the second peak recorded 459.25 and 460.25 insects by 21st Sept. and 10th Sept., respectively. After that, gradually decreased in the population occurred till the end of the season.

Regarding the leafhoppers, the results cleared that the insects appeared in relatively low numbers on June 14th (3.25 insects/20 leaflets) for the first sowing date and on June 21st by a mean of 3.25 insects /20 leaflets for the second sowing date. Then, population fluctuated during the season, recording high numbers on 26th and 12th August on plants of the first and second date with means of 20.50 and 22.50 insects/20 leaflets, respectively. After that, the population gradually decreased till the end of the growing season.

Table (1): population density of *Aphis gossypii*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Empoasca* spp., *Nezara viridula* and predators on soybean plants sown in two dates in season of 2019 at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

I.D.	Mean number/20 leaflets						Mean number/10 plants			
	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>		<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>		<i>Empoasca</i> spp.		<i>Nezara viridula</i>		Predators	
	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May
Jun. 14	0.00	0.00	7.00	33.25	3.25	0.00	0.25	0.00	4.00	7.50
Jun. 21	0.00	5.00	10.00	37.25	3.50	3.25	1.00	3.60	7.50	8.00
Jun. 30	3.00	5.75	20.25	64.25	5.50	4.00	1.50	2.00	11.00	6.75
Jul.7	5.25	8.50	33.25	108.00	6.50	5.75	3.25	2.50	10.00	8.25
Jul. 15	6.50	12.75	64.25	150.25	11.50	9.75	4.50	10.50	10.50	10.25
Jul. 21	7.50	11.00	93.50	160.25	10.00	11.50	5.75	10.00	11.00	9.25
Jul. 28	8.75	13.50	183.25	167.50	10.75	13.75	6.25	10.50	12.00	11.25
Aug. 5	10.75	14.25	165.00	200.00	10.50	15.00	7.25	11.50	12.00	11.50
Aug. 12	12.00	19.50	129.25	185.50	14.25	22.50	8.75	12.00	10.00	9.00
Aug. 19	15.00	20.00	150.25	200.75	15.00	17.00	3.25	13.00	12.75	12.00
Aug. 26	18.50	22.50	160.25	223.50	20.50	15.00	8.50	15.25	9.00	13.25
Sept. 3	19.50	23.75	185.50	294.45	15.00	7.75	9.50	16.50	9.50	12.00
Sept. 10	21.50	17.75	200.75	460.25	12.00	8.00	6.50	15.00	9.25	11.00
Sept. 17	11.50	13.00	294.50	321.50	4.75	6.75	12.50	6.00	9.00	9.75
Sept. 21	11.25	7.00	459.25	160.00	8.00	3.00	15.00	3.00	6.25	5.75
Sept. 28	8.00	5.00	322.50	150.50	6.75	2.75	5.00	3.50	4.00	4.50
Seasonal mean \pm SE*	9.94 \pm 0.49	12.45 \pm 0.19	154.92 \pm 2.18	182.33 \pm 2.77	9.86 \pm 0.16	9.11 \pm 0.08	6.17 \pm 0.33	8.43 \pm 0.20	9.23 \pm 0.19	9.38 \pm 0.20

SE*=Stander error I.D. Inspection date

Concerning of the green stink bug, *N. viridula*, the population firstly appeared on 14th and 30th Jun. for the first and second sowing dates, respectively. After that, the Population increased gradually recording two peaks on Aug.12th and Sept.17th by means of 8.75 and 15.00 insects/10 plants, respectively in first sowing dates, while one peak was formed on Sept. 3rd on plants of the second date by mean 16.50 insects/10 plants.

As for the common predators in soybean based on the total number of

the existed predators it was observed that the population started to appear by 14th Jun. on the plants of two dates. After that, the population suddenly increased forming one peak for first sowing date and the second one by 19th and 26th August in first and second sowing dates with means by 12.75 and 13.25 individuals/10 plants, respectively. *C. carnea* was the most dominant predator forming percent 28.79% and 30.58 of the total predators, while *O. interrupts* was least one by 6.12% and 5.33 of the total predators in

first and second sowing dates ,respectively .

Data presented in Table (2) show the population density of piercing-sucking and the common predators on the two sowing dates of soybean in season of 2020. It was observed four insect species and five predatory insects, in addition to true spiders. The same species were observed similar to the first season.

As for aphid, *A. gossypii* , appeared on soybean plants of the first date in relatively low numbers on 21st June by a mean of 1.00 insects /20 leaflets .After that, the population increased gradually to reach high levels recording peak on 16th of September with a mean of 37.00 insects/20 leaflets, while for the second sowing date aphids appeared on 21st Jun. (5.50 insects /20 leaflets), then fluctuated recording one peak (35.00 insects/20 leaflets) on 9th of September and continued decreased till the end of season.

With regard to the whitefly, *B.tabaci* , the population began to appear in moderate number by 14th Jun. on plants of the first and second sowing dates, then, the population gradually increased to record two peaks of abundance for every sowing date. The first peak took place by July 22nd for the first and second sowing dates by means of 110.50 and 234.00 insects/20 leaflets, respectively. The second peak occurred on plants on 19th and 26th Aug.in the first and second dates by means of 67.00 and 110.00 insects, respectively.

The results revealed that the plants of the two dates in season of 2019 as well as those of the second date in the season of 2020 harbored the highest number of populations with means of 154.92, 182.33 and 100.09 insects, respectively. The plants of the first dates in the season of 2019 received the lowest number by means of 50.85 insects. Also, the population density of the insect was

relatively higher during the first season than the second one.

As for, leafhoppers, *Empoasca* spp., the population appeared in relatively low numbers on June 14th by a mean of 3.00 insects/20 leaflets for the first sowing date and on June 21st by a mean of 3.25 insects / 20 leaflets for the second sowing date, then the population recorded the highest number of abundance on 9th and 23rd Sept. on the plants of the first and, second date with means of 19.50 and 21.25 insects/20 leaflets, respectively after that, the population declined gradually till the end of season. According to the seasonal mean throughout the study period, results revealed that plants of the second date harbored the highest number (13.91 insects / 20 leaflets) for the second seasons. On the other hand, the lowest number of the population (9.11 insects / 20 leaflets) took place on plants of second date for first seasons. Also, the population density of leafhoppers was higher in the second season than in the first one. Concerning of the green stink bug, *N. viridula* , started to appear on soybean plants of the two sowing dates on 14th June. The population of *N. viridula* increased gradually forming the highest number recorded two peaks on 22nd Jul. and 12th Aug. with means of 16.50 and 19.00 insects/10 plants, respectively in first sowing date ,while in second one was formed one peak on Aug.19th by means 15.50 insects/10 plants. After that, the population decreased till the end of the season. The population density of the insect was relatively higher in the second season than in the first one. The results revealed that the second sown plants in the first season were more preferable to infestation by *N. viridula* and first sowing plants in the second season.

As for, the common predators with piercing sucking insects, data cleared that the common predatory

complex fluctuated during the inspection period and the population started in moderate numbers by June 14th on plants of the first and second sowing dates, then, the population increased gradually forming one peak in first sowing date and in the second one by means of 19.00 and 16.25 individuals/10 plants by 12th and 26th August in first and second sowing

dates. *C. carnea* was the most dominant predator forming 29.11 and 41.63% of the total predators, while *O. interrupts* was least one by 7.12 and 2.02% of the total predators in first and second sowing date, respectively.

Table (2): Population density of *Aphis gossypii*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Empoasca* spp. , *Nezara viridula* and predators on soybean fields during season of 2020.

I.D.	Mean number/20leaflets						Mean number/10 plants			
	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>		<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>		<i>Empoasca</i> spp.		<i>Nezara viridula</i>		Predators	
	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May	15 th May	30 th May
Jun. 14	0.00	0.00	20.00	25.00	3.00	3.25	2.75	0.50	2.75	4.25
Jun. 21	1.00	0.00	30.00	45.25	3.75	4.25	6.25	1.00	6.25	7.00
Jun. 28	1.75	0.00	63.00	143.25	5.00	6.25	9.50	1.00	9.50	7.75
Jul.8	2.00	5.50	96.00	148.00	7.50	8.50	12.50	1.50	12.50	8.50
Jul. 15	3.00	8.75	100.00	158.25	12.75	15.75	13.25	2.50	13.25	10.00
Jul. 22	7.00	12.00	110.50	234.00	15.75	16.75	16.50	4.00	16.50	12.50
Jul. 29	8.00	15.50	59.50	54.00	14.00	16.00	11.50	7.00	11.50	12.75
Aug. 5	10.00	18.75	60.00	88.50	13.00	17.00	11.00	15.50	11.00	10.75
Aug. 12	10.50	20.00	65.00	90.00	13.00	15.00	19.00	12.00	19.00	14.50
Aug. 19	11.25	22.75	67.00	100.25	15.00	18.00	11.25	11.00	11.25	16.00
Aug. 26	13.00	25.00	60.00	110.00	16.00	16.00	12.50	5.00	12.50	16.25
Sep. 2	13.50	27.25	30.00	105.75	17.25	17.25	14.00	8.00	11.50	10.75
Sep. 9	22.75	35.00	20.75	100.00	19.50	19.50	13.75	5.00	13.75	8.75
Sep. 6	37.00	31.25	17.00	87.00	14.50	20.50	11.25	8.00	11.25	4.50
Sep. 23	32.00	29.00	12.00	71.67	10.00	21.25	10.25	9.00	10.25	10.75
Sep. 30	30.00	30.00	3.00	40.50	5.25	7.25	5.00	6.25	5.00	11.00
Seasonal mean ±SE*	12.67±0.23	17.55±0.72	50.85±1.02	100.09±2.20	11.58±0.44	13.91±0.39	11.27±0.65	6.08±0.12	11.11±0.82	10.38±0.98

SE*=Stander error I.D. Inspection dates

From the previous results, it can be concluded that, during the first season, the maximum density of aphids

and whitefly was nearly observed during the period from mid-July to end of September synchronizing with the

occurrence of higher population of the predators, while the leafhoppers and green stink bug attained its maximum density during the period from mid-August to end of September. Regarding the second season, the considered insects recorded maximum densities during the period from late July to mid-September synchronizing with the higher density of the associated predators. However, the interaction between the insects and their natural enemies is an essential ecological process that contributes the regulation of insect population (Dent, 1991). In general, results indicated that, sowing date of soybean had a significant effect on the population density of aphids, as the second sowing date (30th May) exhibited the highest densities of aphids, where the lowest densities of aphids took place on the first sowing date (15th May). Also, the population density of aphids was higher during the second season than the first one for the two sowing dates.

However, the aphid population greatly differed according to the sowing dates, 15th and 30th May. Results were in agreement with those of Karungi *et al.* (1999) who found that the early planting of soybean reduced aphid infestation. On contrast, Mousa (2004) revealed that soybean plants sown early on April 24th harbored the highest infestation levels of *Aphis* spp. as compared with those on May 11th. The results were agreeing with those of Abd El-Aty (2011), who studied the effect of two sowing dates; 15th May and 15th June on the infestation of soybean with *A. gossypii*. The total number of *A. gossypii* during the two sowing dates in the first season indicated that the difference was insignificant, while in the second season, the number of aphids was insignificantly higher in the first sowing date than in the second one. Also, El-Sarand (2013) found that soybean sown in early May harbored

the lowest numbers of *A. gossypii* population. Also, Results were agreement with those of Eissa (2018) she revealed that plants in mid -and late May received the highest number of aphids. These results are in agreement with those of Rizk *et al.* (1990b) who showed that infestation of soybean plants with *B. tabaci* increased with the later planting date (1st Jun.). Results agreeing with those of El-Sarand (2013), who found that soybean plants sown on the 1st of June harbored higher densities of *B. tabaci*, while the first sowing date (1st May) had the lowest numbers of insects during 2009 and 2010 seasons.

Also, the second sowing date exhibited moderate numbers. Kalyan and Ameta (2017) found that the mean population of whitefly in the first week of July was significantly higher than the third week of July during two seasons in India. Eissa (2018) revealed that the plants of the third date (30th May) harbored the highest numbers of *B. tabaci* during the first and second season, respectively. On the other hand, the lowest mean numbers took place on the plants of the first date (5th May) in both seasons.

In another hand, these results were contrasted with Rizk *et al.* (1990a) they found that soybean planted earliest (1st Apr.), had the highest infestation of *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli. Similar trend was reached by El-Sarand (2013), who found that soybean sown in early May harbored the lowest numbers of leafhoppers, while plants sown in late May received higher population. Also, Eissa (2018) revealed that plants were sown on 30th May harbored the highest number of leafhoppers for the first and second season and on contrast the plants sown 5th May.

On contrary, Rizk *et al.* (1990b) found that the soybean plants sown earliest (1st Apr.) had the largest infestation of *N. viridula*. These results

disagree with those of Adamu *et al.* (1999) who found that the sowing date of soybean did not significantly affect the infestation with *N. viridula*. Also, Gore *et al.* (2006) found that the earliest planting date (Late March-early April) had the lowest densities of stink bugs, whereas the latest planting date (Late May-early June) had the highest densities of stink bugs. The results agree with those of Gore *et al.*, (2006), who found that the earliest planting date (15th Apr.) of soybean had the lowest densities of stink bugs, whereas the late planting (5th Jun.) attract and harbored the highest densities of stink bugs. Also, Omoloye *et al.* (2015) found that *N. viridula* population was significantly higher at late planting date (25th Jul.) of soybean. Eissa (2018) found that the early sown plants (5th May) in the first season were more preferable to infestation by *N. viridula* and late sowing date (30th May) in second season.

With regard to, these results agree with obtaining data by Samhan (2003) who found *C. undecimpunctata*; *C. carnea*; the *P. alfieri* and unidentified species of true spiders in soybean fields during 2000, 2001 and 2002 growing seasons. El-Sarand (2005) in Egypt, found three predator species; *P. alfieri*, *C. undecimpunctata* and *C. carnea* in soybean fields during 1999 and 2000 seasons. *C. carnea* was the most dominant during the two study seasons, El-Sarand (2013) he recorded predator in soybean field; *C. carnea*, *C. undecimpunctata*, *P. alfieri* and *Scymnus* spp. during 2009 and 2010 seasons. Also, *C. carnea* was the most dominant species. Yadav *et al.* (2015) found that the predatory beetles began to appear on soybean field during 2010 season in the 2nd week of August and its population slightly increased and peaked at 63 days after sowing. The maximum population of predatory observed in 2nd week of July. Also, the

spiders appeared at 35 days after sowing, in the second week of August and its population slightly increased up to 49 days after sowing, thereafter a gradual reduction in the population was observed and finally disappeared after 77 days after sow.

However, varying the planting date of crops works as a mean of cultural control by creating asynchrony between crop phenology and the insect pests' phenology which can retard the rate of colonization (Ferro, 1987) or means that the pest fails to coincide with a critical crop growth stage (Dent, 1991). Also, such methods have a major impact if the planting dates were synchronized between farms within a region to reduce the variation in available crop stages. 2-Seasonal means of four piercing-sucking insects and common predators on soybean plants at two sowing dates during 2019 and 2020 seasons at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate. Results analysis in Table (3) cleared that the plants of 15th May and 30th May harbored significantly higher population of whitefly and green stink bug in second season than first one, while aphid and predators induced insignificant difference between the two sowing date also, leafhoppers harbored significantly population in second sowing dates of second season, while the mean numbers of green stink bug was significantly higher between first sowing dates in both seasons.

From the mentioned results ,during two seasons that the first and second sowing dates; whitefly recorded significantly differences, while leafhoppers appeared significant differences in the second sowing date, but, green stink bug harbored significantly higher differences in first sowing date ,while aphid appeared insignificant.

In general, the results indicated that soybean plants sown in 15th May received lower population of the

considered insects. Similarly, the population of insects was higher in the second season than in the first one except whitefly. However, the differences in the insect population from season to another may be due to

the differences in the prevailing weather factors and/or the existed natural enemies. Results will aid in planning programs of integrated control of soybean insect pests.

Table (3): Seasonal means of four piercing-sucking insects and common predators on soybean plants at two sowing dates during 2019 and 2020 seasons at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

Insect	Season	Sowing date		
		15 th May	30 th May	T-calculated
<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	2019	9.94	12.45	1.06 ^{n.s}
	2020	12.67	17.55	1.65 ^{n.s}
	T- calculated	0.82 ^{n.s}	1.47 ^{n.s}	
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	2019	154.92	182.33	0.66 ^{n.s}
	2020	50.85	100.09	3.18 ^{**}
	T- calculated	3.03 [*]	2.72 [*]	
<i>Empoasca spp.</i>	2019	9.86	9.11	0.38 ^{n.s}
	2020	11.58	13.91	1.18 ^{n.s}
	T- calculated	0.97 ^{n.s}	2.23 [*]	
<i>Nezara viridula</i>	2019	6.17	8.43	1.33 ^{n.s}
	2020	11.27	6.08	3.47 ^{**}
	T- calculated	3.54 ^{**}	1.35 ^{n.s}	
Predators	2019	9.23	9.38	0.16 ^{n.s}
	2020	11.11	10.38	0.55 ^{n.s}
	T- calculated	1.57 ^{n.s}	0.92 ^{n.s}	

T-tabulated =1.697 at 5% level, = 3 .042 at 1% level

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Preliminary occurrence of the sugar beet leaves looper worm *Scopula donovani* (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) and their predatory insects on sugar beet at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract:

The sugar beet leaves looper worm *Scopula donovani* (Distant) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) was recorded in Europe and caused severe damages to the infested crops. This study represents the first published record of *S. donovani* on sugar beet in Egypt. It was noticed for the first time on sugar beet plants (*Beta vulgaris* L, var. Kram) at the farm of Sakha Agriculture Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt. during the seasons, 2019/2020. The *S. donovani* insects as well as their associated predators; *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), *Paederus alfieri* Koch. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae), and *Chrysoperla carnea* Steph. (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *Syrphus corolla* Fabricius (Diptera: Syrphidae), were surveyed at seasons 2019/2020 and 2020/2021. The *S. donovani*, larvae started to appear in the 3rd week of Nov. 2019 and peaked at the 3rd week of Mar. 2020 (7 larvae/20 plants). In 2020-2021, the highest number was recorded in mid-January (9 larvae/20 plants). Based on the results of the simple-correlation coefficient, the larvae of *S. donovani* were significant correlation with *C. undecimpunctata*, *P. alfieri*, and *Scymnus* spp. and (r) values were 0.5, 0.5, and 0.5, respectively. In the second season, the insect positively correlated with *Scymnus* spp., *S. corolla*, with (r) values of 0.2, 0.06, respectively. Weather factors; temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall had a negative and insignificant effect on the insect population in the first season. Whereas the second season was highly significant with temperature, the combined effect of the studied factors on the insect population density was more pronounced in the second season than in the first one. Where EV% values were 30.8 and 46.3. However, the obtained results are very important in integrated sugar beet management programs to avoid damage to this insect in the future.

Introduction

The sugar beet leaves looper worm *Scopula donovani* (Distant) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae), geographical distribution within Africa:

Congo, Egypt, Gambia, Kenya, Madagascar, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, South Africa, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe, the main host

plant is Rice, *Oryza sativa* L. (Sihvonen, 2005).

Fifth instar larvae of *S. donovani* could eat all the leaves parts of sugar beet plants. *Scopula subpunctaria* (Herrich-Schaffer) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) is one of the most important defoliator insect pests attacking the tea trees in China (Zhang *et al.*, 2009 and Hu *et al.*, 2010). The 4th and 5th instar larvae of *Scopula subpunctaria* mainly could eat all the leaves (Tao Ma *et al.*, 2019).

Hermann and Legrand (2004) recorded *Autographa gamma* L. (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) as a major pest of sugar beet in Belgium. Control of sugar beet insect pests could be achieved through optimizing the cultural practices such as beneficial insects inhabiting sugar beet crops, and planting dates (Shalaby, 2001; Abo El-Naga, 2004; Amin *et al.*, 2008; Abou-ElKassem, 2010 and El-Dessouki, 2019).

In Egypt, some insect predators; e.g., coccinellids, Chrysopidae, and staphylinids were surveyed from sugar beet fields (Abo-Saied, 1987; Boraei *et al.* 1993; El-Agamy *et al.*, 1996 and El-Dessouki, 2019). Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) is a member of the family Chenopodiaceae is one of the most important sugar crops in the world. Sugar beet-grown areas in Egypt have been increased to 640.000 Fadden in 2020. Sugar crops (Sugar cane and sugar beet) receive great attention in Egypt because of their strategic and industrial values. Therefore, it is mandatory to increase the local sugar production to cope with the increasing population requirements.

The present work was outlined to evaluate the occurrence and population dynamics of the sugar beet leaves looperworm *S. donovani* and their associated predatory insects and weather factors under field conditions in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Laboratory experiment to the identification of the insect:

During season 2019/2020, the sugar beet leaves looperworm *S. donovani* larvae were collected in plastic gars from sugar beet fields at Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate and transferred to the laboratory at Plant Protection Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo. The larvae were maintained in the growth chambers under the condition of 26 ± 1 °C, and with a photoperiod regimen of (12 L: 12 D) and fed on sugar beet leaves until pupation. The pupae were individually put in the Petri dishes (d = 9 cm) for the emergence of adults. Emerged adults were transferred into plastic tubs to the laboratory for identification at the Department Classification, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center.

2. Field experiments:

Were carried out at the farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt, during seasons; 2019/ 2020 and 2020/ 2021. The experimental area was two feddans, divided into plots each of 2100m² and cultivated with sugar beet var. Karam in mid-September of both seasons. All recommended agricultural practices were followed during the growing season without insecticide applications.

3. Population fluctuations of *Scopula donovani* and its associated predators:

To study the seasonal fluctuation of population density of *S. donovani*, weekly samples consisting of 20 plants were taken randomly from four replicates, replicate size was 84 m² equivalent to 1/50 of feddan. These plants were visually examined in the field to count the larvae of the pests. Five insect predators were counted per plant; the number of eggs and larvae of

the green lacewing, and *Chrysoperla carnea* Steph. (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) larvae and adults of *Scymnus* spp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) and the eleven spotted lady-beetle, *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), adults of the rove beetle, *Paederus alfieri* Koch. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae), and larvae of syrphus fly, *Syrphus corolla* Fabricius (Diptera: Syrphidae), the weather factors: temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall were obtained from Meteorological Station of Sakha, Egypt.

4. Statistical analysis

SAS (SAS Institute, 2003) was used to determine the partial correlation and regression coefficient between the prevailing weather factors and the population of *Scopula donovani*. Significant differences between population means of insects, predatory insects on sugar beet plants were determined according to Duncan (1955).

Results and discussion

1. The looper worm *Scopula donovani* as a new insect pest on sugar beet:

The present study represents the first record of the looper worm, *S. donovani* attractive sugar beet plants (*Beta vulgaris* L.var. Kram) in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, Egypt. Sugar beet plants consider new host plant of *S. donovani* in Egypt during seasons 2019 /2020 and 2020 /2021 in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate The looper worm was noticed for the first time on sugar beet plants at the farm of the Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt, during the sugar beet growing season of 2019. In the subsequent season, the infestations increased heavily.

Photographs showing the infestation of *S. donovani* on leave

parts of sugar beet plants are shown in Figure 1. Larvae, pupa, and adults of *S. donovani* were observed on sugar beet leaves (Figure 1: A–D). The infestation started with a few individuals of *S. donovani* on the small leaves of the sugar beet plant, followed by their spread to the plant. The larvae feed on the plant leaves of the sugar beet plants are shown in Figure (1). where they eat the lower epidermis and the inner tissue, causing serious damage (Figure 1: A) and feed on the plant (Figure1:B). Pupae (Figure1: C).

Adults of this insect (Figure 1:D). These findings are similar to previously recorded symptoms Tao Ma *et al.* (2019) reported that the 1st and 2nd instar larvae of *Scopula subpunctaria* mainly damage the hypodermis and mesophyll, the 3rd instar larvae feed on the margin of leaves causing the shape of "C" and the 4th or 5th instar larvae could eat all the leaves.

Data presented in Figure (2) recorded the weekly mean temperature, relative humidity, and rain during seasons, 2019/2020 and 2020/2021.

These results are similar to previously Mesbah (1991) found that larvae of *Scopula* spp. were firstly recorded on sugar beet as a leaf feeder, a total season of eggs and larvae of *Scopula* spp. from April to May in 1988- 1989 season was 8 and 60 individuals in disouk region and 60 individuals during 1990 season in Sakha region at Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt. El-Dessouki (2019) served *Chrysodeixis gamma*, *Chrysodeixis chalcites*. and *Scopula coenosaria luridata* (Zeller), were from sugar beet plants. The presence of *S. donovani*, was recorded from the European continent for the first time, and the known distribution area of this taxon is extended to include Spain (Granada) (Gaston *et al.*, 2013).

Figure (1): Infestation of *Scopula donovani* larvae on leaf parts of sugar beet plants. A- B: Larvae on leaves, C: Pupae and D: Adult moth.

Figure (2): Mean of temperature (°C), R.H. (%) and ran fall (mm/day) in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate throughout the two successive seasons.

2. Population fluctuations of *Scopula donovani* in sugar beet fields:

Data represented in Figure (3) showed the population density of *Scopula donovani*, larvae started to appear at the 3rd week of Nov. 2019 (2 larvae/20 plants) and then disappeared after three weeks. The highest number was recorded in the 3rd week of Mar.

2020 (7 larvae/20 plants). In the second season, 2020- 2021 the first occurrence of larvae on sugar beet plants was recorded in the 3rd week of Nov. 2020 (3 larvae/20 plants) (Figure 2). The highest number was recorded at 2nd week of Jan. 2021 (9 larvae/20 plants).

Figure (3): Population fluctuation of *Scopula donovani* during (2019-2020) and (2020-2021) seasons.

Data presented in Table (1) showed the monthly average number of *S. donovani*, larvae during two seasons. the first season it can be noticed that, the highest monthly average number of *S. donovani* were recorded in March 2019 with an average number of 5.0 larvae. While the second season the highest monthly average number of *S. donovani* was recorded in Dec 2020 with an average number of 5.2 larvae. In Korea, Leech (1897) first recorded 11 species

of *Scopula*. Rahouma (2018) found that the tomato flower worm, *Scopula coenosaria luridata* (Zeller) is a harmful pest to tomatoes causes the falling of flowers and newly setting tomato fruits, in all regions of Egypt. Mohisen (2012) reported that *Autographa gamma* are common pests attacking sugar beet plants, from period Oct-May in total 20 and 60 larvae in the first and second season, respectively.

Table (1): Monthly average numbers of the sugar beet leaf loopermoth *Scopula donovani*, during 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 seasons.

Month	2019-2020	2020-2021
Nov.	0.6	3.6
Dec.	1.2	5.2
Jan	1.0	5.0
Feb	2.5	2.2
Mar.	5.0	2.0
Total	10.30	18.00
Mean ±S. E	2.0±0.8	3.60±0.67

3. Population fluctuations of insect predators associated with *Scopula donovani*:

3.1. Ladybirds, *Scymnus* spp.:

Data in Figure (4) showed that during 2019/2020 larvae and adults of *Scymnus* spp. the first appearance was recorded on 26 of Nov. (5 insects/20 plants) and existed till the end of the season (2 individuals /20 plants). The highest number (10 individuals /20 plants) was reached at 10 of Mar. 2020. In the 2021 season, the highest number (14 individuals /20 plants) was recorded on 6 of Jan. 2021 (Fig 5). These results are in agreement with these of Mesbah (1991) and El-Khouly (2006) reported that the population of coccinellids started to increase in March and April and reached their higher peaks in April and May.

3.2. The eleven spotted lady-beetle *Coccinella undecimpunctata* :

During 2019-2020 adult of *C. undecimpunctata* first appearance was recorded on 28 of Jan. (1 insect/20 plants). The highest number (10 individuals /20 plants) was reached at 25 of Feb. 2020 (Figure 4). In the 2021 season, the highest number (3 individuals /20 plants) was recorded on 27 of Jan. 2021 (Figure 5). Guirguis (1985) in Egypt found that the Coccinellid predators, *C.undecimpunctata* and *Cydonia vicina nilotica* var. appeared in sugar beet fields from April till June.

3.3. The green lacewing *Chrysoperla carnea* :

The chrysopid individuals in the first season started to appear on 19 of Nov. (6 individuals /20 plants) and remained until the end of the season (17 of Mar. 2020.) where the peak of eggs and the larval population was reached (19 individuals /20 plants) (Fig 4). In the second season, 2020- 2021 the first occurrence of eggs and larvae on sugar

beet plants was recorded on 18 of Nov. 2020 (7 individuals /20 plants). The highest number was recorded on 23 of Dec. 2020 (13 individuals /20 plants) (Figure 5). Mesbah (1991) reported that *C. carnea* exhibited 1-3 peaks of abundance in sugar beet fields. Talha (2001) at Dakahliya, recorded that the highest population of *C. Carnea*, *P. alfierii*, *Scymnus syriacus*, and *C. undecimpunctata* from the September plantation. Shalaby (2012) mentioned that the highest peak of *C. carnea* was (46 egg and larvae/40 plants) on November 25th. Three following peaks were recorded on January 15th (20), February 25th (35), and April 15th (13 eggs and larvae).

3.4. The rove beetle *Paederus alfierii* :

Data in Figure (4) also shows the first season of adult *P. alfierii* existence on sugar beet plants, the first one started on 19 of Nov. Two following peaks were recorded on 11 of February (6) and 3 of Mar. (8 adults/20 plants). The highest peak was recorded on 10 of Mar. 2020 (12 adults/20 plants). In 2020- 2021 the first occurrence of adult *P. alfierii* on sugar beet plants was recorded on 18 of Nov. 2020 (2 adults/20plants). The highest number at 16 of Dec. 2020 (3 adults/20 plants) (Fig 5). Guirguis (1985) in Egypt found that *Paederus alfierii* appeared in sugar beet fields from April till June. Shalaby (2001) stated that *Paederus alfierii* was encountered only from the October plantation at Kafr El Sheikh.

3.5. Syrphus fly *Syrphus corolla* :

In the first season, the larvae of *S. corolla* firstly occurred from a high peak at 21 Jan. 4 larvae/20 plants (Figure 4). In the second season, 2020-2021 the larvae of *S. corolla* started to bear on 20 of Jan.2021 (5 larvae/20 plants) (Figure 5). The highest peak was recorded on 27 of Jan. 2021 (13 larvae/20 plants). Bazazo and Besheit

(2020) demonstrated that *S. corolla* were important predatory insects in sugar beet fields during two seasons studies.

Figure (4): Population fluctuation of predatory insects on 20 sugar beet plants during the first season (2019-2020).

Figure (5): Population fluctuation of predatory insects on 20 sugar beet plants during the second season (2020-2021).

4. The relationship between the insect pests and predators:

The results of simple-correlation coefficient between larvae of *S. donovani* and predators' insects during 2019-2020 season in a Table (2) indicated that significantly effect with predators *C. undecimpunctata*, *P. alferii*, and *Scymnus spp.* and (r) values were 0.51, 0.539, and 0.512 respectively, whereas the relation was insignificant between *S. corolla* and *C. carnea* and insect population, (r) values were -0.18 and 0.13. The correlation between insect population and total

insect predators was a significant effect. While in the second season in Table (2) revealed that correlation analysis values were insignificant positive with (r) values were 0.05 and 0.15 between the insect population and *S. corolla* and *Scymnus spp.*, whereas, the relationship was insignificant. Negative with (r) values were -0.027 and -0.23 between the insect population and *C. undecimpunctata*, *P. alferii* insects. Correlation between the insect population and *C. carnea* insects was positive significant with (r) value -1.18. Correlation between the insect

population and total of insect predators was insignificant effect.

Table (2): Simple correlation analysis on the effect of insect predators in the population fluctuations of *Scopula donovani* during 2019- 2020 and 2020- 2021 seasons, September plantations.

Seasons	Factors	r	P
2019-2020	<i>Syrphus corolla</i>	-0.181	0.471
	<i>C. undecimpunctata</i>	0.51	0.039
	<i>P. alferii</i>	0.530	0.035
	<i>C. carnea</i>	0.136	0.588
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	0.512	0.044
	Total of predators	0.536	0.051
2020-2021	<i>Syrphus corolla</i>	0.057	0.920
	<i>C. undecimpunctata</i>	-0.027	0.843
	<i>P. alferii</i>	-0.239	0.199
	<i>C. carnea</i>	-1.186	0.063
	<i>Scymnus spp.</i>	0.158	0.780
	Total of predators	0.076	0.633

5. Effect of climatic factors on the population density of *Scopula donovani* insects:

The data of the simple correlation in the 2019- 2020 season, Table (3) showed that the relationship was an insignificant relationship between the insect population and daily mean of temperature, daily mean of rain and R.H. % with (r) values were -0.058, 0.11 and 0.53 respectively. On the other hand, the regression coefficient analysis cleared that the relationship was insignificant negative with a daily mean of temperature and insignificant positive with R.H% and daily mean of rainfall (b) values were 0.029, 0.058, and 0.043 insects respectively. The combined effect was 30.8%. in the 2020-2021 season, Table (3) cleared

that the relationship was a significant relationship between the insect population and daily mean of temperature and (r) value were 0.618, whereas the relation was insignificant between the daily mean of R.H.% and rainfall with (r) values were 0.438 and -0.239 respectively. On the other hand, the regression coefficient revealed that the relationship was significantly positive with the daily mean of temperature and the insect population, whereas the relationship was insignificant between the daily mean of R.H% and rainfall with (b) values were 0.719, 0.180, and -0.235 insects respectively. The combined effect of the climatic factors, predators, and the insect population was 46.3%.

Table (3): Statistical parameters of sugar beet leaves loopermoth *Scopula donovani* population in relation to certain weather factors, predatory insects on sugar beet plants during 2020 and 2021 seasons, September plantations.

Seasons	Factors	r	B	E.V%
2019-2020	Temp. °C	-0.050	-0.029	30.8%
	R.H. %	0.111	0.058	
	Rain fall	0.053	0.043	
	Predators	0.536**	0.105**	
2020-2021	Temp. °C	0.618**	0.719**	46.3%
	R.H.%	0.438	0.180	
	Rain fall	-0.239	-0.235	
	Predators	0.076	0.023	

(r) = correlation coefficient (b) = regressions coefficient

** High significantly EV=explained variance R.H.= relative humidity

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Role of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* as a biological control agent for the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Tephritidae : Diptera) under laboratory conditions

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Abstract:

Fungal pathogens are recognized as biological control agents that are increasingly replacing the chemical compounds for controlling fruit flies. The present study aimed to determine the effects of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) against *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Tephritidae : Diptera). In addition, the effects of *B. bassiana* on *in vivo* activity of polyphenol oxidase (PPO) and phenol oxidase (PO) enzymes of *C. capitata* pupae were determined. The toxicity results of *B. bassiana* fungus exhibited mortality of 2.5-12.5% in the pupal stage. Mortality in adult flies is steadily increased, reaching 96.79 and 97.22% on the 35th and 32nd days with 0.88 and 1.75 g/L of fungus treatment. The biochemical analysis of PO and PPO enzymes activity in *C. capitata* pupae showed an increase in enzyme activity with the increase of the fungal concentration and post-treatment duration. This information can aid in pest management in integrated and organic orchards.

Introduction

Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is a key pest of fruits in the Mediterranean basin that has a worldwide distribution. Globally, this fly attacks more than 250 species of fruits and vegetables (Morales *et al.*, 2004). Its economic importance is due to the direct damage caused by ovipositing of the females to the host fruit and the larvae feeding on the fruit. Control of *C. capitata* can be conducted on the adult fly (Aerial treatment with chemical insecticides, sterile

insecticides, chemosterilants, mass trapping, oviposition deterrence) or soil larvae and pupae (Terrestrial treatment with chemical insecticides) (Navarro-Llopis *et al.*, 2004; Rendon *et al.*, 2006 and Ekesi *et al.*, 2007). The heavy application of conventional insecticides against *C. capitata*, may cause serious ecological problems (Magana *et al.*, 2008), as the resistance development of the field strain of *C. capitata* (El-Gendy, 2017).

So, several efforts have been made to restrict the use of harmful insecticides by using safer alternative

approaches to control *C. capitata*. Entomopathogenic fungi play a significant role in the natural biological products for many insects (McCoy *et al.*, 1988). The importance of fungi in the control of insects was noticed by ancient Chinese (Roberts and Humber, 1981). Thus, environmentally compatible strategies for managing *C. capitata* populations have been developed, including using entomopathogenic fungi as one of the biological control agents (Castillo *et al.*, 2000) as *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) (Ascomycota: Cordycipitaceae) (Beris *et al.*, 2013).

B. bassiana is widely spread and considered a natural enemy of a wide variety of insects and arachnids (Roberts and St Leger, 2004). *B. bassiana* is the only insect pathogens infecting their hosts by direct penetration of the cuticle, showing promising perspectives for the *C. capitata* control against pupae in the soil (Soil inoculation) (Garrido-Jurado *et al.*, 2011). *B. bassiana* was a safe bio-control organism in an application that has been assessed based on its impacts on non-target insects and mammals, including humans (Zimmermann, 2007).

On the other hand, entomopathogenic fungi were observed to produce several proteases that degrade insect cuticles (Samuels and Paterson, 1995). A broad variety of trypsin, chymotrypsin, elastases, collagenase, and chymoelastase was described (Smith and Grula, 1982) as a liability for insect cuticular deterioration (St Leger, 2008).

The current work aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *B. bassiana* as a soil application against *C. capitata* larvae, as well as the fungus effect on the activity of peroxidase and phenol oxidase enzymes.

Materials and methods

1. Insect rearing:

Adult fly of *C. capitata* was raised in wooden cages (30 x 30 x 30 cm), provided with a food medium (Dry yeast: sugar 1:3), and saturated sponge of water as a source of water in Petri dishes. Eggs were allowed to fall into a water reservoir located beside the base of the cage. The eggs were collected daily from the water reservoir and added to the larval artificial diet which consisted of wheat bran (96.8 g), sugar (64.8 g), dry yeast (9.07 g), citric acid monohydrate (2.4 g) sodium benzoate (2 g) and tap water (200 ml) according to Tanaka *et al.* (1969).

2. Virulence assay of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* against *Ceratitis capitata* :

The microbial insecticide, *B. bassiana* fungus (WP 2.5%, 2.3×10^8 conidia/gm) was carried out against the 3rd larval instar of *C. capitata*. *B. bassiana* was get from Bioinsecticides Production Unit, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt. The experiments were carried out in plastic cups (250 cm³) closed at the top with a cloth net (1 mm mesh). The cups contained 75 gm of sterilized sand, which had been autoclaved at 105 °C for 24 hours. *B. bassiana* was assayed in six fungal concentrations, 0.75, 1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, and 20 gm/l, and the control treatment was treated with water only. Ten ml of fungal suspension per replicate were added to the soil by the pipette. One hundred of the full-grown larvae of *C. capitata* were used per each concentration (Treatments) in five replicates, 20 larvae each. Popped larvae were transferred to the cups and freely allowed to pupate in the fungus-treated soil. At 2, 4, and 6-days post-treatment, the treatments were inspected, and the dead pupae were recorded. On the 7th day, the pupae were transferred to Petri dishes until emerged flies. Emerged flies were transferred to plastic cups (250 cm³)

covered with a cloth net, provided with a source of food and water as described above. The dead flies were removed daily to Petri dishes containing a wet filter paper. Petri dishes were sealed with Parafilm® and kept in a room at 26°C to promote the growth of the fungus on the dead bodies to confirm that fungus infection was the cause of death (Ekesi *et al.*, 2002).

3. Determination of lethal concentration (LC50):

The dose-mortality relationship is determined for the concentration that showed the virulence against fruit fly of >0 and <100 % mortality. The concentrations evaluated were between 0.75 -20 gm/L of 2.3×10^8 conidia/ml. This procedure was repeated with five batches of flies, and the lethal concentrations of each replicate were used for statistical comparisons. LC50 was calculated according to Finney (1971) using the Ldp-Line program (Bakr, 2007).

4. Enzyme preparation:

For biochemical determination of detoxification enzymes, the 3rd larval instar of *C. capitata* was exposed to *B. bassiana* concentrations (As mentioned above) of 1.25, 2.5, 5, and 10 gm/l, in 3 replicates each. About 20 larvae were used for each replicate. After 2-, 4- and 6-days of exposure, pupae were homogenized in 1000 µl chilled phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 6.5), containing 0.01% (w/v) of triton X-100. The crude homogenate was centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 5 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was collected and used further as an enzyme source for the biochemical estimation of peroxidase (PO) and polyphenol oxidase (PPO) enzymes. Untreated flies were used as control.

5. Assay of phenol oxidase (PO) activity :

The activity of PO was assessed by mixing 500 µl of a sample with 2 ml of Tris-HCl solution (pH 6.5) and then

incubated at 30 °C for 3 min. PO activity was measured with a spectrophotometer (PG instrument T80 UV/VIS spectrometer) at 420 nm (Ishaaya, 1971).

6. Assay of polyphenol oxidase (PPO) activity:

PPO activity was assessed by mixing 200 µl of the sample with 1.5 ml of Tris-HCl solution (pH 6.5) and then incubated at 30 °C for 2 min. PPO activity was measured with a spectrophotometer (PG instrument T80 UV/VIS spectrophotometer) at 495 nm (Ishaaya, 1971).

7. Statistical analysis:

The corrected mortality percentages were corrected through Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925), after which LC50 is estimated by Probit analysis. All experiments were completely randomized designs; mortality data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and enzyme data were subjected to two-way analysis of variance using CoStat Software (2008) Version 6.4. Means were compared by a Tukey-Kramer test at a 5% probability level where significant differences existed between them.

Results and discussion

1. Virulence assay of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* against *Ceratitis capitata* :

Six fungal concentrations of *B. bassiana*, 0.75, 1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, and 20 gm/L, were assayed on the full-grown larvae of *C. capitata* by soil treatment application. Results in Table (1) show no infectious symptom in the pupal stage of *C. capitata* until the 5-days of treatment. On the 6th day of pupal age, *B. bassiana* exhibited little mortality effects ranging from 2.5 to 12.5%, with the tested fungal concentrations ($F=2.86$, $p=0.04$).

Adults' mortality was observed from the outset. With increasing the

flies' age and fungal concentrations, the flies' mortality rates were steadily increased, which statistically were significant among the different fungal concentrations within each time of post-treatment. On the 8th day, flies' mortality reached < 50% with treatment by 20gm/L of *B. bassiana* ($F=18.92, p=0.0001$). The fly mortality increased with elapsed time to reach < 90% on the 23rd day with fungal concentrations of 10 and 20 gm/L ($F=6.09, p=0.0018$), to achieve elimination for the fly at the 28th day of fly age with respective fungal concentrations of 5, 10 and 20 gm/L ($F=14.67, p=0.0001$). While the concentrations of 2.5 and 1.25 gm/L eliminated the fly at the 32nd and 35th day of the adult age.

The results in Table (2) indicated that LC50 values of the fungus were not registered at the 2nd and 4th-day post-treatment of *C. capitata* pupae, it was recorded on the 6th day with 1115.78 mg/L. LC50 value in the pupal stage was higher than that in the adult flies (589.82-0.007 mg/L). On the 2nd day of adult age, LC50 was 589.82 mg/L, which decreased by increasing time of treatment; On the 5th day of the adult fly age, LC50 decreased by about 7.11 times than those on the 2nd day. A Similar trend was achieved with LC50 reduction of 52.213, 399.592, 2027.822, 40701.286, and 71227.25 times at 8, 13, 18, 23, and 28 days of treatment of that on the 2nd day of the adult stage, respectively.

2. Biochemical assay of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* against *Ceratitis capitata* :

2.1. Specific activity of phenol oxidase enzyme:

Results presented in Table (3) indicate that biochemical assay for a specific activity (SA) of PO enzyme in *C. capitata* pupae increased with increasing the tested fungal concentrations and time post-treatment.

The highest SA of PO value (General mean \pm SE) in pupae was 1.74 μ m/gm protein/min when the *C. capitata* larvae are processed at 10 gm/L of fungus. PO activity declined by decreasing the fungal concentration to 1.44, 1.20 and 0.92 μ m/gm protein/min at 5, 2.5 and 1.25 gm/L fungal treatments, respectively, compared to 0.34 μ m/gm protein/min for control treatment ($F=10884.86, df=4, p=0.0000$). For PO activity at different days post-treatment, PO was the lowest in the SA (1.094 μ m/gm protein/min) at the 6th day of the pupal age, which was significantly differed from those at the 4th (the highest activity; 1.148 μ m/gm protein/min) and the 2nd day (1.144 μ m/gm protein/min) ($F= 58.76, df=2, p= 0.0000$). The SA of the PO enzyme ratio was increased by treating *C. capitata* larvae with increasing concentrations of *B. bassiana* fungus by 2.71, 3.54, 4.25, and 5.13-fold at the fungal concentrations of 1.25, 2.5, 5, and 10 g/L of that of the control treatment, respectively. Significant differences were observed between SA values of PO recorded at both treatments and at times post-treatment, followed by high interaction between fungi treatments and elapsed times of treatment ($F= 9.54, df=8, p= 0.0000$).

2.2. Specific activity of polyphenol oxidase enzyme:

The SA of the PPO enzyme of *C. capitata* pupae was found to be directly related to the fungal concentrations (Table 4). Results show an increase in the SA of the enzyme (general mean \pm SE) at the tested fungal concentrations (1.25, 2.5, 5, and 10 g/L) along inspected dates (2, 4, and 6 days). The lowest specific activity was 0.44 μ m/gm protein/min at 1.25gm/l of fungus which increased significantly with the increase of the fungal concentrations of 2.5, 5 and 10 gm/l that significantly recorded 0.54, 0.73 and

0.93 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ protein/min, respectively, compared to 0.353 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ for the control one ($F= 14277.69$, $df=4$, $p= 0.0000$). The SA of PPO increased by 1.25, 1.54, 2.07, and 2.65-folds of the untreated one at the tested concentrations, respectively. The general mean of SA of the enzyme for all fungal concentrations at the tested times showed that at the 2nd day (0.58 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ protein/min) of treatment was lower than the other tested days; the 4th day (0.60 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ protein/min) and 6th day (0.62 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ protein/min) with significant differences between the treatments ($F= 122.3$, $df=2$, $p= 0.0000$), followed by a remarkable interaction effect between treatments and inspected time on SA of PPO enzyme ($F= 9.77$, $df=8$, $p= 0.0000$).

The present work was planned to assess the efficacy of the fungus *B. bassiana* on the pupal stage of *C. capitata* and their extended effect on the adult stage. The bioassay of *B. bassiana* treatments of fungus against the *C. capitata* was carried out under laboratory conditions of $25^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2.0$ and $70\%\pm 5.0$ R.H. Results of Qazzaz *et al.* (2015) showed that temperature dramatically influenced *B. bassiana* growth and development, with differences observed between the isolates. All the isolates failed to grow and develop at temperatures below 10°C and above 30°C . Furthermore, several investigators have reported that the optimum temperatures for *B. bassiana* mycelial growth, conidial germination, sporulation, and virulence are in the range $20\text{--}30^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Dimbi *et al.*, 2004 and Tefera and Pringle, 2003).

The present results didn't show any impacts on the pupal stage of *C. capitata* up to the age of five days, On the 6th day of the pupal stage, *B. bassiana* exhibited little mortality effects 2.5-12.5% in parallel with the fungal concentration., the results of Imoulan and Elmeziane

(2014) showed that all isolates of *B. bassiana* were able to infect the larval stage of *C. capitata* and caused a significant reduction in adult emergence.

However, *B. bassiana* caused a large mortality rate in puparia ranging from 65 to 95 %. The mortality of adult fly, *C. capitata* from the outset, increases with the increase of the fungal concentration of *B. bassiana* and increase of the flies' age. The higher fungal concentration of 5, 10, and 20 gm/L, had clear mortality effects that began on the 13th day of the fly's age reached 79.17% to eliminate the fly at the 28th day of the adult stage with fungal concentrations of 5, 10, and 20 gm/L. Also, there were responsive mortality percentages at the lower fungal concentrations of 0.75, 2.5, and 1.25 gm/L, to exterminate the fly with respective concentrations at the 37th, 35th, and 32nd days of treatments.

The obtained results confirmed the results of Qazzaz *et al.* (2015) who indicated that *B. bassiana* isolates induced significant mortality (58% - 100%) to adult *C. capitata* flies, depending on the isolate and inoculum concentration used. Similar results were obtained by Konstantopoulou and Mazomenos (2005) who found that *B. bassiana* induced 85.6% mortality in a *C. capitata* population but was less effective against *Bactrocera oleae*. Similarly, Munoz (2000) evaluated the pathogenic potential of 16 strains of *B. bassiana* against adult *C. capitata* flies and reported a mortality range of 20% - 98.7%. Castillo *et al.* (2000) exhibited 100% mortality in *C. capitata* adults. Also, Atia (2018) reported 47.08-70.98% mortality in *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) treated with 1-4gm/L of *B. bassiana*. However, the results showed 37.75-55.02 mortality in the pupal stage treated with 1-4gm/L.

Results showed that the pupal stage was more tolerant to the fungal

insecticide than adults fly. Furthermore, LC50 values of *B. bassiana* for *C. capitata* decreased by increasing the time of treatment. LC50 value in the *C. capitata* pupae was more 1.89 times higher than that in the adult stage at 2 days old. The LC50 values of adult fly ranged from 569.8 to 0.008 gm/l (As a log concentration) with obvious differences at the tested times; 2, 5, 8, 13, 18, 23, and 28 days post-treatment, respectively. Such LC50 value was strongly decreased with a reduction ratio of 71227.25- fold. Similar results were obtained by Quesada-Moraga *et al.* (2006), who found that lethal concentrations (LC50) for *C. capitata* of the four most virulent isolates fungus ranged from 4.9×10^5 to 2.0×10^6 CFU/mL, with LT50 ranging from 4.6 to 5.3 days. In addition, Mwamburi *et al.* (2010) reported that the LC50 of 34 *B. bassiana* isolates against adult house flies (*Muscadomestica* L.; Diptera, Muscidae) ranged between 103 - 105 conidia/mL.

The findings of the biochemical assay of PO enzyme activity in *C. capitata* pupae exhibited an increase by increasing the fungal concentrations of *B. bassiana*, also as increasing the

times tested with high activity of 551.11 $\mu\text{m/gm}$ protein/min in treating flies with 0.88 gm/L. PO enzyme maybe play an essential role in the immunity of the insects to infections. Active PO catalyzes quinones formation that submits to additional melanin-forming reactions (Nappi and Christenson, 2005) that helps the larvae integument hardness of epidermis epithelial cells as a protective mechanism for fungal invasion. These results are supported by the results of Atia (2018), who mentioned that the PO activity in full-grown larvae of *Bactrocera zonata* treated with *B. bassiana* increased to 1.5 folds of control, which increased to 12 folds after 7 days of treatment. The same trend of PPO enzyme activity in *C. capitata* pupae was obtained, where the activity of the PPO enzyme was directly related to the fungal concentrations as well as time post-treatment.

This study concluded the high effects of *B. bassiana* in *C. capitata* control under laboratory conditions. This information could be helpful in pest management in integrated and organic orchards.

Table (1): Cumulative mortality percentages of medfly, *Ceratitis capitata* treated with fungus, *Beauveria bassiana* in the larval stage under laboratory conditions.

Fungus concentration (gm/l)	Corrected mortality percentages (mean ± SE)												
	Post-processing inspection (days)												
	Pupae			Adults									
	2	4	6	2	5	8	13	18	23	28	32	35	37
0.75	00±00	00±00	02.50±1.48 _c	02.50±1.90 _c	15.00±0.90 _d	20.51±0.58 _d	44.72±1.16 _c	62.55±8.46 _c	78.89±1.43 _c	86.38±0.82 _c	91.32±0.84 _a	96.97±0.58 _a	100±0.00
1.25	00±00	00±00	02.50±1.50 _c	07.50±1.43 _{bc}	12.50±0.43 _d	17.93±0.58 _d	52.50±1.73 _{bc}	71.67±.32 _{bc}	81.39±0.58 _{bc}	89.16±0.91 _{bc}	97.22±0.19 _a	100±0.00 _a	-
2.5	00±00	00±00	05.00±1.61 _{bc}	10.00±3.58 _{abc}	17.50±0.58 _d	23.08±1.29 _d	57.78±1.16 _b	74.90±7.18 _{bc}	84.16±0.29 _{bc}	91.94±0.01 _b	100±0.00 _a	-	-
5.0	00±00	00±00	05.00±1.59 _{bc}	12.50±2.02 _{ab}	22.50±1.00 _{bc}	38.46±1.16 _c	60.28±1.16 _b	78.37±2.53 _{ab}	89.17±0.58 _{ab}	100±0.00 _a	-	-	-
10.0	00±00	00±00	10.00±0.00 _{ab}	15.00±2.59 _{ab}	25.00±0.59 _b	48.72±0.79 _b	73.33±1.16 _a	84.62±.32 _{ab}	94.72±0.58 _a	100±0.00 _a	-	-	-
20.0	00±00	00±00	12.50±2.20 _a	17.50±2.50 _a	40.00±1.01 _a	61.54±2.36 _a	79.17±1.27 _a	90.53±3.22 _a	97.50±0.44 _a	100±0.00 _a	-	-	-
LSD _{0.05}	-	-	7.21	8.57	6.78	9.94	12.87	15.17	8.97	4.8	9.85	7.34	-

Means followed by the same letter (s) are not significantly different at 0.05 of probability.

LSD_{0.05}: Least significant difference at 5%.

Table (2): LC₅₀ and statistical analysis parameters of the chronic toxicity of *Beauveria bassiana* fungus against the medfly *Ceratitis capitata* under laboratory conditions.

Parameter	Acute toxicity post-treatment (day)							
	Pupae	Adults						
	6	2	5	8	13	18	23	28
LC ₅₀ (mg/L)	1115.78	589.818	80.126	10.913	1.426	0.281	0.014	0.008
Ratio	0	1.0	7.11	52.21	399.59	2027.82	40701.286	71227.25
χ ²	0.337	0.848	1.39	1.695	0.385	0.25	0.032	2.95
χ ² tabulated	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	3.8
Slope ± SE	0.65±0.29	0.59±0.244	0.61±0.20	0.93±0.19	0.68±0.18	0.67±0.21	0.61±0.30	0.40±0.24

LC₅₀: concentration producing 50% mortality; χ²: Chi square; Slope ± SE; Standard Error of the concentration-mortality regression line.

Table (3): Specific activity of peroxidase (PO) in pupae of medfly, *Ceratitis capitata* treated with fungus, *Beauveria bassiana*.

Fungus concentration (gm/l)	SA ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg protein}/\text{min}$)			General mean \pm SE	Ratio
	Time post-treatment (day)				
	2	4	6		
1.25	0.936 \pm 0.003	0.936 \pm 0.007	0.889 \pm 0.006	0.92 \pm 0.31 ^d	2.71
2.50	1.230 \pm 0.007	1.240 \pm 0.003	1.140 \pm 0.006	1.20 \pm 0.41 ^c	3.54
5.00	1.476 \pm 0.004	1.447 \pm 0.023	1.411 \pm 0.002	1.44 \pm 0.59 ^b	4.25
10.00	1.757 \pm 0.007	1.777 \pm 0.008	1.683 \pm 0.015	1.74 \pm 0.49 ^a	5.13
Control	0.327 \pm 4.60	0.340 \pm 0.26	0.351 \pm 0.04	0.34 \pm 0.12 ^e	1.00
General mean \pm SE	1.144 \pm 0.45 ^a	1.148 \pm 0.46 ^a	1.094 \pm 0.44 ^b	-	-

Means followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different according to L.S.D.; L.S.D. for con.= 0.015. L.S.D. for date=0.011; SA: specific activity; $\mu\text{M}/\text{mg protein}/\text{min}$

Table (4): Specific activity of polyphenol oxidase (PPO) in pupae of medfly, *Ceratitis capitata* treated with fungus, *Beauveria bassiana*

Fungal concentration (gm/l)	SA ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg protein}/\text{min}$)			General mean \pm SE	Ratio
	Time post-treatment (day)				
	2	4	6		
1.25	0.425 \pm 0.001	0.433 \pm 0.002	0.467 \pm 0.001	0.442 \pm 0.007 ^d	1.25
2.50	0.516 \pm 0.003	0.542 \pm 0.003	0.573 \pm 0.004	0.543 \pm 0.009 ^c	1.54
5.00	0.723 \pm 0.001	0.734 \pm 1.330	0.733 \pm 25.39	0.730 \pm 0.006 ^b	2.07
10.00	0.914 \pm 0.001	0.939 \pm 0.006	0.952 \pm 0.006	0.934 \pm 0.002 ^a	2.65
Control	0.344 \pm 0.001	0.352 \pm 0.002	0.363 \pm 0.004	0.353 \pm 0.003 ^e	1.00
General mean \pm SE	0.584 \pm 0.06 ^c	0.600 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.618 \pm 0.05 ^a	-	-

Means followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different according to L.S.D.; L.S.D. for con= 0.006., L.S.D. for time=0.004; SA: specific activity; $\mu\text{M}/\text{mg protein}/\text{min}$

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Efficacies of some commercial insecticides on leaf spot disease of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) in Ishiagu, Southeast Nigeria

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Abstract:

Three years experiments were carried out at the Research and Teaching Farm of Federal College of Agriculture, Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, during 2016, 2017 and 2018 cropping seasons to evaluate the effect of some insecticides on leaf spot disease of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). The experiments were fitted into Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four treatments replicated three times. The various insecticides with different trade names used as treatments were Lambda-cyhalothin sold as Lara Force gold, dimethoate 40% EC sold as Dime Force, chlorpyrifos 48% EC sold as Act Force and zero treatment (Control). Data were collected on plant height, number of leaves and number of infected leaves at 100 days after planting, number and weight of pods at harvest. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis of variance and significant treatment means separated at the 5% level of probability. Results obtained revealed that the treatments did not have any significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on the growth parameters but reduced significantly ($P < 0.05$) the number of infected leaves in 2016, 2017 and 2018. The number and weight of pods were significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased in 2016, 2017 and 2018 when compared with plants in the control plots. Lambda-cyhalothin performed better than other treatments in the reduction of disease incidence and concomitant increase in the yield parameters of groundnut.

Introduction

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is an important food and forage crop because of its high protein and oil content. Its seed is used as a source of cooking oil and in confectionery products for human consumption (Naab and Smart, 2005 and Nutsugah and Mecutcheon, 2007).

It is one the most popular and universal crops cultivated in so many

countries, but mainly Asia, Africa and America (FAO, 2007). Groundnut is one of the crops grown due to its nutrient value. It can be transformed from one form to another for both human and animal consumption. Groundnut hay vine is a nitrous animal feed, particularly for in the subsequent dry season when green forage is not available. In addition, groundnut seed and hay are often sold in local markets,

providing income to the source poor farmers (Naab and Smart, 2005).

Fungi affect the leaves, which go a long way to reducing the growth and yield of the groundnut. Reduced yield as high as 37% in groundnut is being observed in Nigeria almost annually due to leaf spot disease. In Nigeria, leaf spot and rosette virus are the most serious damaging diseases of groundnut (Alabi *et al.*, 2001). Worldwide loses as high as 50% of the seed yield and even higher for haulms due to *Cercospora arachidicola* and *Cercospora personata* have been reported by Dewaele and Swanevelde (2001).

Use of various fungicides to control fungal diseases has been the normal practice in groundnut producing areas, but resistance to the fungicides has been observed with increased yield losses annually. However, spraying with fungicides is required to achieve optimal yields during most years (Bailey, 2002).

Ogwulumba *et al.* (2008) posited that *Cercospora* leaf spot is the most important foliar diseases of groundnut in the world. In order to curb the increased resistance of this disease and yield losses, some insecticides commercially sold in the markets were evaluated for their efficacies against leaf spot diseases in addition to their insecticidal properties.

This development has therefore necessitated the need to evaluate their respective efficacies in the control of leaf spot disease and their effects on the growth and yield of groundnut in a three year trial.

Materials and methods

The experiments were carried out at the Research and Teaching farm of Federal College Agriculture Ishiagu, Ebonyi State during 2016, 2017 and 2018 cropping seasons. The site lies within a longitude of 72 °E and latitude 5 °N in the derived savannah zone of

south eastern Nigeria. It has an annual temperature of 27 °C (Minimum) and 33 °C (Maximum) with an average relative humidity of 88% and annual rainfall between 1600 mm and 2000 mm (FCAI, 2015).

The experiment was laid on Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), with four treatments replicated three times in each year. The experimental sites measured 10 m X 10 m giving the total land area of 100 m² in each year. In each year, the experimental site was cleared, ploughed mechanically and divided into three blocks and twelve plots with each block measuring 1m apart, 0.5m between plots and each plot size was 2 m X 2 m. Samnut 10 varieties which is an erect type of groundnut was used for the research.

Two seeds were sown per hole and later thinned down to one, three weeks after germination with spacing of 40 cm X 40 cm. Twenty- five (25) plants were maintained in each plot. Weeding was done manually using a weeding hoe as the weeds arose to minimize weed interference. The insecticides used as treatments were: Lambda-cyhalothin with trade name Lara Force gold, dimethoate 40% EC with trade name Dime Force and chlorpyrifos 48% EC with the trade name Act Force.

The insecticides were applied according to manufacturers' specifications as obtained from the labels. Plots without insecticide application served as control. Sixteen (16) plants were randomly selected in each plot for data collection. Data were collected on plant height (By using a measuring tape from the soil to the apex of the plant), number of leaves (By counting the number of the main leaves produced by the plant) and leaf disease incidence (By counting the number of plants with disease symptoms) at 100

days after planting, number of pods and weight of pods at harvest.

Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significant treatment means were separated using Least Significant Difference (L.S.D.) and all inferences were made at the 5% level of probability.

Results and discussion

The results shown in Table (1) showed that the insecticides did not

Table (1): Effect of various insecticides on plant height (cm) and number of leaves at 100 days after planting during 2016, 2017 and 2018 cropping seasons.

Treatments	Plant height (cm)			Number of leaves		
	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018
Control	23.20	28.11	38.72	239.01	318.04	380.97
Lambda-cyhalothin	23.96	35.53	39.05	244.21	328.92	386.56
Dimethoate 40% EC	23.90	32.25	38.73	234.94	325.61	380.63
Chlorpyrifos 48% EC	23.33	29.31	37.91	241.11	311.22	375.02
L.S.D. (0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

NS = Not significant

The result in Table (2) revealed that the insecticides significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the number of infected leaves at 100 days after planting. Lambda-cyhalothin differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) in the reduction

have any significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on the plant height and the number of leaves produced by the plants.

of the infected leaves when compared with other insecticides and control. The plants in the control plots had the highest number of infected leaves. These results were consistent across the years evaluated.

Table (2) : Effect of various insecticides on Number of infected leaves 100 days after planting in 2016, 2017 and 2018.

Treatments	2016	2017	2018
Control	97.61	94.83	91.71
Lambda-cyhalothin	17.82	20.81	16.09
Dimethoate 40% EC	54.31	59.23	60.42
Chlorpyrifos 48% EC	44.82	72.10	79.17
L.S.D. (0.05)	7.91	5.97	6.05

The plants that were treated with the insecticides significantly ($P < 0.05$) had increased numbers of pods and pod weight as recorded in Table (3). Plants treated with Lambda-cyhalothin recorded significantly

($P < 0.05$) higher number of pods and pod weight than plants treated with other insecticides and control across the years under study.

Table (3) : Effect of the various insecticides on number and weight of fresh pods (kg) at harvest in 2016, 2017 and 2018.

Treatments	Number of pods			Mean weight of fresh pods (kg)		
	2016	2017	2018	2016	2017	2018
Control	35.51	33.34	48.49	0.14	0.12	0.18
Lambda-cyhalothin	96.27	65.92	71.66	0.26	0.17	0.28
Dimethoate 40% EC	71.12	60.91	66.18	0.15	0.15	0.20
Chlorpyrifos 48% EC	76.07	49.14	64.694	0.16	0.13	0.19
LSD (0.05)	3.43	13.80	7.23	0.343	0.11	0.12

The control plots, however, produced the lowest number of pods and pod weight. The application of the insecticides did not affect the plant height and number of leaves produced by the plants. This demonstrated that the insecticides did not have any growth inducing compounds in their formulations. The plants depended on the relative availability of plant nutrients in the soil for their growth. The incidence of the fungal disease on the foliage of the crops was highly reduced by the application of the various insecticides. This was attributed to the relative efficacies of the insecticides in controlling the menace of the leaf spot disease caused by *Cercospora arachidicola*. The symptoms were brown spots surrounded by a yellow colour on the upper part of the leaves. Comparing the number of diseased leaves observed in the leaves of the control plots clearly brings out the relative fungicidal potentials of the fungicides.

Petit *et al.* (2012) posited that fungicides are a vital solution to the effective control of plant diseases which are estimated to cause yield reductions of almost 20% in major food and cash crops worldwide. Sharma *et al.* (2018) stated that application of fungicides reduces intensity of diseases in crops. The reduction of the disease incidence in the leaves of the crops by the application of the fungicides resulted in increased number and weight of the pods when compared with that obtained from the control plots. The increased yields also revealed the deleterious effects leaf spot disease could have on groundnut when left untreated, as evidenced by the plants in the control plots.

This underscores the importance of the fungicides in the control of ravaging leaf spot disease of groundnut. This further revealed that fungicides inhibit the occurrence of

diseases in plants. Massalatchi *et al.* (2017) posited that the use of plant protection products plays a very important role in agriculture. Leaf spot disease causes enormous yield loss in groundnut producing areas.

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Evaluation of Dismate (PE) pheromone and its comparison by some chemicals control against wax moths under storage conditions at Menoufia Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract:

A study aimed to some chemicals and evaluate four Dismate (PE) pheromone control treatments against the greater wax moth, *Galleria mellonella* L. and the lesser wax moth, *Achroia grisella* Feb. in the storages of waxes was carried out at the apiary (50 colonies) of New Lands, Sadat City, Menoufia Governorate, Egypt during autumn and winter season 2018 and 2019. The Paradi-chlorobenzene (PDB) achieved better control against both pests. The mean general reduction percentage reached 96.5%. In addition, the reduction percentage reached 94.4 %, 96.6% and 97.1% during December 2018, January and February 2019, respectively. The mean numbers of male greater and lesser wax moth attractant for trap by using Dismate (PE) pheromone were 14, 27, 45.25, 52.25, 59.5 and 59.5 after treatments for both insects during October, November and December 2018 and January, February and March 2019, respectively (General numbers 41.40). This study is considered one of the modern fields in controlling wax moths using pheromones. It reduces or prevents mating between males and females and its better method than using the PDB used by beekeepers, as it has a harmful effect on stored wax, which is used in the colonies after that and affects the bee products especially honey.

Introduction

Honey bee colonies are infected many pests and diseases. Wax moths are serious pests of bees wax. It can be considered as an extremely destructive pest that can destroy empty combs in a very short time (Borges, 1978 and Watkins, 2005). It can cause huge problems for beekeepers by decimating storage wax combs. The moths neither cause a disease, nor them parasites the individual honey bees, but they are responsible for the tremendous destruction of the colony (Jedruszuk *et al.*, 1994).

Larvae of greater wax moths, *Galleria mellonella* L. (Fam: Galleridae) and lesser wax moth, *Achroia grisella* Fab. (Fam: Pyralidae) are by for the most danger pest, especially to comb both in the weak hive and in storage. The Lepidoptera wax moth *G. mellonella* and *A. grisella* are extremely destructive pests, as they highly damage the empty wax combs during storage in winter in a relatively short time (Watkins, 2005). Adult females at wax moths fly at night and lay eggs on honey wax combs in the tiny crevices in hives. After a few days,

the larvae hatch, crawl onto the combs, and begin to feed, damaging or destroying combs by boring through the cells as they consume cocoons, cast skins and pollens. As they chew through the wax, they spin silken galleries for protection.

Finally, wax combs become a mass of debris and dust. They also pollute the wax combs with feces, which may contain contaminants and a mass of webbing rendering what is left of the wax comb useless (Atallah *et al.*, 1983). Compared among 5 treatments for controlling of wax moths (Mansour, 2008). Mabrouk *et al.* (2009) investigated the efficacy of certain natural and chemical compounds against wax moths (Formic acid 85%, oxalic acid 5%, phostoxin, agrin and Para-dichlorobenzene). Abou-Lila (2012) compared among 3 treatments against *G.mellonella* (Para-dichlorobenzene, formic acid 85% and clove oil).

The present study was designed to evaluate the Dismate pheromone against the wax moths *G. mellonella* and *A. grisella* under storage conditions.

Materials and methods

This experiment was carried out in store under conditions during Autumn and winter 2018 and 2019 for experimental para-dichlorobenzene (PDB) and experimental evaluation of Dismate pheromone at the store, Sadat city, New Lands, Menoufia Governorate during Autumn and winter 2018 and 2019. This experiment for controlling wax moths infested wax combs.

1. Baradix (Para-dichlorobenzene) PDB:

Was tested as a commercial chemical compound commonly used to kill and repel the greater and lesser wax moths. PDB crystals were sprinkled on the tops of combs at a rate of 25 g/hive box (Recommended 50 g./m³). Each

treatment was represented by 3 replicates for a period 3 months (10 combs each/ box) and one box was untreated to be used as a check (Shimanuki, 1991 and Mansour, 2003). The results were calculated according to the formula of Henderson and Tilton (1955):

$$\text{Reduction (\%)} = 1 - \frac{T_a \times C_b}{T_b \times C_a} \times 100$$

Where: Ta is % infestation of mite after treatment, Tb is % infestation of mite before treatment, Ca is % infestation of mite after treatment for the control and Cb is % infestation of mite before treatment for the control.

2. Evaluation of Dismate (PE) pheromone:

Three hive boxes were chosen for conducting this experiment. Each hive box was supplied by 10 infested wax combs contain different stages of wax moths. The input of this wax combs at storage. Dismate pheromone 2 capsules and 2 traps were used in storage (2.25x2.25x3.25 meters= 16.453 m²). Data all 15 days until experiment end.

Trade name: Dismate PE.

Company name: Russel IPM Ltd (United Kingdom); Active substance: Z-9, E-12-Tetradecadien-1-yl acetate; Functions (uses); Repellent and attractant.

Chemical name: (9,12-Tetradecadien-1-01, acetate, (9z,12E) Figure (1).

Figure (1): Chemical structure of Dismate (PE) pheromone.

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Agric. Pesticide Committee Effective amounts pheromone for 3 months (Pesticide Committee, 2017).

Application: the Dismate PE dispensers trap should attach to walls at 2-meter heights, 2 meter in between, before moth emergence and changed every 3 months. Mode of action: This product acts by disrupting the mating between male and female moths. Populations of the insects are reduced as the adult insects die and are not replaced by the next generation. The data were recorded all of 15 days from before and after treatments, 2018 and 2019 years. Statistical analysis was determined according to SAS Institute (1988).

Results and discussion

1. Baradix (Para-dichlorobenzene):

Data presented in Table (1) and Figure (2) shows mean reduction percentages in infestation with the greater and lesser wax moth, which reached 94.4, 96.6 and 97.1 % (general mean 96.5 %) after using Baradix during December 2018, January and February 2019, respectively. Analysis of the obtained data showed significant differences between the months and years. Mabrouk *et al.*, 2009; Abou-Lila, 2012; Mansour, 2008 and Mansour *et*

al., 2010 investigated the efficacy of certain natural and chemical compounds against wax moths. These compounds were more effective in controlling wax moths.

2. Evaluation of Dismate (PE) pheromone:

As shown in Table (2) and Figure (3) mean numbers of greater and lesser male wax moths after using Dismate (PE) pheromone attractant. These means were 14, 27, 45.25, 52.25, 59.5 and 59.5 (General means 41.4) during October, November and December 2018 and January, February and March 2019, respectively. Analysis of the obtained data showed significant differences between months and years.

In conclusion, this study is considered one of the modern fields in controlling wax moths using pheromones. It reduces or prevents mating between males and females and its better method than using the PDB used by beekeepers, as it has a harmful effect on stored wax, which is used in the colonies after that and affects the bee products especially honey.

Table (1): Reduction percentages of wax moths by using Baradix (Para-dichlorobenzene) in store at Minoufia Governorate.

Date	Treatment	Infestation % (3 months)		Reduction % (Month)	Reduction % Mean Month
	Replicates	Before Treatments	After Treatments		
December, 2018	1	50	7.5	93.7	94.4 ^b
	2	40	5.0	94.8	
	3	55	7.0	94.7	
January, 2019	4	55	5.0	96.2	96.6 ^a
	5	25	2.0	96.7	
	6	35	2.5	97.0	
February, 2019	7	45	3.0	97.2	97.1 ^a
	8	25	2.0	96.7	
	9	50	3.0	97.5	
F _{0.05}	-	-	-	-	27.26**
LSD	-	-	-	-	0.9628
General Mean Reduction %		-	-	-	96.5 %
Untreated (control)		40	95.0	-	-

Replicates= 3 boxes (each 10 wax combs/ box)/ month

Rate of Baradix (per day= 25g./box)

LSD = Least Significant Deference

Figure (2): Mean Reduction percentages (3 months) of wax moths by using paradix in store at Minoufia Governorate.

Figure (3): The stages of using Dismate PE pheromone during the experimental period in store at Minoufia Governorate.

Table (2): The numbers of greater and lesser males of wax moths by Dismate (PE) pheromone under store conditions at Minoufia Governorate.

Dates	Numbers of flies of wax moths		Total No./trap	Mean	
	Near to the trap	Far from the trap		Traps	month
15/10/2018	15	11	26	13	14.0 ^e
30/10/2018	17	13	30	15	
15/11/2018	25	25	50	25	27.0 ^d
30/11/2018	33	25	58	29	
15/12/2018	51	36	87	43.5	45.25 ^c
30/12/2018	58	36	94	47	
15/1/2019	62	40	102	51	52.25 ^b
30/1/2019	65	42	107	53.5	
15/2/2019	69	50	119	59.5	59.5 ^a
28/2/2019	69	50	119	59.5	
13/3/2019	69	50	119	59.5	59.5 ^a
F _{0.05}	-	-	-	-	722.96***
LSD	-	-	-	-	2.13
Total	533	378	911		45.55
Mean	48.45	34.36	82.81		41.40

LSD = Least Significant Deference

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Efficiency of one biopesticide and chitin *synthesis* inhibitor on toxicity, some biological and biochemical aspects of the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract:

The present study, investigate the effect of the entomopathogenic fungi (EPF), *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Bioranza) and chitin *synthesis* inhibitor lufenuron (Wormatin 5% EC) on the fourth instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) were investigated under laboratory conditions of $27 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$ and $65 \% \pm 10 \% \text{R.H.}$ The results revealed that the LC_{50} values obtained were 1.0677 and 0.0921 ppm for *S. littoralis* larvae treated with different concentrations of *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron respectively. The result recorded prolongation of larval duration, decreasing of both pupation % and pupal duration. The enzyme activities show a decrement of chitinase and elevation of protease. Also, the result reflects decrement in the total content (Lipid, protein, carbohydrate) for both treatments. Finally, it could be concluded that the used alternative insecticides have potentialities to reduce population density of *S. littoralis*, so could be used in combating the population of *S. littoralis*. Hoping that the obtained results may be of help in integrated pest management as it could be investigated in further researches.

Introduction

Lepidopterous insects are the most destructive pests of the cotton plant, namely the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), a highly polyphagous lepidopteran pest found worldwide, and an important model system used in a variety of biological research (Legeai *et al.* , 2011).

The using synthetic chemical insecticides resulting in high control efficacy of *S. littoralis*, cause a negative effect on human health, agriculture, natural enemies as a result of chemical

residue, environmental pollution and development of insect resistance to this chemical insecticides (Batta, 2016 and Fernandes *et al.* , 2010).

As a result, it is increasingly recognized that the biodiversity in agroecosystems delivers significant ecosystem services to agricultural production such as biological control of pests. Entomopathogenic fungi, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, (Meyling and Eilenberg , 2007).

Also, the insect growth regulators (IGR,s); recently exist in markets affect insects by regulating or

inhibiting specific biochemical pathways or processes essential for insect growth and development principally to death due to abnormal regulation of hormone mediated cell or organ regulation, among these IGR,s, chitin synthesis inhibitors (CSI's) was wormatin (Lufenuron) which interfere with the chitin deposition.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the susceptibility of fourth instar larvae of the Egyptian cotton leaf worm *S. littoralis* to fungi, bioranza and the CSI's lufenuron, and its effects on some biological and biochemical aspects on the 6th larval instar homogenate.

Materials and methods

1. Rearing technique of the Egyptian cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis*:

The colony of the cotton leaf worm *S. littoralis* was obtained from the division of the Cotton Leaf Worm, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center larvae were reared for about 13 generations on castor bean leaves (*Ricinus communis* L) before any treatment as the method described by El-Defrawi *et al.* (1964).

2. Compounds used:

Bioranza a commercial product formulation of *M. anisopliae*. The international unit was 32,000 viable spores per mg (32 x 10⁶ viable spore/mg). The active ingredient was 10% W.P. and the recommended application rate was 200 gm/100 liter water/feddan. Wormatin 5% EC (Lufenuron): a commercial insect growth regulator product lufenuron. The active ingredient was 5% EC and the recommended application rate was 160 cm³/feddan.

3. Toxicological studies:

Dipping method was used in this bioassay. 4th instar larvae were fed on treated castor bean leaves in different concentrations of the tested compounds, *M. anisopliae* and

lufenuron for 3 seconds. Five concentrations were prepared for each compound which were 6, 4, 2, 1 and 0.5 gm/litter for *M. anisopliae* and 0.75, 0.375, 0.1875, 0.0938 and 0.0469 ppm for lufenuron. 45 of 4th instars were divided into three replicates for each concentration and fed on treating leaves for 48hrs.

Also 30 4th instars used as control was performed using castor bean leaves dipped in water, then the survived larvae were transferred to other clean jars and supplied daily fresh castor bean leaves for 7 days after treatment. The mortality percentage was recorded daily and corrected according to (Abbott, 1925) formula. Percentages of correcting mortalities were statistically analyzed according to (Finney, 1971) and the LC₅₀ value was determined.

4. Biological studies:

From the maintained insect culture, newly ecdysed Fourth instar larvae (30 larvae for each treatment 10 and 30 as control) were collected and fed on castor bean leaves treated with the determined LC₅₀ value of *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron. Larvae were examined daily, and the following parameters were studied; larval duration, pupation %, pupal duration and pupal malformation %.

5. Biochemical studies:

5.1. Preparation of samples for biochemical studies:

Larvae were collected after six days following the treatment of the fourth instar, placed in ice containers and homogenized in appropriate buffer using a Teflon homogenizer surrounded with a jacket of crushed ice for 3 minutes. Homogenates were centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C (Biofuge 28RS Heraeus, Sepatech centrifuge). The resulted supernatants were used directly for determination of enzymatic activity.

5.2. Determination of the enzyme activities:

The activity of both protease and chitinase were determined according to the method of Ishaaya *et al.* (1971) and Ishaaya and Casida (1974), respectively.

5.3. Determination of the main components:

Total proteins, total lipids and total carbohydrates were determined in the total body homogenates according to the method of Bradford (1976), Singh and Sinha (1977) and Knight *et al.* (1972), respectively.

6. Statistical analysis procedure:

The significance of the main effects was determined by using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The significance of various treatments was evaluated by Duncan's multiple range tests ($p < 0.05$) and using student t-test. All analysis was preceded using a software package "Costat", a product of cohort software Inc. Berkley, California (Duncan, 1955).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicological studies of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron against 4th larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Table (1) represents the efficiency of *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron on 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis*. The LC₅₀ as well as regression lines were calculated, the LC₅₀ values recorded 1.0677 g/l and 0.0921 ppm for *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron respectively. Also, the slope values were 4.949 and 1.5387 for *M. anisopliae* and Lufenuron respectively, showing the homogeneity of the larvae.

The mode of action of *M. anisopliae* infection of the insect host with *M. anisopliae* starts with the unspecific adhesion of the fungal spores to the insect cuticle and penetrate into the insect haemolymph where extensive growth in the haemolymph and the production of toxins then to the insect tissue and the death occur.

These results agree with El Husseini (2019) where assumed the efficacy of the entomopathogenic fungus, *M. anisopliae* through applying different concentrations against *S. littoralis*. Also, Ramos *et al.* (2020) recorded that *M. anisopliae* caused the highest sporulation rates in controlling *S. frugiperda* with *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*

While the larval mortality with lufenuron may be attributed to direct inhibition of chitin synthesis within the integument rather than to any indirect extracuticle effects on hormone levels and the ingestion of chitin synthesis inhibitor compounds by insect larva disturbed the endocuticular deposition during moulting process and abortive moulting because they block chitin synthesis.

Generally, treated larvae were observed to be less active in their movement with obvious muscle contractions and prior to their death larvae exhibited severe tremors followed by paralysis. These finding agree with Wahba and Shaker (2020) where studied the toxicity of lufenuron, against the 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis*. These findings also agree with Abdel-Aal and El- Shikh (2012) and Maqsood *et al.* (2016) reported that lufenuron proved the most effective insecticide against *S. littoralis*.

Table (1): Toxicity values of and lufenuron against 4th instars *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae

Treated compound	LC ₅₀	Confidential limit (95%)		Slope±S.E.	Accumulative mortality% (At the end of larval stage)
		Lower	Upper		
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> gm/1litter	1.0677	0.7194	1.4285	4.9489± 0.3094	51.2
Lufenuron (ppm)	0.0921	0.0561	0.1293	1.5387±0.2188	50.5

2. Biological studies:

Table (2) illustrated that the duration of the *S. littoralis* treated as 4th instar with LC₅₀ of *M. anisopliae* was 11.0 days, which was more than that of the control by 0.5 days, i.e. an increase of 4.76% than the control. Pupation % following treatment of 4th instar larvae was 49.5%, which was a reduction of nearly half its value in untreated insects, while the larval duration was lengthened by 2.17 days, i.e. 12.67 days as compared to 10.5 days in the control, making a 20.67% increase for lufenuron treatment. Meanwhile, the pupal duration was 8.67 days as compared to 11.0 days in the control, i.e. less than the control by 2.33 days making -23.9% reduction. Pupation % was reduced to 49.0 and 47.5 % for *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron respectively. Meanwhile, the percentage of malformed pupa was more evident when 4th instar larvae were treated with LC₅₀ of lufenuron as it reached 33.33 %. The delayed effects of the insecticides which occurred during the development processes play an important role for their efficacy. The resulted data showed that, *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron caused a significant prolongation in the larval duration of *S. littoralis* larvae attributed to the slower metabolic rate of these larvae as a direct effect of insecticidal application. The feeding impairment of treated larvae could lead to prolongation of the larval instars and subsequently led to reduction in the percentage of pupation. These results were supported by El-Akad *et al.*

(2016) when treated the newly hatched larvae of *P. gossypiella* with both of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* found changes in the different biological aspects. Also, Kimberly and Seow (2017) and Jennifer *et al.* (2014) *M. anisopliae* caused more effect against *Diatraea flavipennella* larval period. El-Sayed *et al.* (2017) after studying the toxicity of lufenuron and flufenoxuron against the 2nd instar larvae of *S. littoralis*, treated with the sublethal concentrations of it showed also significantly reduce of the larval duration and pupation%. The changes in larval and pupal durations may reflect metamorphic disruption that in harmony with the percentage of malformed pupae recorded for lufenuron in our results.

Table (2): Biological effects of LC₅₀ of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron on certain biological aspects of *Spodoptera littoralis* treated as 4th instar larvae:

Treated compound	Mean larval duration (days± S.E.)	Pupation %	Mean pupal stage (days± S.E.)	Pupal malformation %
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	11.0 ^b ± 1.04 (4.76)	49.5	8.67 ^b ± 0.88 (23.9)	4.04
Lufenuron	12.67 ^a ± 0.88 (20.67)	47.5	7.67 ^c ± 0.2 (22.2)	33.33
Control	10.5 ^b ± 0.57	97.0	11.0 ^a ± 0.58	0.0
F. Value	21.973**		85.369***	
L.S.D.	0.8389		0.6399	

Numbers between brackets are percentages of reduction than the control.

Numbers of the same letters have no significant difference.

3. Biochemical studies:

3.1. Effect of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron on specific activities of some enzymatic systems of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

The activities of some enzymatic systems in 4th instar *S. littoralis* larvae, on the 6th day post treatment with the determined LC₅₀ value of *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron was determined. These enzymes represent a variety of hydrolases which are essential in physiological function of and hence in the metabolic pathway of a wide variety of a principal biochemical constituent in the targeted insect. When larvae were treated with *M. anisopliae* the activities of chitinase and protease were calculated to be 27.39 µg NAGA/min/g and 354.7 respectively, then those in untreated insects. These values were calculated to be a significant decrease than values of the control by 82.450 and 77.993%, respectively (Table 3 and Figure 1). Meanwhile, treatment of 4th instar *S. littoralis* larvae with LC₅₀ of Lufenuron was significantly reduced as they were 49.96 µg NAGA/min/g and 245.3 µg casein/min for chitinase and protease, respectively (Table 3 and Figure 1). In untreated insects these values were 42.81µg NAGA/min/g and 282.6 µg casein/min to the respective mentioned enzymes which represent a significant decrease than the enzymatic activities in control insects by 116.702 and 86.801%.

Chitinolytic enzymes are produce from cells in epidermis, gut, salivary glands or fat body of insects (Kramer and Koga, 1986). Chitinolytic enzymes secreted by the hypodermis and founded in the moulting fluid in the space between the old and the new cuticles during ecdysis (Kimura, 1976). Both enzymes chitinase and protease have role in digestion of old endocuticle in moulting process. So, any change in this enzyme activity may attributed to the inference of the insecticides (Hussain *et al.*, 2010). The production of cuticle-degrading enzymes, chitinases, lipases and proteases effected and facilitating penetration of various fungi as well as providing nourishment for further development. Also, St Leger *et al.*, 1991 in *M. anisopliae* appressorium formation, hydrophobins, and the expression of cuticle degrading proteases are triggered by low nutrient levels. The resulting as Assar *et al.* (2016) recorded increase in activity of chitinase, Phenoloxidase, carbohydrates hydrolyzing enzymes by use some insect growth regulators and bioinsecticides against *S. littoralis*. Also, Abdel-Aal *et al.* (2009) found that some chitin synthesis inhibitors (CSI) increased chitinase activity of the late 6th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* and recorded that chitinase and protease are essential for digestion of old endocuticle in the moulting process. So, any changes in these enzyme activities

may attribute to the interference of the (CSI) in moulting process.

Table (3) : Enzymes activities of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae after six days of treatment as 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ values of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron.

Compound	Chitinase µg NAGA/min/g	Activity % according to control	Protease µg casein/min	Activity % according to control
Control	33.22 ± 0.107	82.450	454.4 ± 10.05	77.993
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	27.39** ± 0.284		354.7*** ± 2.188	
Control	42.81 ± 1.223	116.702	282.6 ± 6.493	86.801
Lufenuron	49.96*** ± 1.335		245.3*** ± 5.099	

% Activity in the control= 100% less than 100% or more than 100% (decrease or increase)

** : moderately significant (p < 0.01) and *** : highly significant (p < 0.001), (student-t test).

Figure (1): Effect of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron at their corresponding LC₅₀ values on the specific activities of chitinase and protease 6 days following treatment of 4th instar *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae.

3.2. Effect of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron on total soluble protein content, total carbohydrate and total lipid in treated *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae:

Larvae treated by LC₅₀ of *M. anisopliae* and lufenuron induced a significant reduction in total soluble protein content 6th day post treatment, i.e. 235.0 mg/g and 396.8mg/g, respectively, then those in untreated insects. These values were calculated to be a significant decrease than values of the control by 32.413 and 32.413 %, respectively (Table 4 and Figure 2).

Similarly, the activity of the total carbohydrates was significantly reduced as they were 273.3 mg glucose/larva and 318.4 mg glucose/larva for mg glucose/larva, respectively. In untreated insects these values were 313.4 and 365.7 mg glucose/larva to the respective mentioned compound which represent a significant decrease than the total carbohydrates in control insects by 12.795 and 12.934 % (Table 4 and Figure 3). The data in Table showed a highly significant in the total lipid contents in the tested compound, *M.*

anisopliae and lufenuron comparing with control. They were calculated to be 254.8 and 261.8 mg oleic/larva which represent a marked decrease in the total lipid contents of the respective

mentioned compound untreated insects to 23.872 and 38.846 % (Table 4 and Figure 4).

Table (4) : The amounts of total protein, total carbohydrate and total lipid in *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae after six days of treatment as 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ values of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron.

Compound	The biochemical components		
	Total protein mg/larva	Total carbohydrate mg glucose/larva	Total lipid mg oleic/larva
Control	347.7 ± 20.19	313.4 ± 7.818	334.7 ± 6.332
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	235.0*** ± 5.863 (32.413)	273.3*** ± 4.573 (12.795)	254.8*** ± 5.82 (23.872)
Control	459.8 ± 6.347	365.7 ± 4.53	428.1 ± 6.851
Lufenuron	396.8*** ± 3.602 (13.702)	318.4*** ± 4.126 (12.934)	261.8*** ± 6.572 (38.846)

Numbers between brackets presented % decrease or increase in case the biochemical components
 ***: highly significant (p < 0.001), (student-t test).

Figure (2) : Total protein content in *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae after six days of treatment as 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ values of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron

Figure (3) : Total carbohydrate contents of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae after six days of treatment as 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ values of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron.

Figure (4) : Total lipid contents of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae after six days of treatment as 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ values of *Metarhizium anisopliae* and lufenuron.

Proteins are the most important compounds found in cells of all living organism, including many substances like enzymes and hormones that necessary for the main function of the living organisms (Fagan *et al.*, 2002). Carbohydrates providing the energy wanted for the growth of the cell (Lee *et al.*, 2002). Lipids are significant source of energy (Ali, 2011). The significant reduction in the total protein may be due to binding with foreign substances, as any insecticides (Ahmed *et al.*, 1985). The reduction of carbohydrates may due to the effect of anti-feedent and increased metabolism under toxicant stress (Remia *et al.*, 2008). The present results agree with El-Badawy *et al.* (2018) where found that *P. lilacinum* isolate caused significant increase in total carbohydrates and total lipids and reduction in total protein content of *S. littoralis*. Also, Nirupama (2015) the total protein of silkworm, *Bombyx mori* was reduced gradually with the fungal infection. Also, our results were proved by Vidhya *et al.* (2016) where infection of the army worm *S. litura* (Fabricius) by *B. bassiana*, *M. anisopliae* showed significant decreased of total protein content. Also our results were proved by Sobhi *et al.* (2020) they recorded inhibition of total lipid and total protein of *S. littoralis* treated with essential camphor oil while reduction in total

carbohydrates they observed are in contrast to our findings as we reported stimulation of total carbohydrates after treatment with essential *C. cyminum* oil. Kungreiliu Panmei *et al.* (2021) the results support the reduction in the body nutrients of *Ae. aegypti* larvae infection by lufenuron where the metabolic disturbances affected the growth and development of larvae. Aliabadi *et al.* (2016), reported the effects of sub-lethal concentration of lufenuron has been reported in *Glyphodes pyloalis*. The reduction of hemolymph and body homogenate total carbohydrate contents of the treated larvae (2nd and 4th instar) of *S. littoralis* may due to starvation, damage of the alimentary canal by the tested IGRs (Saleh and Abdel-Gawad, 2018).

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Effect of storage temperature conditions on the stability and biological effectiveness of insecticides formulation

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Abstract:

The present work was carried out to study the insecticide formulations for all chlorpyrifos 48 %EC, spinosad 24 % SC, and methomyl 90 % SP through storage at 54°C for 21 days. The toxicity of three insecticides (Chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl) against the 4th larval instar of the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) at different exposure times. The LC50 values chlorpyrifos were 0.62 , 0.62, 0.527 , 0.380 and the LC50 values Methomyl were 279.44, 279.44, 259.9, and 189.0 after 0,7 14 and 21 days respectively storage period at 54C. The stability of chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl active ingredients were 48.62, 24.61, and 91.61% before storage for all chlorpyrifos , spinosad, and methomyl and become after storage at the end of the experiment were 38.79,22.01 and 80.91% for 21dyes storage respectively. The loss experiment percentage was 20.79, 10.50, and 11.68 when the chlorpyrifos , spinosad, and methomyl compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 21 days. On the other hand, it was demonstrated that chlorpyrifos and methomyl had high acute toxicity against cotton leafworms. spinosad negatively affected the longevity and fecundity of the pest.

Introduction

The cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is the most destructive pest of tomato and cotton In Egypt. The cotton leafworm feeds on most plant parts including stem, leave, flower buds, flower heads, and fruits at different larval development stages (Amin and Gergis, 2006).

Spinosad is a bioinsecticide based on the fermentation product of the soil bacterium *Saccharopolyspora*

spinosa (Sparks *et al.*, 1998). This pesticide has two unique modes of action, acting primarily on the insect nervous system at the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor, and exhibiting activity at the GABA receptor (Watson, 2001).

Chlorpyrifos exerts its toxic action by inhibiting cholinesterases (ChE) enzymes of the nervous system, (Ware and Whitacred, 2004). The insecticide (Methomyl), is a broad-spectrum insecticide that belongs to the carbamate family of pesticides. It is

used for foliar treatment of vegetable, fruit, and field crops, cotton, commercial ornamentals, and in and around poultry houses and dairies (Alam, 1996). According to Gosselin (1984), it is a very toxic and hazardous compound and a pollutant causing environmental concerns because of its high solubility in water.

The present work aims to study the insecticides formulations for all chlorpyrifos 48 %EC, spinosad 24 % SC, and methomy 1 90 % SP through storage at 54°C for 21 days and studying of the toxicity of three compounds (Chlorpyrifos, spinosad and methomyl) against the 4th larval instar of the cotton leafworm at different exposure times.

Materials and methods

1. Insect used:

Test insect a laboratory strain of the cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis* was reared in the laboratory on castor bean leaves under laboratory conditions of $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH. (El-Defrawi *et al.*, 1964). The culture of the cotton leafworm was initiated from freshly collected egg masses supplied from the Division of Cotton Leafworm, Central Agricultural Pesticide Lab, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

2. Source of pesticides: Center Agric. Pesticides Laboratory (Table 1).

Table (1): Pesticide formulation types, the active ingredient, structure and its impurities.

Treed name	Formulation types	Active ingredient	Structure	Impurities
Bestban 48 %	EC	Chlorpyrifos		Sulfotep O,O,O',O'-tetraethyl dithiopyrophosphate.)
Treser 24 %	SC	Spinosad		UND
Lanet 90 %	Sp	Methomyl		UND

3. Bioassay tests:

The efficiency of the tested insecticides; chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and Methomyl, were assessed against the 2nd instar larvae of *S. littoralis*. Serial concentrations of each tested insecticide were prepared using water. Disks (9 cm. diameter) of castor bean leaves were dipped in the tested concentrations for 10 seconds then left to dry and offered to larvae, which starved for 4- 6 hours before treatment (Merdan, 1968). Each treatment was replicated 3 times (10 larvae per). Control disks were dipped in water only. The larvae were allowed to feed on treated leaves for 24 hr., transferred

to fresh untreated ones. The LC50, LC90, and slope values of the tested compounds were calculated using Finney's equation (Finney, 1971), through a software computer program.

4. Sample preparation for tested pesticides:

Accurately weighed sufficient samples formulation equivalent to 10 mg of standard in a different 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample, and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

5. Storage conditions:

The tested chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl formulation

were stored at 54°C for 14 days according to FAO (2002, 2004, and 2006), respectively. During the storage period, samples were taken at 0, 3, 7, 14, and 21 days to determine the active ingredient, and their impurities content for the tested formulations under test.

6. Determination of active ingredient Gas-Liquid Chromatography (GLC):

Determination of chlorpyrifos by GLC analysis compared with the standard used chlorpyrifos has carried out GLC model Agilent Technologies, the column with flame ionization detector (FID).

7. Conditions:

Injection Temperature: 225 °C

Detector Temperature: 300 °C

Oven Temperature: 130 °C for 5 min.,

8. Determination of product degradation of chlorpyrifos and methomyl by GC/MS:

Apparatus Agilent B, 5977 MSD gas chromatography equipped with an Agilent mass spectrometric detector, with a direct capillary interface and fused silica capacity Column (30 m x 0.025 mm HP -5 0.25 microm 60 to 325/325 °C). Samples were injected under the following condition; Helium was used as carrier gas at approximately 1 ml /min, pulsed split mode, split ratio (10:1) split-flow 10 ml /min. The solvent delay was 4 min and the injection size were 1 UL. Oven temperature program, 50 °C for 0.5 min, the 10 /min ramp to 190 °C followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 210 °C for 1 min followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 300 °C and held for 2 min (total run time followed by an injection temperature was set at 280 °C. Wiley mass spectral data was used in the identification of the Separated peaks

9. Determination of spinosad and methomyl by HPLC:

The active ingredient for spinosad and methomyl were evaluated

by HPLC. A revised phase high-performance liquid chromatographic was used for quantitative analysis. Agilent technologies 1200 series HPLC in student equipped with degasser, quaternary pump, photodiode array detector connected with injection system and computer (Model vectra was used for analysis. The stationary phase consisted of lichrosphere on Rp-8 packed stainless steel column 15cm x4.6mm id.

Results and discussion

1. Toxicity of chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl and biological insecticides different storage periods on larvae *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Serial:

The results presented in Table (2) show the toxicity of three insecticides (Chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl,) against the 4th larval instar of the cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis* at different exposure times. This experiment was conducted at laboratory conditions of 26°C and 65 ± 5% RH. Among the tested insecticides, chlorpyrifos was the most effective compound followed by chlorpyrifos, spinosad Methomyl the least effective one after 7, 14, and 21 days of exposure storage 54°C.

The results indicated that there was a positive relationship between the time post-treatment chlorpyrifos and methomyl. The LC50 values chlorpyrifos were 0.62, 0.62, 0.527, 0.380 and the LC50 values. Methomyl was 279.44, 279.44, 259.9, and 189.0 after treatment 0, 7, 14 and 21 days, respectively, storage period at 54°C. These obtained results were in agreement with Awad *et al.* (2019). Results obtained from acute toxicity assays of the tested insecticides showed that chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and methomyl were the most toxic chemicals against cotton bollworms. Similar results were found by Aslam *et al.* (2004), who have reported that

chlorpyrifos was the most effective insecticide for controlling cotton bollworm among tested in 192 insecticides. Nirmal and Manjit (2008) reported that the LC50 values of spinosad and chlorpyrifos were 0.04 and 0.66, respectively. Differences in LC50 values of these two studies would be due to differences in the duration of exposure to the insecticide and larval instar. Therefore, according to our results and the mentioned studies, spinosad and chlorpyrifos have a high potential for controlling cotton

leafworm. Chlorpyrifos had the highest slope among the test insecticides. The high slope indicates that a slight increase in insecticide concentration will lead to high mortality compared with the other insecticides. However, the higher slope indicates that there will be increased selection pressure on the population. Thus, there will be a greater risk of selection of resistant individuals compared with the other insecticides especially in cases of continued use of the same insecticide.

Table (2): Toxicity of chlorpyrifos, spinosad and methomyl and biological insecticides a different storage periods larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* . Serial.

Insecticides	Storage period (Days)	Slope	SE	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀
Chlorpyrifos	0	0.669	0.308	0.62	279.44
	7	0.669	0.308	0.62	279.44
	14	0.309	0.589	0.527	259.0
	21	0.380	0.479	0.380	189.0
Spinosad	0	0.212	0.9571	19973,8	25.6
	7	0.212	0.9571	19973,8	25.6
	14	0.156	1.261	112675.94	14.91
	21	0.196	1.044	12341.11	13.59
Methomyl	0	0.753	0.122	0.163	30.30
	7	0.631	0.235	0.1981	25.11
	14	0.540	0.278	0.148	24.11
	21	0.680	0.288	0.123	19.746

0 = initial storage

Slope = toxicity line intercept

SE = Standard Error of the slope

On the other hand, it was demonstrated that chlorpyrifos and methomyl had high acute toxicity against cotton leafworm. Spinosad negatively affected the longevity and fecundity of the pest. These impacts are very important for practical management of the pest, because these effects may lead to the reduction of the pest population to a lower level even under economic injury levels. Therefore, the authors propose that both lethal and sub-lethal effects of the insecticides should be considered in developing a pest management program.

2. Effect of storage at 54 °C on the active ingredient (a.i) of

chlorpyrifos , spinosad, and methomyl formulation:

The present data in Table (3) illustrated that the stability of chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and Methomyl active ingredients were 48.62, 24.61, and 91.61 % before storage for all Chlorpyrifos, spinosad, and Methomyl and become after storage at the end of the experiment were 38.79, 22.01 and 80.91% for 21 days storage, respectively. The loss experiment percentage was 20.79, 10.50, and 11.68 % when the chlorpyrifos , spinosad, and methomyl compound previously were stored at 54 °C for 21 days.

According to the international organization WHO specification (Storage at 54 °C for 3 days and FAO specification storage at 54 °C for 14 days). In general, increasing temperature and period of exposure of increasing the rate of degradation of insecticides Emara *et al.* (2009). Pesticides can be degraded by photolysis, hydrolysis, oxidation and reduction, metabolism (plant, animals, or microbes), temperature and

pH, FAO/IAEA (2009). Also, the impurities of chlorpyrifos 48 % EC before exposure 54 °C were 0.32 before storage and become after storage 0.73, 1.61, 2.23, 2.82 and 3.11 were stored at 54 °C for 0, 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days respectively. This results in disagreement with FAO maximum impurity of 3mg/kg in chlorpyrifos.

Table (3): Effect of Storage at 54 °C on active ingredient (a.i) of chlorpyrifos, spinosad and methomyl formulation.

Storage period (days)	Chlorpyrifos 48 %			Spinosad % 24%		Methomyl 90%	
	Active ingredient (a.i)	Loss	Sulfotep g/kg Chlorpyrifos	(a.i)	Loss	Active ingredient (a.i)	Loss %
0	48.62	00	0.32	24.61	00	91.61	00
1	48.50	0.24	0.73	24.31	1.22	91.00	0.66
3	48.00	1.27	1.61	23.50	4.51	90.02	1.73
7	47.62	2.06	2.23	22.80	7.35	88.50	3.39
14	46.50	4.36	2.82	22.25	9.58	85.11	4.42
21	38.51	20.79	3.11	22.01	10.56	80.91	11.68

0* one hour before exposure to storage

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A survey of the predators of the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) on *Citrus aurantifolia* in Lahj Governorate, Republic of Yemen

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Abstract:

During this study, the types of predators present in the environment of the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* Ashby (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) were identified in two different locations in Al-Houta district - Lahj Governorate, were conducted during the period extending from April 2010 to March 2011, in order to benefit from them in the integrated pest management program. Nineteen species of predators have been grouped. Twelve species are insect predators, 7 of which belong to the family Coccinellidae, 2 species, each to the families Chrysopidae and Formicidae, and one species to the family Coniopterygidae. Seven species of non-insect predators (Spiders) of the order Araneae and mites of the order Acarina. The results also showed that the insect predators of the family Chrysopidae of the type *Mallada boninensis* Okamoto and the family Coniopterygidae and non-insect (Spiders) 3 species of them of the order Araneae, and a new record in Yemen.

Introduction

Asia is the original home of the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* Ashby (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), which was first classified in the Caribbean in 1913 in Jamaica and is currently found in many Caribbean countries and Central America. It was first seen in Trinidad in 1997 and then spread on the island (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000). It was recorded in South Africa in January 1959 (Bedford and Thomas, 1965), in America (Nguyen and Sailer, 1987), and the United States of America (Dowell and Steinberg, 1990). And in Nagpur in India (Satpute *et al.*, 1989). In the Arab world, it is found in Egypt, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, the Sultanate of Oman, Iraq, Syria and Yemen (Ba-Angood, 2008). It spreads

in Yemen in all citrus growing areas (Ba-Angood *et al.*, 1997). It was recorded in Yemen for the first time in 1970 (Ba-Angood, 1977). The citrus black fly is considered the deadliest insect pest in citrus throughout the Republic of Yemen and infects other hosts in addition to citrus trees such as mango, banana, guava, papaya, pomegranate and dams trees (Ba-Angood, 2008). Al-warf plants and Indian cork (Al-Kaf, 1988), coffee (Ba-Angood *et al.*, 1997), okra and some types of flowers (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000), and in Lahj Governorate, 27 host plants were recorded, including citrus species (Murad and Ba-Angood, 2008), and they were found in more than 300 host plants (Nguyen and Hamon, 1993).

The damage occurs by feeding the nymphs and the adult insects on the lower surface of the leaves with their sucking piercing mouthparts, and they secrete honeydew materials that are a suitable environment for the growth of the black mold fungus on the leaves, which causes them to blacken and attract dust, which affects the process of photosynthesis and the feeding process of trees, so the fruits appear black, atrophic and small size, and the combined action of sucking the sap with the presence of the black mold fungus leads to a severe decrease in tree production (Rajak and Diwakar, 1987; French *et al.*, 1997; Ministry of Agriculture, 2000 and Ba-Angood, 2008). A group of predators attacks the citrus black fly, and a large burrow contributes to limiting its spread. A number of predators have been found in the Yemeni environment on the insect. As indicated by many studies, it was mentioned by Ba-Angood (1977) that the predator *Serangium* sp. was found in the eggs of the insect. Also, Ba-Angood (1990), through a preliminary inventory of some vital enemies of insect pests in Yemen, recorded a number of predators on the citrus black fly, including the larvae *Chrysoperla carnea*, *Cheilomenes vicina propinqua*, *Coccinella septempunctata*, predatory ladybirds, *Chilocorus* sp. and *Delphastorus* sp. The following predators were also found (Ba-Angood, 2002) in a survey study of the most important natural enemies in the Republic of Yemen: *Serangium citctum* (coleoptera: coccinellidae), *Eryngiopus harteni* (Acarina: Stigmataeidae) and *Chilomenes vicina propinqua* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) on the citrus black fly. Al-Kaf (1988) mentioned that there are some predators, including *Chrysoperla carnea* and beetles belonging to the family Coccinellidae found on the insect. Muharram (2003) and Al-

Ghashem (1994) indicated the presence of the following predators: *Eryngiopus harteni* (Acarina: Stigmataeidae) and *Tetraprachys* sp. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) on the insect. Raimundo *et al.* (2000) found the predator *Serangium buettikeri* on in the insect. Ba-Angood and Murad (2008) recorded 6 types of insect predators belonging to 3 families, including the family Coccinellidae, Formicidae, Raphidiidae on the insect, and three types of unclassified spiders belonging to the order Araneae.

Satpute *et al.* (1989) studied the natural enemies of an insect and found that predators *Catana parcesetosa* (*Serangium parcesetosum*) and *Anisochrysa boninensis* (*Mallada boninensis*), fed on the insect. Elizondo and Quezada (1990) explained that the predators *Chrysopa* spp. and *Delphastus* sp. are considered one of the most important vital enemies of the insect in Costa Rica. And Khan *et al.* (1991) found in Pakistan five types of predators on the insect. Aruna *et al.* (2017) observed predators Coccinellidae and Chrysopidae and spiders as natural enemies of *A. woglumi*. It is worth noting that predators were used in the control of the insect and gave effective results, as Cherry and Dowell (1979) indicated that the predator *Delphastes pusillus* (LeConte) and spiders were the most common, as it reached 90% of the predators that were captured, and the predator *D. pusillus* reduced the infection from 52 - 66 % In the Florida region, this depends on the predator stage, especially in the fourth larval stage, as the fourth stage of larvae preys 52% of the nymphs of the citrus black fly. And Legaspi *et al.* (2001) noted the success of the predator *Serangium parcesetosum* on the eggs of the insect, as it was able to reduce the number of eggs hatched from 157-47 eggs for the female, in a laboratory experiment at

the Texas Agricultural Station at Texas A & M University. Lavhe and Nimbalkar (2000) reported that the predator *M. boninensis* (Okamoto) was used to control the insect's nymphs.

To evaluate the use of the previous predator against the citrus black fly Kolhe *et al.* (2003) in Maharashtra state, India, found that the release of two pairs of adults from this predator reduced the infestation by a range of between 34 - 40%. Inspecting the natural enemies of pests in the agricultural environment, identifying them and using them in the control process aims to reduce the use of pesticides (Al-Ghashem, 1994). Since the global trend today is to rationalize the use of pesticides and implement the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) program, this study aimed to identify the predators of the pest in the city of Al-Houta in order to benefit from them in the integrated management programs and reduce the use of pesticides.

Materials and methods

Regular visits were made, one visits every week, to the two study sites (Al-Haj Yahya farm, Al-Fallujah farm) in Al-Houta in Lahj Governorate during the period from the beginning of April 2010 until the end of March 2011. The predators were observed and collected during the survey process and the detection of insect instars and yellow sticky traps (which are rectangular wooden panels with dimensions of 12 x 20 cm painted yellow, wrapped with transparent rectangular plastic pieces to place the adhesive and fixed with clips, then the trap is attached inside the field to the tree branches with a tie nylon clip attached to the top of the trap to identify predators.

The predators present on the insect instars that were seen preying on the insect were collected and their presence was assessed before collecting the leaves by a magnifying 20x lens, and the assessment of the predators on

the traps was also done after collecting from the field and brought to the laboratory, and the larva of the predator was carried in nylon bags to the laboratory I fed on the insect and left until it turned into a complete insect. Then the predators were taken and kept in plastic test tubes, each 1.5 cm in diameter and 5 cm long, containing 70% ethyl alcohol.

The obtained samples of predators were classified based on a study (Ba-Angood and Murad, 2008), and some of them were identified in Yemen, and samples of them were sent abroad and were classified by Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou (Plant Protection Research Institute , Agricultural Research Center, Egypt).

Results and discussion

The results of the current study showed the presence of 19 species of predators in the vicinity of the citrus black fly in the city of Al-Houta, belonging to five families belonging to five orders. The results (Table 1) indicated that 12 types of insect predators and 7 types of non-insect predators were recorded.

The results also showed that the Coleoptera order recorded the most number of predators (7 species) belonging to the Coccinellidae family found on eggs, nymphs and adults, followed by the Araneae order, where 6 species were recorded on the whole unclassified insect, and the Neuroptera order, 3 of which were recorded Species on eggs and nymphs belonging to the two families Chrysopidae, and only one species is not classified, Coniopterygidae, while the order Hymenoptera, two species were recorded, including whole insects, while the order Acarina, only one species was recorded on nymphs and pupae, not classified.

It is clear from the results that the highest rate of predators on one leaf was for the species *D. pusillus*, *Scymnus*

spp, *C. vicina propinqua* of the Coccinellidae family, whose numbers ranged from 8 adults, 10 larvae/leaf, 5 adults, 6 larvae/ leaf, and 4 adults/leaf, respectively. As for the rest of the predatory species, their numbers ranged from 1-2 adults and 1-2 larvae/leaf.

The results (Table 1) indicate that 10 species of whole insects were recorded as predatory insects found on the yellow sticky trap, 7 of them belong to Coleoptera of the family Coccinellidae, and the rest belong to the ranks Neuroptera 2 and Hymenoptera only one of them. It is noted from the results obtained (Table 1) that the predator *D. pusillus* of the Coccinellidae family had more rates and quality on the trap than the other predators: 23 adults / trap, followed by the predators *Scymnus* spp, *C. vicina propinqua* whose numbers ranged from 12 adults / trap, 6 adults /trap, respectively. As for the rest of the predatory species, the rate of their presence on one trap ranged from 1-3 whole insects/trap. The results also showed that the insect predators of the family Chrysopidae of the type *M. boninensis* and the family of Coniopterygidae and non-insect (Spiders) of the order Araneae, 3 of which are not classified, are a new record in Yemen.

These obtained results are consistent with what was indicated by Ba-Angood (2002 and 1990) and Ba-Angood and Murad (2008) in the recording of the predator *Cheilomenes vicina propinqua* on the insect. It also agrees with the results reached by Ba-Angood (1990), Al-Kaf (1988) and Ba-

Angood and Murad (2008) in the recording of the predator *Chrysoperla carnea* on the insect. It corresponds to the findings of Alivm *et al.* (2016) that the predators of Coccinellidae and Chrysopidae were distinguished as predators of this insect and the first was the dominant one. It is consistent with the findings of (CABI, 2021) in the recording of the predator *Scymnus smithinus* on the insect. It is also similar to the results obtained by Dowell *et al.* (1981) and Ba-Angood and Murad (2008), where they found some spiders feeding on the whole insects of the citrus black fly. Our results are consistent with what was found by Satpute *et al.* (1989), which showed that there are unknown mites that feed on the citrus black fly. It agrees with what was indicated by Dowell and Cherry (1981) that yellow traps captured a large number of whole insects of predators of the family Coccinellidae, up to 7 species.

Many predators of the citrus black fly have been monitored and due to the importance of biological control and the effectiveness of predators in reducing the pest community, so its use in biological control can play an effective role within the framework of integrated pest management. - Some studies indicated the presence of predators on the insect, including Neuroptera and *D. pusillus* beetle, and they were important in reducing the pest population. These predators were recorded in this study, so we believe that it is necessary to raise and use them in Yemen.

Table (1): Types of predators collected from the farms of Al- Haj Yohya and Al-Fallujah in the city of Al-Houta on the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* from April 2010-March 2011.

M	Order	Family	Type of predator	Predator locations on		The rate of predator presence/		Collection area	
				Life stages (Citrus blackfly host)	The trap	Leaf	Trap	Al-Haj Yohya farm	Al-Fallujah farm
1	Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	<i>Scymnus</i> sp.1	Adults / Eggs /Nymphs	+	5 adults and 6 larvae	12 adults	+	+
2			<i>Scymnus</i> sp.2	Adults / Eggs	+	2 adults	4 adults	+	+
3			<i>Scymnus smithinus</i>	Adults / Eggs	+	1 adult	3 adults	-	+
4			<i>Delphastus pusillus</i>	Adults/ Eggs /Nymphs	+	8 adults and 10 larvae	23 adults	+	+
5			<i>Cheilomenes vicina propinqua</i>	Adults / Eggs	+	4 adults	6 adults	+	+
6			<i>Serangium</i> sp	Eggs	+	1 adult	3 adults	-	+
7	Hymenoptera	Formicidae	<i>Cataglyphis sinaitica</i>	Adults	+	1 adult	3 adults	+	+
8			<i>Monomorium Yemen</i>	Adults	-	1 adult	-	-	+
9	Neuroptera	Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	Eggs / Nymphs	+	1 larva	2 adults	+	+
10			<i>Mallada boninensis</i>	Eggs / Nymphs	+	1 larva	2 adults	+	+
11		Coniop-erygidae	Unclassified	Eggs/ Nymphs	-	2 larvae	-	+	+
12	Araneae	-	Six unclassified species	Adults	-	1 adult	-	+	+
13	Acarina	-	Unclassified	Nymphs / Pupae	-	2 adults	-	+	+

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Incidence of certain insect pests infesting faba bean *Vicia faba* cultivars under some agriculture practices

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Abstract:

The unreliability fluctuations in faba bean yield from year to year could be attributed to insect and pathological infestations. Cowpea aphid, *Aphis craccivora* Koch. (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and the leafminer *Liomyza trifolii* (Burgess) (Diptera: Agromyzidae) were found to be the most destructive pests. Some agricultural practices have a major influence on the pest populations. Among the former factors, the faba bean cultivars can be considered. The time of bean seedling seemed to be a critical factor influencing the bean damaging. The early sowing date gave the chance to the majority of plant flowers to avoid from aphid infestation. The nitrogen fertilization played a major role to increase the level of piercing-sucking insect pest population.

Introduction

Faba bean is among the most important crops that supply the Egyptian people with protein. Moreover, it is essential for the feeding of livestock. Assiut Governorate is considered as one of the famous areas cultivated with faba bean in Egypt. Many reasons have been given to explain the yield fluctuations.

One of them attributed to the cowpea aphid which causes severe crop losses principally by direct feeding damage or as virus disease vector and disseminator. Moreover, many of other insect pests may cause a considerable crop damage, i.e. The leafminer and the leafhopper (Marzouk, 1990; Abate and Ampofo, 1996; El-Khawalka *et al.*, 1996; Sabra, 1997; El-Khayat, 1998; Mannaa *et al.*, 1999; Shaalan, 2005;

Shalaby *et al.*, 2012; El-Khayat *et al.*, 2015; Hosseini *et al.*, 2015; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2015; Jaskulska *et al.*, 2017 and Popat *et al.*, 2019).

During the past few years, the faba bean production in upper Egypt subjected to unstable status, the drastic losses in crop had been happened unexpectedly twice with this decade. Some situation has been mentioned by Wang and Zhou (1989) in China. Since faba bean considered as edible plant, the use of insecticides to control its pests would raise the residues remaining on treated plant and posed the health hazards.

The main purpose of this work is to examine some agricultural practices as alternative methods of insecticides to control the key pests of faba bean at Assiut.

Materials and methods

The present study was undertaken at Refa village (27.0976° N, 31.2070° E), Assiut District (10 Kilometers south of Assiut City). It has long been planted to patches of alfalfa, faba bean, Egyptian clover, wheat, maize and vegetables. The present investigation was carried out throughout two successive seasons, 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 to evaluate the effect of sowing dates, faba bean cultivars and nitrogen fertilizer on the infestation levels of *A. craccivora* and leafminer. The rates of each tested variable were as follow: 1. Sowing dates (3 treatments): Early (7 October), recommended (20 October) and late (1 November). 2. Faba bean cultivars (3 treatments): Sakha 1, Giza 843 and Misr3. 3. Nitrogen fertilization (3 treatments): Half recommended 75 NU, Recommended 150 NU, and one and half of recommended. The experiments were carried out in a split – split plot in three replicates each was 1/400 feddan (6 rows) in equal size (72 plots) were applied. The insects (aphids and leafminer) were monitored weekly (after one month from the planting till the end of season by counting (all forms) visually in five faba bean plants in each plot weekly. Data were statistically analyzed with spilt spilt for the cowpea aphid and leafminer infestation means were compared according to Duncan's multiple range test.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of sowing dates and faba bean cultivars:

Data in Table (1) show that the average numbers of the aphid were 167.52, 1939.44 and 2370.51 / plant on the faba bean planted in 7 October, 20

October and First of November during 2017-2018. It is clear obviously that the third date (Late) (1.11) harboured the highest population of aphid, which constituted about 1.22 times of those of the second sowing date and 14 times of the first. It means that the abundance of aphid grew rapidly on late growth of faba bean. The differences between sowing dates proved to be statistically significant. The same trend could be applied for 2018-2019 season (Table 2).

On the other hand, date in Table (1) show the population of leafminer (Larvae inside the mine) reached its maximum level on the early owing date (7 October), which constituted about 1.42 and 1.62 times to those prevailing on the plants of the second (20 October) and third sowing date (1 November). It means that the leafminer infestation affecting the plants of early sowing more than those that the other sowing dates. Contrary to aphid infestation. The differences between the mean numbers for different sowing dates were significant. The same trend was noticed for 2018-2019 season.

From the fore- mentioned results, it could be concluded that the early sowing of faba bean gives the plants the chance to escape from the heavy infestation of aphids, while the gradual late successive sowing dates increased the aphid populations to reach its maximum level on the delayed time. Consequently, the plants of the late sowing date suffering greatly from the aphid infestation affecting the plants of the early sowing dates (Contrary to the aphid infestation).

Altering the sowing date of crops has been a recognized method of cultural control for many pests (Abd El-Hafez *et al.*, 2012).

Table (1): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of cultivars, at the three studied sowing dates through the whole period of observation, 2017-2018, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	1 st (7.10.2017)	2 nd (20.10.2017)	3 rd (1.11.2017)
Aphids	167.52c	1939.44b	2370.51a
Leafminer	153.21a	107.45b	94.41c
Total	320.73	2046.89	2464.92
Mean	160.36	1023.44	1232.46

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

Table (2): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of cultivars, at the three studied sowing dates through the whole period of observation, 2018-2019, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	1 st (13.10.2018)	2 nd (27.10.2018)	3 rd (10.11.2018)
Aphids	3157.83c	3252.16b	3697.46a
Leafminer	122.53a	114.23b	82.65c
Total	3280.36	3366.39	3780.11
Mean	1640.18	1683.19	1890.05

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

2. Effect of faba bean cultivars:

From the obtained data in Tables (3 and 4), it is obvious that the faba bean cultivar Misr 3 was harbours the lowest number of aphids with significant differences between this cultivar and the others. Sakha 1 came in

the next grades. The cultivar Giza 843 was harboured the highest population of aphids during the two seasons of study. It is clear from the results that all of the studied cultivars did not exhibit any resistance effect against aphid infestation.

Table (3): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of sowing dates, on the studied cultivars through the whole period of observation, 2017-2018, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	Cultivars		
	Sakha 1	Giza 843	Misr 3
Aphids	1722.15b	2243.63a	1015.24c
Leafminer	73.28b	95.87a	55.56c
Total	1795.43	2339.5	1070.80
Mean	897.71b	1169.75a	535.40c

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

Table (4): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of sowing dates, on the studied cultivars through the whole period of observation, 2018-2019, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	Cultivars		
	Sakha 1	Giza 843	Misr 3
Aphids	3203.42b	3558.28a	3189.83c
Leafminer	107.44a	106.67a	97.55c
Total	3310.86	3664.95	3287.38
Mean	1655.43b	1832.47a	1643.69b

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

3. Effect of nitrogen fertilization:

Data presented in Tables (5 and 6) indicate that the population of aphids and leafminer increased significantly with the increase of nitrogen fertilizer. Significant differences were existed between the number of aphids and

leafminer on plants received different rates of nitrogen fertilization. The results obtained do not contradict with of the entomologists who worked on insects infesting faba bean in Egypt and abroad (Al-Jassany and Al-Adil, 1988; Marzouk, 1990; Abdel-Rassoul and

Abdel-Moity, 1992; El-Khawalka *et al.*, 2005; Shalaby *et al.*, 2012 and 1996; Mannaa *et al.*, 1999; Shaalan, Megawer *et al.*, 2017).

Table (5): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of sowing dates, on the studied Nitrogen fertilizer rate / plot through the whole period of observation, 2017-2018, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	Fertilization rate / plot		
	50 NU	100 NU	150 NU
Aphids	3100.31c	4800.45b	6521.23a
Leafminer	1945.21c	2150.54b	4581.20a
Total	5045.52	6950.99	11102.43
Mean	2522.76c	3475.49b	5551.215a

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

Table (6): The average number of studied insects/plants regardless of the effect of sowing dates, on the studied Nitrogen fertilizer rate / plot through the whole period of observation, 2018-2019, Assiut.

Studied Insects	No. / plant		
	Fertilization rate / plot		
	50 NU	100 NU	150 NU
Aphids	2770.37c	5946.10b	7641.32a
Leafminer	2067.11c	3148.74b	5264.13a
Total	4837.48	9094.84	12905.45
Mean	2418.74c	4547.42b	6452.72a

Means followed by the same letter within a row are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

It should be mentioned that the infestation started early in November and grew up rapidly to be dominated in February and March, until the end of the season. The achieved results revealed to the following conclusion and recommendations: 1. The time of bean seedling seems to be a critical factor influencing the bean damage. The early sowing date gives the chance to majority of plant flowers to avoid the aphid infestation. 2. High infestation with aphids and leafminer were occurred in the case of plants receiving high rates of nitrogen fertilization. Nitrogen fertilization at the rate of 100 units' nitrogen / feddan.

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Demographic growth aspects of cowpea aphid *Aphis craccivora* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on faba bean *Vicia faba* cultivars

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The performance of cowpea aphid *Aphis craccivora* Koch. (Hemiptera: Aphididae), on the three faba bean *Vicia faba* L. (Fabales: Fabaceae) cultivars were evaluated. Development time, survival, and life table parameters were studied to measure the cowpea aphid performance. The time needed for the development of nymphal instars varied significantly with the cultivars. Duration of the nymphal stage lasted 8.71, 6.30 and 4.65 days when reared on the cultivars of Misr 3, Sakha 1 and Giza 843, respectively. Generation time (GT), reproductive potential (R_0), population doubling time (DT), intrinsic (r_m) and finite rate (λ) of increase of the pest were also computed and discussed in relation to three cultivars.

Introduction

The cowpea aphid, *Aphis craccivora* Koch. (Hemiptera: Aphididae), is one of the most common and well-known insect pests throughout the world (Minks, A. K. and Harrewijn, 1987; Blackman and Eastop 2006 and Sadeghi *et al.*, 2009). Aphids are important piercing-sucking insects that during feeding cause significant loss of plant phloem saps, which is essential for plant growth (Dixon, 1998). Indirectly, cowpea aphid also disturbs the photosynthesis process by the presence of fungus on the leaves that is supported by the aphids honeydew secretion (Klingler *et al.*, 2001 and Smith and Boyko, 2007). Plant damage increases because of the aphids role as vectors of numerous plant viruses (Aldryhim and Khalil, 1993 and Smith

and Boyko, 2007), such as faba bean necrotic yellow virus, and bean leaf roll virus (Weigand and Bishara, 1991).

Cowpea aphids as a pest of faba bean, *Vicia faba* L. (Fabales: Fabaceae), are increasingly more important because of their higher occurrence in the field and increased deleterious effects on plants (Weigand and Bishara, 1991). A short generation time and high fecundity of the aphid cause enormous reproductive potential during a growing season (Klingler *et al.*, 2001).

Many attempts have been made to control cowpea aphid, mostly by insecticides; however, the increasing awareness of environmental and human health hazards has led researchers to develop alternative control measures with integrated pest management (IPM) (Shannag and Ja'far, 2007; Joplin, 1974

and Schoonhoven *et al.*,1998) estimated that the use resistant plants have increased yields by 120 folds. Although partial resistance is usually possible, it is difficult to achieve complete resistance to a particular insect species. From the IPM point of view, this is an advantage because it poses weaker selection pressure on the insect population to overcome host plant resistance. Therefore, the use of plant resistance should be combined with other IPM tactics (Schoonhoven *et al.*, 1998).

Resistant faba bean cultivars against aphids have been developed, such as *V. faba* Minor and *V. faba* landrace V51, which are tolerant and resistant to *Aphis fabae* and *A. craccivora*, respectively (Laamari *et al.*, 2008 and Shannag and Ja'far, 2007). Because aphids can overcome resistance factors of selected cultivars, additional studies of resistant mechanisms of other faba bean cultivars are urgently needed.

In this experiment, we investigated possible resistance traits in some selected faba bean cultivars against cowpea aphid. We examined the developmental time, survival, index of efficacy and some life table parameters of *A. craccivora* reared of some faba bean cultivars.

Materials and methods

1. Plant rearing:

Three faba bean cultivars (Sakha 1, Giza 843 and Misr 3) were used for experiments. Faba bean seeds were obtained from the Ministry of Agriculture. Seeds were soaked in water for 48hrs and then germinated in a mixture of sand and peat moss (1:1) growth medium. After 1 week, To carry out the trials, seeds of three varieties of faba bean namely; Sakha 1, Giza 843 and Misr 3 were sown separately pots under laboratory conditions.

2. Aphid source:

Adults of *A. craccivora* were collected from faba bean, grown in the field. Colonies of the pest were maintained in an electrical incubator at $20\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for about 10 generations.

3. Experiments:

To evaluate the effects of faba bean cultivars on biological characters and life table parameters. First instar nymphs were placed in separate Petri dish supplied with a leaf of faba bean varieties (Three varieties separately) lined with damp tissue paper. Petri dishes were placed in an incubator adjusted to $20\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thirteen (30) nymphs were reared on each cultivar. Faba bean leaves were replaced if necessary. Nymphs are observed daily until; the appearance of adult (Aptera). Aptera was allowed to complete at the previously mentioned varieties. Aptera was inspected daily to observe and record the number of nymphs born daily.

Indices of efficiency (IE) for development of the different stages of *A. craccivora* were calculated according to the formula of Khattat and Stewart (1977):

Index of Efficiency (IE) = $\frac{St}{Tt}$, where
S, is the percentage survival, T
is the time required for development in days.

Analysis of Varian's (F test) was used to compare the effect faba bean varieties on the duration of development and fecundity of the pest. Obtained results were used to calculate life table statistics. Namely:

- Net reproductive rate (R₀),
- Generation time (GT),
- Population doubling time (DT),
- Intrinsic (r_m) and finite rate of increase (λ).

These parameters were calculated according to the procedures of (Birch, 1948).

Results and discussion

1. Developmental time:

The effect of three faba bean cultivars on the development should be presented in both nymphal and adult stages.

1.1. Nymphal stage:

The developmental period of the nymphal stage reared on the three varieties is presented in Table (1). A significant decrease in the duration of the three cultivars was observed. The duration of the four instars was respectively, 1.44, 1.84, 2.66 and 2.77 days; 1.35, 1.53, 1.77 and 1.65 days and third cultivar, 1.01, 1.21, 1.22 and 1.21 days on the cultivars of Misr 3, Sakha 1 and Giza 843, respectively. Nymphal duration varied significantly with three cultivars. The first nymphal duration, however, lasted for 8.71, 6.30 and 4.65 days on Misr3, Sakha 1 and Giza 843, respectively. Statistical analysis showed that the longest for nymphal development on three cultivars was recorded on Misr 3 while the shortest period was noticed on the cultivar of Giza 843. On the other hand, the time needed for the development decreased

development time by about 1.24 and 1.78 times. The cultivar Giza 843 had the lowest nymphal duration (4.65 days) followed by Sakha 1., Misr 3 had the highest.

Data presented in Table (2) indicate that survival of nymphal instars and whole nymphal stage reared on three cultivars. The highest percentage of survival was observed at cultivar of Misr 3 and Sakha 1, respectively, whereas, the lowest (24%) was noticed on the cultivar of Giza 843 (Tables 2 and 3).

Using an Index of Efficiency for development of nymphal instars (Table 4), data indicate that the index values varied from cultivars. The highest index value was obtained for the cultivar of Misr 3 followed by Sakha 1. The cultivar Giza 843 had the highest Index (17.20). Based on the obtained data, it may be concluded that cultivars of Giza 843 and Sakha 1 were the most suitable for the development of the pest.

Table (1): Developmental time (In days \pm SD) of *Aphis craccivora* reared on three varieties of faba bean at temperature of $20\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Varieties	Developmental time (days \pm SD)				
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Total
Misr 3	1.44 \pm 0.51a	1.84 \pm 0.67a	2.66 \pm 0.74a	2.77 \pm 0.69a	8.71 \pm 2.41a
Sakha 1	1.35 \pm 0.31b	1.53 \pm 0.39b	1.77 \pm 0.38b	1.65 \pm 0.59b	6.30 \pm 1.87b
Giza 843	1.01 \pm 0.41c	1.21 \pm 0.00c	1.22 \pm 0.32c	1.21 \pm 0.11c	4.65 \pm 0.84c

Means followed by the same letter vertically, are not significantly different >0.05 .

Table (2): Cumulative survival (Numbers) of *Aphis craccivora* reared on different varieties of faba bean at temperature of $20\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Varieties		Cumulative survival (numbers)				
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Total
Giza 843	Number	30	29	28	27	30
	Alive	(29)	(28)	(27)	(26)	(26)
Sakha 1	Number	30	28	27	26	30
	Alive	(28)	(27)	(26)	(25)	(25)
Misr 3	Number	30	27	26	25	30
	Alive	(27)	(26)	(25)	(24)	(24)

Table (3): Survival (%) of *Aphis craccivora* reared on different varieties of faba bean at temperature of $20\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Varieties	Survival (%)				
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Total
Giza 843	96.67	96.55	96.43	96.29	86.67
Sakha 1	93.33	96.43	96.29	96.15	83.33
Misr 3	90.00	96.29	96.15	96.00	80.00

Table (4): Index of Efficiency (IE) of *Aphis craccivora* reared on different varieties of faba bean at temperature of 20±1°C.

Varieties	Index of Efficiency (IE)				
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Total
Misr 3	67.13	52.47	36.25	34.76	9.95
Sakha 1	69.13	63.02	54.40	58.27	13.22
Giza 843	89.11	79.57	78.81	79.33	17.20

1.2. Adult stage:

Data presented in Table (5) show the average length of life of the adult at the three cultivars. Adult longevity was divided into pre-reproductive, reproductive and post-reproductive periods. The results indicate that reproductive periods varied from cultivar to another. Adult apterous cowpea aphid numbers in Giza 843 were significantly higher than on Misr 3 and Sakha 1 (Table 5).

In the detached-leaf biological assay, the cultivar Giza 843 had a longer pre-reproductive, reproductive, post-reproductive, and total longevity period as compared with Misr 3 and Sakha 1, whereas the number of progenies was lower as compared with Misr 3 and Sakha 1. Generally, cowpea aphid performance on whole plants was different as compared with the detached leaf assay.

Demographic parameters study (Table 6) showed that cultivar Misr 3 had a significantly lower net reproduction rate (R_0) compared with Giza 843; other parameters had no clear relationship with the lesser suitability character of Sakha1 compared with Misr3.

On the detached leaf, all the demographic parameters supported that Giza 843 was less suitable for the aphid compared with Misr3, indicated by the significantly lower net reproduction rate (R_0), intrinsic rate of increase (r_m), and finite rate of increase (λ), and longer generation time (GT) and doubling time (DT). Similar to biological parameters (Table 3), cowpea aphid demographic performance on the whole plant and

detached leaf was different (Table 4). Results show that Misr3, either on the detached leaf or whole plant, seems preferable to the aphid compared with Giza 843, indicated by a higher fecundity rate on Misr3.

The colony development study was conducted initially to obtain general information about the potential resistant characters that might be present among three faba bean cultivars. Studies showed that the tested cultivars differed in their suitability for the cowpea aphid development. All the parameters in colony development assay indicated that the order of cultivar resistance from the highest to the lowest was Giza 843, Sakha 1 and Misr 3.

Results obtained from the colony development assays probably reflect a similar phenomenon in the field because aphids could move freely and to feed on any part of the plant (Alvarez *et al.*, 2006). Factors such as leaf surface, leaf size, or leaf color supposedly affects the results of colony development assays (Bernays and Chapman, 1994). Some differences in host plant quality among cultivars due to genetic variation or environmental factors also can determine cowpea aphid performance (Islam and Shunxiang, 2007).

It also was shown that adult numbers in Giza 843 were not significantly different as compared with Misr3 and Sakha 1, which could indicate the unsuitability of Giza 843 as host plant. This may reflect that the cultivar Giza 843 exhibited higher resistance compared with Sakha 1 and Misr3. However, other parameters did not give a clear relationship to support

this conclusion. Longer total longevity and fewer progeny are essential parameters indicating the suitability of a host plant, especially for sucking insects (Awmack and Leather, 2002 and Bernardi *et al.*, 2012).

Most of the biological parameters evaluated in the detached-leaf assay showed that the cultivar Giza 843 was less suitable for cowpea aphid development compared with Misr 3 and Sakha 1, indicated by longer pre-reproductive, reproductive, post-reproductive, and total longevity periods, and fewer aphid progeny. Bernardi *et al.* (2012) reached a similar conclusion on the resistant strawberry cv. Aromas infested by green aphid *Chaetosiphon fragaefolii* (Cockerell).

Using the detached-leaf method for the biological assay is recommended by some researchers because of its efficiency (Sharma *et al.*, 2005; Smith, 2005 and Michel *et al.*, 2010). We noted that the detached-leaf assay was easier to handle and provided more accurate information because all the environmental parameters were controlled. When comparing whole-plant and detached leaf methods in the biological study, results varied among cultivars for all parameters, but the progeny number parameter was significantly higher in the detached-leaf assay.

This result gave a precaution in using detached leaves in resistant screening assays for faba beans, probably because of the difference in tissue properties. However, these studies might be useful for determining the persistency of resistant characters,

Table (5): Longevity and number of progenies of *Aphis craccivora* reared on three varieties of faba bean at temperature of 20±1°C.

Varieties	Longevity and number of progeny / ♀				
	Longevity (in days)				Number progeny / ♀
	Pre-	Reproductive	Post-	Longevity	
Giza 843	1.22±0.47a	21.15±3.24a	7.45±3.22a	29.82±6.93	55.71±9.55a
Sakha 1	1.79±0.79b	17.77±1.56b	3.77±1.66b	23.33±4.01	38.60±8.48b
Misr 3	1.17±0.22c	13.41±2.41c	2.75±2.01c	17.33±4.64	19.66±14.91c
Total	4.18±1.48	52.33±7.72	13.97±6.89	70.48±15.58	113.97±29.68
	1.39±0.49	17.44±2.40	4.65±2.29	23.49±5.19	37.99±9.89

Means followed by the same letter vertically, are not significantly different >0.05.

as shown in Michel *et al.* (2010) soybean cultivar study against soybean aphid, *Aphis glycines* (Matsumura), which concluded that the resistant character was retained in detached leaves in PI 243540' but it was lost in PI 567301B.

The net reproduction rate of whole plant faba bean cultivar Misr3 was significantly higher than Giza 843 (Table 6). If the net reproduction rate value is used as the only parameter, it can be concluded that Giza 843 was less suitable for the aphids than Misr 3 and Sakha 1. The net reproduction rate value is important in representing the host plant quality and the capacity of a female producing the progeny (Bernardi *et al.*, 2012).

It was important to note that cowpea aphid fecundity in faba bean cv. Misr3 remained high at the end of their reproductive period. This fact deviated from the general assumption that the progeny is supposed to peak at the beginning of the reproductive period (Wyatt and White, 1977).

These phenomena result in the higher value of generation time and decrease the intrinsic rate of increase value of Misr3 compared with Giza 843. The demographic parameters study gave reliable results and supported the suggested less suitability of cultivar Giza 843 compared with Misr 3 and Sakha 1, indicated by significantly lower net reproduction rate, intrinsic rate of increase, and the finite rate of increase, but longer generation time and doubling time, compared with Misr 3.

Table (6): Some life table aspects of *Aphis craccivora* on reared on three varieties of faba bean at temperature of 20±1°C.

Aspects	Faba bean varieties		
	Giza 843	Sakha 1	Misr 3
Generation time (GT)	16.46	15.34	12.81
Doubling time (DT)	4.06	3.59	3.05
Net reproductive rate (R ₀)	22.64	33.68	15.85
Intrinsic rate of increase (r _m)	0.22659	0.2667	0.2294
Finite rate of increase (λ)	1.2543	1.3056	1.2578

Finally, those demographic results are important to justify resistant characters of certain cultivars, such as in strawberry cv. Aroma against green aphid (Bernardi *et al.*, 2012). In addition, demographic parameters can be used to measure the suitability of a host plant for certain insects, such as in some tomato cultivars against *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Islam and Shunxiang, 2007), the suitability of chickpea pods for *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) (Dabhi and Patel, 2007), the suitability of different host plants for glassy-winged sharpshooter, *Homalodisca vitripennis* (Germar) (Chen *et al.*, 2010). Overall, these results suggested that the use of faba bean cultivar Giza 843 should decrease the cowpea aphid population. The colony development study ranked the resistance level among cultivars as Giza 843>Sakha 1 and Misr 3.

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Survey of the pseudococcid mealybugs (Hemiptera:Pseudococcidae) infesting dragon fruit and their natural enemies in some new reclaimed lands, Egypt

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Abstract:

The present work was conducted on three dragon fruit varieties in private farms at three localities, new reclaimed lands, Ain Ghosin (Ismailiya Governorate), New Nubariya (Beheira Governorate) and Berqash district (Giza Governorate). The study was conducted to survey mealybug species and their associated natural enemies on the dragon fruit trees; it considered a new kind of fruit in the Egyptian environment. The obtained results revealed four pseudococcid species, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsle, *Ferrisia virgata* (Ckll.), *Planococcus citri* (Risso) and *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Green) (Hemiptera:Pseudococcidae). Associated parasitoids were *Aenasius arizonensis* (Giraut), family: Encyrtidae and *Chartocerus dactylopii* (Ashmead), family: Signiphoridae on *Ph. solenopsis*; *Coccidoxenoides peregrinus* (Timberlake) and *Leptomastix abnormis* (Giraut) on *P. citri*, family: Encyrtidae; *Anagyrus kamali* Moursi and *Leptomastix dactylopii* Howard, family: Encyrtidae on *M. hirsutus* and *Blepyrus insularis* (Cameron) family: Encyrtidae on *F. virgata* Also, Associated predators, two predators, *Dicrodiplosis manihoti* Harris and *Diadiplosis donaldi* Harris on *Ph. solenopsis* and *P. citri*, family: Cecidomiidae, respectively. Also, one predator *Cryptolaemus montrouzieri* Mulsant, family: Coccinellidae. About susceptibility of three varieties of dragon fruit had differences with the infestation of the four mealybug species were recorded.

Introduction

Dragon fruit or pitaya, (*Hylocereus* spp. and *Selenicereus* spp.) is a new tropical fruit tree (Caryophyllales: Cactaceae). The first time to plant in Egypt was at the European countryside region 58 kilometer of desert Alexandria road, and then increasing gradually year by year in newly reclaimed lands in Egypt. The crop manifested susceptibility was attacked by insects and diseases. It is a lack of information to understand them.

Mealybugs (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) are major pests that infest a wide range of fruit trees, shrubs and ornamental plants worldwide (Ben-Dov *et al.*, 2010). The mealybug nymphs and adult females can be extremely polyphagous and feed by piercing and sucking plant sap. This feeding behavior often causes considerable economic losses to agriculture through direct damage to infested crops (Golino *et al.*, 2002 and Miller *et al.*, 2002).

The pseudococcids excrete large quantities of honeydew that ensure leave, stems and fruits, resulting in further crop damage and the growth of sooty moulds and bunch rots (Godfrey *et al.*, 2003). Mealybug control is made difficult because characterized by the presence of a white, waxy secretion covering the whole body that serves as a barrier to insecticide penetration. Repeated chemical treatments also affect natural enemies of mealybugs negatively (Walton and Pringle, 1999).

The objective of this study was to inventory, for the first time, the mealybug fauna and its natural enemies in a dragon fruit plantation in newly reclaimed land in Egypt.

Materials and methods

Survey of mealybug species on dragon fruit varieties cultivated in three new reclaimed lands, Ain Ghosin (Ismailiya Governorate), New Nubariya (Beheira Governorate) and Berqash district (Giza Governorate) (Figure 1) were carried out for one complete year from March 2020 to February 2021. Three private dragon fruit orchards are cultivated with different varieties of dragon fruit trees were chosen for sampling purposes.

The study was conducted on three varieties i.e. Pitaya blanca or white-fleshed pitaya, *Hylocereus undatus*. Pitaya roja, or red-fleshed pitaya, *Hylocereus costaricensis* and

yellow pitaya *Hylocereus megalanthus*. These trees were about 5-7 years old and about 2 meters in height, the distance between trees about 4 meters and heavily infested with mealybugs. These orchards were reserved for the normal agricultural practices without any insecticidal applications before and during sampling processes.

Regular monthly excursions were carried out for sampling purposes throughout one complete year. Monthly sampling, 3 tender green stems about 20-30 cm. long from each variety were randomly collected from each locality. These samples were kept in a special plastic box and transferred to the laboratory for inspection. The monthly samples from the three localities were examined with aid of a stereoscopic microscope. After examining the stems and fruits of dragon fruit varieties per each variety and some specimens from each mealybug species were confined in big glass jars and kept in the laboratory for securing any emerging parasitoids.

The surveyed mealybug species and their natural enemies were identified in the Scale Insects and Mealybugs Division, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza – Egypt by the key of pseudococcids Zeinat and Youssef (2017) and the key of parasitoids by Güleç *et al.* (2007) and Hayat (1970).

Figure (1): Localities of three orchards of dragon fruit and its coordinate.

Results and discussion

1. Survey of mealybugs:

The obtained results Table (1) revealed four species of mealybug species on dragon fruit varieties at three

Table (1): The mealybug species which recorded on stems and fruits of dragon fruit varieties from three localities in the new reclaimed lands from March, 2020 to February, 2021.

Family	Common name	Scientific name
Pseudococcidae	Cotton mealybug	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> Tinsley.
	Striped mealybug	<i>Ferrisia virgata</i> (Ckll.)
	Citrus mealybug	<i>Planococcus citri</i> (Risso)
	Hibiscus mealybug	<i>Maconellicoccus hirsutus</i> (Green)

Four pseudococcid species were recorded on the stem and the fruits of the three different varieties of dragon fruit trees (Figure 2 A and B), the cotton mealybug, *P. solenopsis*, the striped mealybug, *F. virgata*, the citrus mealybug, *P. citri* and the hibiscus mealybug, *M. hirsutus*. They suck the plant sap and secrete honeydew which leads to the growth of sooty mould. The

localities (Ain Ghosin, Ismailiya; New Nubariya Beheira and Berqash district Giza Governorates). The surveyed species belonging to one family are as follows:

black fungus coats the most of plant parts interfering with photosynthesis. In this respect, Sartiami *et al.* (2016) reported that the, *Ph. solenopsis* and *F. virgata* are pests on dragon fruit trees in Indonesia. *P. citri* and *M. hirsutus* are pests of grapes and may be transferred from vineyards very closed with dragon fruit plantation (Youssef, 1991).

Figure (2): (A): Colony of mealybugs on stem, (B): Colony on fruit scales.

2. Degree of infestation:

The degree of infestation with the four mealybug species which recorded on dragon fruit varieties was presented in Table (2) and illustrated in Figure (3). The obtained results showed different infestation with mealybug species on dragon fruit varieties at the three different localities. The red-fleshed pitaya, *H. costaricensis* had the heaviest infestation with three pseudococcids mealybugs, *Ph. solenopsis*, *F. virgata* and *P. citri*,

respectively. The followed by Yellow pitaya which is infested with *P. solenopsis* and *M. hirsutus*, respectively. The white-fleshed pitaya infested with only one mealybug species, *Ph. solenopsis* but a heavy infestation. On the other side, *Ph. solenopsis* has more population density on the three varieties of dragon fruit followed *F. virgata* on (Red-fleshed pitaya), *H. costaricensis*. The lowest density was *M. hirsutus* on Yellow pitaya, *H. megalanthus*.

Table (2): The mealybug species which recorded on three varieties of dragon fruits and degrees of infestation.

Dragon fruit varieties	Mealybug species recorded	Degree of infestation
<i>Hylocereus undatus</i> (White-fleshed pitaya)	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i>	+++
<i>Hylocereus costaricensis</i> (Red-fleshed pitaya)	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> <i>Ferrisia virgata</i> <i>Planococcus citri</i>	+++ +++ ++
<i>Hylocereus megalanthus</i> (Yellow pitaya)	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> <i>Maconellicoccus hirsutus</i>	+++ +

Note: (+): >10 individuals, (++): 11-25 individuals, (+++): < 25 /1 inch² According to Facylate (1971)

Figure (3): Average numbers of mealybug species were recorded on three dragon fruit varieties during March, 2020 to February, 2021 in three localities.

3. Natural enemies associated with mealybug species on dragon fruit trees:

Results in Table (3) and Figure (4) revealed the parasitoids and predators associated with surveyed four mealybug species on dragon fruit varieties at three localities as follows:

- The cotton mealybug, *Ph. solenopsis* was associated with encyrtid parasitoid, *Aenasius arizonensis* (Giraut) and signiphorid, *Chartocerus dactylopii* (Ashmead) whereas, has one cecidomiid predator *Dicrodiplosis manihoti* Harris
- The citrus mealybug, *P. citri* was associated with two encyrtid parasitoids, *Coccidoxenoides peregrinus* (Timberlake) and *Leptomastidae abnormis* (Giraut), also,

has one cecidomiid predator *Diadiplosis donaldi* (Harris).

- The hibiscus mealybug, *M. hirsutus* was associated with two encyrtid parasitoids, *Anagyrus kamali* Moursi and *Leptomastix dactylopii* Howard.
- The striped mealybug, *F. virgata* was associated with encyrtid parasitoid, *Blepyrus insularis* (Cameron) and one coccinellid predator *Cryptolaemus montrouzieri* Mulsant.

These results are in harmony with those obtained by many authors ,Abdul Rahman *et al.* (2010); Aga *et al.* (2016); Attia and Awadallah (2016 a and b), Attia and El Arnaouty (2009) and Afifi *et al.* (2010) and Attia (2012) they recorded the same parasitoids and predators on the above mentioned mealybugs but different host plants.

Table (3): Natural enemies associated with mealybug species recorded on dragon fruit varieties at three localities in the new reclaimed lands (March,2020 -February, 2021).

Mealybug species	Parasitoids and predators with their families	
<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i>	<i>Aenasius arizonensis</i> (Giraut)	Hymenoptera – Encyrtidae
	<i>Chartocerus dactylopii</i> (Ashmead)	Hymenoptera- Signiphoridae
	<i>Dicrodiplosis manihoti</i> Harris	Diptera – Cecidomiidae
<i>Planococcus citri</i>	<i>Coccidoxenoides peregrinus</i> (Timberlake)	Hymenoptera -Encyrtidae
	<i>Leptomastidae abnormis</i> (Giraut)	
	<i>Diadiplosis donaldi</i> (Harris)	Diptera – Cecidomiidae
<i>Maconellicoccus hirsutus</i>	<i>Anagyrus kamali</i> Moursi	Hymenoptera- Encyrtidae
	<i>Leptomastix dactylopii</i> Howard	
<i>Ferrisia virgata</i>	<i>Blepyrus insularis</i> (Cameron)	Hymenoptera -Encyrtidae
	<i>Cryptolaemus montrouzieri</i>	Coleoptera -Coccinellidae

Figure (4): Parasitoids and predators associated with recorded four mealybug species on dragon fruit varieties.

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A contribution to the study of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) of Iran

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Abstract:

This paper deals with ichneumonid species (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) which were collected from different regions of Iran and are preserved in insect collections and museums. In total of 81 species within 17 subfamilies are represented in this paper which nine species are new records for the fauna of Iran: *Alexeter segmentarius* (Fabricius, 1787), *Sympherta splendens* (Strobl, 1903), *Syntactus minor* (Holmgren, 1857) (Ctenopelmatinae), *Asyncrita designatus* (Förster, 1876), *Asyncrita exilis* Haliday, 1838 (Cryptinae), *Diphyus monitorius* (Panzer, 1801), *Diphyus trifasciatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829) (Ichneumoninae), *Lissonota maculata* Brischke, 1865 (Banchinae), and *Macrus parvulus* (Gravenhorst, 1829) (Campopleginae).

Introduction

Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) is the biggest hymenopteran family with some 42 generally recognized subfamilies and more than 25,000 described species (Yu *et al.*, 2016). The real number of species was estimated by Townes (1969) to be far higher, with probably up to 60 000 species (Gauld, 1991). The distribution of Ichneumonidae is one of the most notable exceptions to the common latitudinal gradient in species diversity because it shows greater speciation at high latitudes than at low latitudes (Sime and Brower, 1998). The most

common groups as the hosts of Ichneumonidae are Lepidoptera, Coleoptera and Diptera to a less extend spiders and the egg sacs of spiders and pseudoscorpions. The biology of ichneumonids is very variable, and all forms of parasitism are represented (Gupta, 1991; Laurenne, 2008 and Çoruh and Özbek, 2011).

The purpose of this paper is to record the species of Ichneumonidae collected from different regions of Iran as part of ongoing faunistic studies of Ichneumonidae in Iran.

Materials and methods

The materials of this faunistic research were collected by Malaise traps and sweeping net from different regions of Iran. Additionally, several specimens of insect collections of some universities, and museums were studied. Some specimens were reared in optimum conditions at laboratory conditions or incubator (25 ± 2 °C, $65\pm 5\%$ RH. and 14: 10 L: D). The specimens are preserved in the private collections of the authors and Zoological Museum of Turku University. Resources used to identify the specimens included Townes (1969),

Broad (2011), and Rouse and Villemant (2012) on the subfamily level; Townes (1969, 1970a, b, 1971); Bennett (2015) on the generic level; Van Rossem (1966), Delrio (1975), Horstmann (1968, 1990), Kasparyan (1981), Schwarz (2002, 2007), Humala (2002), Çoruh and Özbek (2008), Jussila *et al.* (2010), Rouse and Villemant (2012) and Vas (2016) on the specific level. Here we follow Yu *et al.* (2016) for nomenclature, classification and distributional data. The provinces of Iran are represented in Figure (1).

Figure (1): Map of Iran with boundaries of provinces.

Results and discussion

This faunistic paper on Iranian Ichneumonidae comprises 81 species within 59 genera and 17 subfamilies: Adelognathinae (3 species, 2 genera), Anomaloninae (5 species, 3 genera), Banchinae (7 species, 4 genera), Campopleginae (14 species, 11 genera), Cryptinae (12 species, 8 genera), Ctenopelmatinae (9 species, 6 genera), Diacritinae (one species), Diplazontinae (4 species, 4 genera), Ichneumoninae (12 species, 9 genera), Mesochorinae (3 species, one genus), Ophioninae (one species), Orthocentrinae (one species), Pimplinae (one species), Stilbopinae (one species), Tersilochinae (3 species, 2 genera), Tryphoninae (3 species, 3 genera) and Xoridinae (One species). Totally nine species are newly recorded from Iran. The list of species within subfamilies and genera are given below alphabetically together with distributional data.

Subfamily Adelognathinae Thomson, 1888

Genus *Aethecerus* Wesmael, 1845

Aethecerus discolor Wesmael, 1845

Material examined: Golestan province, Gorgan (Naharkhoran), 1♀, August 2011.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Adelognathus* Holmgren, 1855

Adelognathus laevicollis Thomson, 1883

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh, 2♀, October 2015.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia,

France, Germany, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Adelognathus pallipes (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Ourmieh (Nazloo), August 2014.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Canada, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Japan, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, USA and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Anomaloninae Viereck, 1918

Genus *Agrypon* Förster, 1860

Agrypon anomelas (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Semnan province, Shahrood (Jangal-e Abr), 1♀, 1♂, 23.vii.2012.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Korea, Moldova, Netherlands, Pakistan, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and Finland (R. Jussila).

Agrypon anxium (Wesmael, 1849)

Material examined: Guilan province, Lahijan, 3♀, 1♂, June 2016, ex *Yponomeuta malinellus* (Zeller, 1838) (Lepidoptera: Yponomeutidae).

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Sweden, Turkmenistan, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Agrypon gracilipes (Curtis, 1839)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Fereydonkenar, 1♀, May 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Korea, Latvia, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Barylypa* Förster, 1869

***Barylypa rubricator* (Szépligeti, 1899)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Salmas, 2♀, 11.viii.2014.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Russia, Turkey (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and Finland (R. Jussila).

Genus *Habronyx* Förster, 1869

***Habronyx biguttatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Minoodasht, 31 m, 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Belgium, Canada, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, USA and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Banchinae Wesmael, 1845

Genus *Apophua* Morley, 1913

***Apophua genalis* (Möller, 1883)**

Material examined: Hamedan province, Toyserkan, 1♀, 1♂, September 2012.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Banchus* Fabricius, 1798

***Banchus volutatorius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Chaharmahal-Bakhtiari province, Farsan, 2♀, 2♂, 21.vii.2013.

General distribution: Eastern Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental, and Western Palaearctic regions.

Genus *Exetastes* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Exetastes nigripes* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Kiakola, 2♀, 2♂, May 2011, ex *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Pieridae).

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Lissonota* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Lissonota culiciformis* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh, 3♀, 1♂, October 2015, ex *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Lasiocampidae).

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Lissonota maculata* Brischke, 1865**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Mahabad, 1♀, 11.viii.2014. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Lissonota saturator* (Thunberg, 1824)**

Material examined: Lorestan province, Azna, 2♀, 7.viii.2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

***Lissonota subaciculata* Bridgman, 1886**

Material examined: Guilan province, Talesh, 1♀, June 2008.

General distribution: Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Genus *Campoletis* Förster, 1869

***Campoletis cognata* (Tschek, 1871)**

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan province, Sabzevar (Roodab), 3♀, 1♂, May 2012, ex *Agrotis segetum* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae).

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, France-Corsica, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Uzbekistan (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and Finland (R. Jussila).

***Campoletis latrator* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Hamedan province, Malayer, 1776 m, 1♀, September 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland,

Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Campoplex* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Campoplex borealis* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Gorgan (Jafar-Abad), 2♀, 1♂, June 2017, ex *Archips rosana* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Charops* Holmgren, 1859

***Charops cantator* (DeGeer, 1778)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Golpayegan, 3♀, 2♂, July 2016, ex *Zygaena dorycnii* Ochsenheimer, 1808 (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Diadegma* Förster, 1869

***Diadegma rufatum* (Bridgman, 1884)**

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Baneh (Vali-Abad), 1♀, September 2015.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Dusona* Cameron, 1900

***Dusona cultrator* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Northern Khorasan province, Safi-Abad, 2♀, 1♂, October 2017, ex *Cydia pomonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Dusona tenuis* (Förster, 1868)**

Material examined: Markazi province, Tafresh (Sarabadan), 1♀, 1♂, May 2018.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Eriborus* Förster, 1869

***Eriborus braccatus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Mianeh, 2♀, 16.ix.2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Spain, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Diadegma* Förster, 1869

***Diadegma laterale* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Takab (Ghoshkhaneh), 1♀, September 2003.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, New Zealand, Poland, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869

***Hyposoter caedator* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Ourmieh (km 12 Seroo Road), 1♀, July 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia and United Kingdom.

***Hyposoter neglectus* (Holmgren, 1860)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Oshnavieh, 1♀, August 2014.

General distribution: Austria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Macrus* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Macrus parvulus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Zanjan province, Abhar, 1540 m, 1♀, June 2011. *New record for Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, USA, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Meloboris* Holmgren, 1859

***Meloboris alternans* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon (Asal Mahalleh), 1♀, April 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Sinophorus* Förster, 1869

***Sinophorus juniperinus* (Holmgren, 1856)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Minoodasht, 1♀, 1♂, April 2009.

General distribution: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Cryptinae Kirby, 1837

Genus *Acroricnus* Ratzeburg, 1852

Acroricnus seductorius (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined: Isfahan province, Chadegan, 1♀, 10.v.2011.

General distribution: Algeria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Syria and Turkey.

Genus *Aptesis* Förster, 1850

Aptesis cretata (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Kermanshah province, Javanrood, 1340 m, 2♀, April 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Aptesis jejunator (Gravenhorst, 1807)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Qaemshahr (Ghadikola), 2♀, 2♂, July 2014, ex *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae).

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Asyncrita* Förster, 1876
Asyncrita acuminator Roman, 1909

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Ourmieh (km 12 Seroo Road), 1♀, July 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Italy, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

***Asyncrita exilis* Haliday, 1838**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Golpaygan (Saeid-Abad), 2♂, 2♀, May 2015. *New record for Iran.*

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greenland, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

***Asyncrita croceicornis* Haliday, 1838**

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 2♀, 1♂, June 2010, ex *Lymantria dispar* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Erebidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Atractodes* Gravenhorst, 1829

Atractodes designatus Förster, 1876

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Khoy, 1153 m, 1♀, July 2013. *New record for Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Genus *Cubocephalus* Ratzeburg, 1848

Cubocephalus anatorius (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh (Zirab), 2♀, June 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

***Cubocephalus associator* (Thunberg, 1824)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Gisum forest, 1♀, September 2016.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Diaglyptidea* Viereck, 1913

***Diaglyptidea conformis* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Behshahr (Zaghemarz), 2♀, 1♂, September 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Gambrus* Förster, 1869

***Gambrus tricolor* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Shahin-Dezh, 1422 m, 1♀, August 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Gelis* Thunberg, 1827

***Gelis mangeri* (Gravenhorst, 1815)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Chalus, 1♀, September 2009.

General distribution: Austria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Ctenopelmatinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Alexeter* Foester, 1869

***Alexeter niger* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Golpaygan (Saeid-Abad), 1♀, May 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

***Alexeter segmentarius* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Khansar (Mehr-Abad), 2♂, 2♀, May 2015. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Campodorus* Förster, 1869

***Campodorus variegatus* (Jurine, 1807)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Sari (Dasht-e Naz), 2♂, June 2017.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Czech Republic,

former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom.

Genus *Ctenopelma* Holmgren, 1855
Ctenopelma nigripenne
(Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Guilan province, Amlash, 2♀, May 2009.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Korea, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and former Yugoslavia.

***Ctenopelma nigrum* Holmgren, 1857**

Material examined: East Azarbayjan province, Maragheh (Qarehnaz), 1♀, 12.viii.2012.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and Ukraine.

Genus *Sympherta* Förster, 1869
Sympherta splendens (Strobl, 1903)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon (Asal-Mahalleh), 2♀, April 2013. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Russia, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Syntactus* Förster, 1869
Syntactus delusor (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: Isfahan province, Khansar (Mehr-Abad), 3♀, 1♂, May 2015.

General distribution : Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

***Syntactus minor* (Holmgren, 1857)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Astara, 1♀, 1♂, September 2017. *New record for Iran.*

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Zemiophora* Förster, 1869
Zemiophora scutulata (Hartig, 1838)

Material examined: Kermanshah province, Sonqor, 1632 m, 2♀, June 2004.

General distribution: Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Diacritinae Townes, 1965

Genus *Diacritus* Förster, 1869
Diacritus aciculatus (Vollenhoven, 1878)

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Baneh, 2♀, September 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Diplazontinae Viereck, 1918

Genus *Diplazon* Nees ab Esenbeck, 1819

***Diplazon varicoxa* (Thomson, 1890)**

Material examined: Zanjan province, Abhar, 2♀, 1♂, May 2016.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Belgium, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Mongolia, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Syrphoctonus* Förster, 1869

***Syrphoctonus elegans* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Chadegan, 1♀, 10.v.2011.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greenland, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Genus *Woldstedtius* Carlson, 1979

***Woldstedtius flavolineatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Salikandeh, 2♀, 2♂, July 2014, ex *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae).

General distribution: Eastern Palaearctic, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oriental, and Western Palaearctic regions,

Genus *Xestopelta* Dasch, 1964

***Xestopelta gracillima* (Schmiedeknecht, 1926)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Amlash (Rankooh), 1♀, July 2004.

General distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Germany, Italy, Kyrgyzstan, Poland and Russia.

Subfamily Ichneumoninae Latreille, 1802

Genus *Alomya* Panzer, 1806

***Alomya debellator* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon (Jangal-e 2000), 1♀, July 2013, ex *Hepialus humuli* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Hepialidae).

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland,

Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

***Alomya punctalata* (Schellenberg, 1802)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Makoo, 1♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Belarus, Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Spain and Switzerland.

Genus *Callajoppa* Cameron, 1903

***Callajoppa exaltatoria* (Panzer, 1804)**

Material examined: Chaharmahal-Bakhtiari province, Lordegan (Khalil-Abad), 1♀, 1♂, 15.vii.2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Cratichneumon* Thomson, 1893

***Cratichneumon sicarius* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Chadegan, 1♀, 10.v.2011.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Diphyus* Kriechbaumer, 1890

***Diphyus monitorius* (Panzer, 1801)**

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Ourmieh (km 12 Seroo Road), 1♀, July 2014. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former

Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain and United Kingdom.

Diphyus quinquecinctus (Kriechbaumer, 1882)

Material examined: Isfahan province, Khansar (Mehr-Abad), 2♀, May 2015.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Bulgaria, Germany, Kazakhstan, Romania, Russia, Spain, Turkey and Turkmenistan.

Diphyus trifasciatus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Guilan province, Fooman, 1♀, April 2009. *New record for Iran.*

General distribution: Belgium, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain and United Kingdom.

Genus *Ichneumon* Linnaeus, 1758

Ichneumon primatorius Forster, 1771

Material examined: Chaharmahal-Bakhtiari province, Koohrang, 2288 m, 1♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Pristicerops* Heinrich, 1962

Pristicerops infractorius (Linnaeus, 1761)

Material examined: Hamedan province, Gol Tappeh, 2♀, September 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands,

Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Stenichneumon* Thomson, 1893

Stenichneumon militarius (Thunberg, 1824)

Material examined: Northern Khorasan province, Shirvan (Ulashloo), 1♀, 1♂, April 2011.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, USA, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Uzbekistan and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Thyrateles* Perkins, 1953

Thyrateles haereticus (Wesmael, 1854)

Material examined: Semnan province, Damghan, 1♀, 25.vii.2012.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Virgichneumon* Heinrich, 1977

Virgichneumon faunus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Babol (Nakhkola), 2♀, 1♂, September 2002.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

**Subfamily Mesochorinae Foerster,
1869**

Genus *Astiphromma* Förster, 1869
Astiphromma dorsale (Holmgren,
1860)

Material examined: Guilan province, Siahkal, 2♀, June 2015, ex *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Pieridae).

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, China, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Taiwan and United Kingdom.

Astiphromma leucogrammum
(Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon (Jangal-e 2000), 1♀, July 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and USA.

Astiphromma varipes (Holmgren,
1860)

Material examined: West Azarbayjan province, Makoo, 1♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania and Sweden.

**Subfamily Ophioninae Shuckard,
1840**

Genus *Enicospilus* Stephens, 1835
Enicospilus undulatus (Gravenhorst,
1829)

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Deh Golan, 1837 m, 1♂, July 2010.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, China, former Czechoslovakia, Egypt, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Libya, Morocco, Netherlands, Paraguay,

Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

**Subfamily Orthocentrinae Forster,
1869**

Genus *Plectiscus* Gravenhorst, 1829
Plectiscus impurator Gravenhorst,
1829

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Tonekabon (Jangal-e 2000), 1♂, July 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Pimplinae Wesmael, 1845

Genus *Acrodactyla* Haliday, 1838
Acrodactyla carinator (Aubert, 1965)

Material examined: Qazvin province, Moalem Kelayeh, 1517 m, 2♀, September 2011.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and Finland (R. Jussila).

Subfamily Stilbopinae Förster, 1869

Genus *Stilbops* Förster, 1869
Stilbops ruficornis (Gravenhorst,
1829)

Material examined: Guilan province, Siahkal, 2♀, June 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Tersilochinae
Schmiedeknecht, 1910

Genus *Barycnemis* Förster, 1869

***Barycnemis exhaustator* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Qorveh, 1323 m, 1♀, September 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Barycnemis punctifrons* Horstmann, 1981**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Sari (Pahnehkola), 1♀, September 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Russia, Ukraine, United Kingdom (Yu *et al.*, 2016) and Finland (R. Jussila).

Genus *Probles* Förster, 1869

***Probles (Euporizon) exilis* (Holmgren, 1860)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Astara (Qarehsu), 1♀, September 2004.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden and Turkey.

Subfamily Tryphoninae Shuckard, 1840

Genus *Cycasis* Townes, 1965

***Cycasis rubiginosa* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan, Neyshabour (Khajeh-Abad), 3♀, 2♂, August 2011, ex *Cydia pomonella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae).

General distribution: Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands,

Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Eridolius* Förster, 1869

***Eridolius alacer* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Khuzestan province, Izeh, 897 m, 1♀, 1♂, April 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Polyblastus* Hartig, 1837

***Polyblastus varitarsus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Kurdistan province, Qorveh (Shoorab-Haji), 2♀, 2♂, September 2011.

General distribution: Eastern Palaearctic, Europe, Nearctic, and Western Palaearctic regions.

Subfamily Xoridinae Shuckard, 1840

Genus *Odontocolon* Cushman, 1942

***Odontocolon appendiculatum* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Qazvin province, Moalem Kelayeh, 1♀, September 2011.

General distribution: Austria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and Switzerland.

The results of the present research with nine new country records indicate that the fauna of Iranian Ichneumonidae is very diverse and also has poorly been studied. Faunistic surveys on Iranian Ichneumonidae have not been conducted in all areas and there are several regions where have not been sampled systematically so far, especially eastern and southern areas.

Continue to faunistic surveys in these areas surely will result to finding of new data (New country records, new distributional data, new host records, and probably new species). Regarding to ichneumonids' importance in biological control of several agricultural and forest pests, conservation of these powerful parasitoids will result to suppression of pests' populations (**Godfray, 1994; Gurr and Wratten, 2000 and Quicke, 2015**).

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Impact of the pesticides spinosad, azadirachtin and abamectin on *Chrysoperla carnea*
(Neuropetra: Chrysopidae)

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Abstract:

The use of pesticides of natural origin help preserving the predators population in environment. This study using the International Organization of biological control (IOBC) -system and the life table response experiment for spinosad, *Azadirachtin indica* and abamectin on the common green lacewing *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuropetra: Chrysopidae) under laboratory condition. The results indicated that the height mortality was observed to tearted *C.carnea* larvae by spinosad at 38.07% and low mortality with abamectin at 13.85%, while total eggs were lower with spinosad than azadirachtin indica and abamectin, no significant different from treated with *A.indica* and abamectin. Abamectin was classified as a harmless but spinosad and *A. indica* were slightly harmful. The result showed significant different among percent of larval survival % between the pesticides and control which was 80.6% , also adult survival% of the control was 86.7%. Life table assays reveled that no significant different among the mean generation time (T) between the treatments and not significant among doubling time (DT), intrinsic rate of increase (rm) and finite rate of increase(λ). The lowest value for net reproductive rate(R0) occurred during spinosad treatment. Abamectin and azidirachtin were non-toxic to *C.carnea* under the tested conditions. Using life table assay was more accurate to find out effects of Spinosad than IOBC method.

Introduction

Chrysoperla carnea (Stephens) (Neuropetra: Chrysopidae) is one of the important natural enemies that has been effectively used to control different pests in the field (Athar *et al.*, 2004) and has been fascinating subject for side effects investigation (Vogt *et al.*, 1992; Badawy and EL Arnaouty, 1999; Dutton *et al.*, 2003 and Medina *et al.*, 2003). *C. carnea* has a large number from preys such as eggs , nymphs and adult of insects and spiders which are harm on the plants in open field and

green houses, so *C.carnea* considered very important predators. The pesticides harmony with biological control agent is a great go into Integrated pests management (IPM) and understanding about the activity of pesticides toward the pests the non-target insects and the environment in a needful (Stark *et al.*, 2004).

The impact of synthetic pesticides on non-target organizes in the natural and the human health risks posed by exposure to these chemicals are issues of growing concern (National

Research Council, 1996 and Cisneros *et al.*, 2002). The method used in experiments the side effect of pesticides on natural enemies, suggest by the International Organization of biological control (IOBC) is a classification approach where by initial pesticides hide is done in the laboratory, hemifield and field experiments (Hassan,1998).

This method has designed to evaluate the acute residual toxicity as well as sublethal effect of the pesticides on the reproductive performance (Vogt *et al.*,2000). The death and reduced fecundity, exposure to a toxicant may result in simultaneous manifestation of multiple sublethal effects such as shortened life span, mutation in offspring, changes in fertility rates, developmental rates and sex ratio (Stark *et al.*,2004).

Spinosad is a stomach toxic with contact activity against lepidoptera and Diptera (Xian- Hui *et al.*,2008), it is also a neurotoxin but some field studies show that spinosad is moderately harmful on some parasitoid. Neem oil is a natural pesticide against some insects, but it is deleterious effect on *c. carnea* (Sana *et al.*, 2015) compare to abamectin which is safe on some predators.

The objective of this study was to obtain information on the susceptibility *C.carnea* to the pesticides

Table (1): Pesticides used in this study .

Active ingredient	Brand name	Recommended field rate
Spinosad	Tracer 24% Sc	0.2 ml/L.
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	Neemix 4.5% Ec	1 ml/L.
Abamectin	Vertemic 1.8% Ec	0.4 ml/L.

3. IOBC approach :

The larvae of *C .carnea* were placed on glass plats sprays with pesticides with water as control and left dry. Vogt *et al.* (1998). There were three replicates per treatment each treatment contains twenty larvae under laboratory conditions. During the

spinosad, azadirachtin and abamectin. Using the International Organization of biological control (IOBC) and life table response experiments (ITREs). Besides giving a report about degree of damage of the pesticides on the fertility, life table parameters, including R0, RM, T, DT and lambda (λ).

Materials and methods

1.Chrysoperla carnea rearing:

Adults of *C. carnea* were collected from fields, in Giza, Egypt in Oct. 2020 and were kept in a plastic container 7 cm diameter and 15 cm height, covered with a piece of black gauze. They were fed on an artificial diet consisting of two parts brewer’s yeast, one part of honey and a part of sugar mixed to a paste with water. Water was offered using a damp cotton plug put on the cage. Eggs laid by female green lacewing on the walls of chimney and muslin cloth were harvested with sharp razor and one egg per test tube was placed with the help of camel hair brush, after hatching the newly hatched larvea were fed on eggs of *Sitotroga cerelella* with under laboratory conditions (27± 5 C° and 70 ± 5% RH.).

2. Pesticides using in this study:

The tested pesticides were used at the recommended field rates (Table 1).

experiments larvae were fed on *S. cerealella* eggs. Dead larvae were recorded daily, and the mortality was also calculated. The number of pupae that failed to adult was registered as dead larvae. The value of mortality (M) were estimated according to Abbott (1925).The average number of eggs (R)

was measured as fecundity affected by exposure to the pesticides. The total effects of the pesticides E were calculated by formula proposed by Overmeer and Van Zon (1982):

$$Er=Rt/Rc.....(1).$$

Er=Effect on reproduction.

Rt=Reproduction in treatment.

Rc=reproduction in control.

$$E=100%-(100%-M) \times Er... (2).$$

M=Mortality corrected according to Abbott (1925).

E= Total effect.

Based on total effect was evaluated through the Working Groups Joint pesticides testing programmed in guideline IOBC (Bakker *et al.*,1992):

Class 1 : E < 30% (harmless).

Class 2 : 30 < E < 80% (Slightly harmful).

Class 3 : 80 < E < 99% (Moderately harmful).

Class 4 : E > 99% (Harmful).

4.Life table assay:

Age specific life table parameters were studied on Spinosad, Azadirachtin and Abamectin at 25±1 C, 65±5% RH. Fifty eggs freshly of *C. carnea* from female offspring kept in a plastic bottle and provide with *S. cerealella* after hatching. Life table parameters were determined by taking age class X and the number of individuals surviving to age NX following and calculation of fertility life table parameters by solving the Euler equation (Andrewartha and Birch,1954), the age specific survival rate LX and age specific MX were determined daily.

Table (2): Effect of pesticides on mortality and fecundity of *Chrysoperla carnea*.

Treatments	Con.	Mortality %	Total eggs/Female
Spinosad	0.2ml/l.	38.07a	318c
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	1ml/l.	24.30 b	433b
Abamectin	0.4ml/l.	13.85 c	395b
Control	-	10.10 d	613a
LSD 0.05	-	3.10	45.3

2.Classification of the pesticides according to IOBC :

The net reproductive rate ($R_0 = \sum Lxmx$), intrinsic rate of natural increase [$r_m = \ln R_0(T)-1$], finite rate of increase ($\lambda = e^{rm}$), mean generation time [$T = (\sum xl xmx)/R_0$: the sum of development time from the egg stage to half of the life expectation of females after sexual maturation], doubling time ($DT = \ln 2/r_m$) and gross reproduction rate ($GRR = \sum mx$) (Sultan *et al.*,2017).

5.Statistical analysis:

Statistical analyses were used Bartlett s test the homogeneity of variances, an assumption of ANOVA.

Results and discussion:

1. Mortality and fecundity:

Results in Table (2) indicated that high mortality were observed when tearted *C.carnea* larvae by Spinosad at 38.07% and low mortality with abamectin at 13.85%,while total eggs were lower with spinosad than *A. indica* and abamectin, while no significant was observed form treated with *A.indica* and abamectin. This results similarly with (Elzen *et al.*, 2000) who stated that spinosad at the recommended field rate caused 19-65% mortality in the parasitoid *Catolaccus grandis* (Burks) (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidea). Spinosad also showed high toxicity to some predators such as lady beetle *Stethorus japonicus* Kamiya (Mori and Gotoh ,2001). Our results with neem oil agree with (El-Wakeil *et al.*, 2006) whose reported that neem was harmful to adults of *C. carnea*. Our results with those of (Medina *et al.*, 2001) whose indicated that neem oil toxic to *C. carnea*.

Data in Table (3) showed that Abamectin was total effect less than Spinosad and *A. indica* , so abamectin

was classified as a harmless ,but spinosad and *A. indica* were slightly harmful on *C. carnea*. (Sana *et al.*,2015) reported that abamectin benzoate was low residual effect on larvae *C.carnea*. Our results of abamectin are harmony with those (Bueno and Freitas, 2004) who found that *Chrysoperla externa* (Hagen) (Neuroptera:

Chrysopidae) egg viability was not affected by abamectin. Our results also agree with (Sana *et al.*, 2015) who indicated that Spinosad and neem oil slight residual effect, while indicated (Mostafa *et al.*, 2010) who indicated that spinosad was moderately toxic to *C.carnea* compared with chemical insecticides.

Table (3):Total effect and classification of pesticides for *Chrysoperla carnea* according the IOBC evaluation categories.

Treatments	Con.	Total effect	Classification
Spinosad	0.2 ml/l.	70.66	2
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	1 ml/l.	62.08	2
Abamectin	0.4 ml/l.	28.88	1

1= Harmless, 2= Slightly harmful.

3. Life table parameters:

Results in Table (4) revealed that no significant different through the incubation days , but larval durations increased with spinosad treated to 9.6 days, while it for control was 8.0 days while abamactin treated 8.6 days. Amany (2017) reported that larval duration increased from 7.67 days in control to 9.33 days for abamactin compound. Also, significant different in the pupal days of spinosad treated compared all the treatments. Significant different OF 80.6% larval survival on control compared with pesticides. Rezael *et al.* (2007) said that the survival curve of control was significantly different imidacloprid, propargite and pymetrozine pesticides on *C.carnea* . Table (5) indicated that the lowest and highest pre-oviposition period (Days) occurred during treatment with *A. indica* (3.66) and control (7.26), while were lowest oviposition period (Days) was found with spinosad compound. Observed that no significant different during post oviposition period (Days) of all treatments but no. of eggs/female with spinosad treated was significant different compared with the of treatments. Our results are harmony with (Sana *et al.* , 2015) who reported that Abamectin can be included in (IPM) program without any adverse residual

effect on bio-control agents used in IPM. This results compatible with (Muhammad *et al.*,2013) who stated that neem oil concentration relatively safe to beneficial insects and suitable for use in integrated pest management of aphids in canola, but our results disagree with Medina *et al.* (2001 and 2003) who found that the residual toxicity of neem oil against adults of *C.carnea*.

Data in the Table (6) showed that no significant different among the mean generation time (T) between the treatments and no significant among doubling time (DT), intrinsic rate of increase (rm) and finite rate of increase (λ). The lowest value for net reproductive rate (R0) occurred during Spinosad treatment . Amany (2017) who that abamectin is used with *C. carnea* in integrated pest management (IPM). The highest value of (Lx)=0.8 was reported with control, while lowest value of (Lx)=0.6 was reported with Spinosad compound. The results are harmony with (Rezaei *et al.*, 2006) who reported that the life table assay showed more adverse effects of pymetrozine than the IOBC method.

These results indicated that abamectin and *A.indica* can be used safety on *C.carnea* in integrated pest management (IPM),while spinosad compound need field studies.

Table (4): Effect of the pesticides on developmental parameters to *Chrysoperla carnea* offspring produced by treated larvae of *Chrysoperla carnea* under laboratory condition.

Treatments	Con.	Incubation days	Larval Days	Pupal Days	Larval Survival%	Adult survival%
Spinosad	0.2ml/l	2.66ab	9.6a	9.3a	60.8%b	61.4%a
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	1ml/l	2b	8.6ab	7.6ab	69%b	70.1%a
Abamectin	0.4ml/l	2.66ab	8.6ab	7b	67.6%b	74.1%a
Control	-	2.33ab	8b	8ab	80.6%a	86.7%a
L.S.D 0.05		1.33	1.33	2.24	11.26	42.6

Table (5): Effect of pesticides on reproductive offspring female to *Chrysoperla carnea*

Treatments	Con.	Pre-oviposition period(days)	Oviposition Period(days)	Post-oviposition Period(days)	No. of eggs/female
Spinosad	0.2ml/l	4.66b	10b	7.33a	5.4b
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	1ml/l	3.66b	13.66a	5b	6.36a
Abamectin	0.4ml/l	4.0b	14a	5.3b	6.5a
Control	-	7.26a	16.66a	5.3b	7.2a
L.S.D 0.05	-	1.29	4.10	0.76	0.90

Table (6): Life table parameters of *Chrysoperla carnea* treated with pesticides

Treatments	Mean generation time(T)in days	Doubling time(DT) in days	Net reproductive rate(R0)	Intrinsic rate of increase(rm)	Finite rate of increase(λ)	Survivor-Ship(Lx)
Spinosad	39	7.7	45.1	0.09	1.09	0.6
<i>Azadirachtin indica</i>	42	6.93	78.7	0.10	1.10	0.7
Abamectin	41	6.93	77.8	0.10	1.10	0.7
Control	44	6.93	101	0.10	1.10	0.8

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**Evaluation of three different pesticides sprayers equipment techniques
on the contamination ratio on the applicator body**

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Abstract:

The main experiments were carried out during the marrows agricultural successive seasons of 2017 and 2018 at the New Salheia district, El-Sharkia Governorate to evaluate three different techniques (Pressure or hydraulic atomization, air atomization and centrifugal atomization) in applying two pesticides and studying their effect on contamination ratio of applicator body legs, chest (right and left) and head. In this work four equipment were tested at five spray rates, the equipment used were knapsack motor sprayer (Air atomization technique), ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization technique), electric battery sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) fitted with hollow cone (Tx-6) nozzle, flat fan (Ss-83) nozzle and conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization), with variable spraying rates. In addition, pesticides (Buprofezin and imidacloprid) on marrows plant were used. The current study was determined the effect of each used technique on the reduction ratio of contamination on the applicator body. The obtained results during the two studied seasons showed that the spray with conventional motor sprayer gave high contamination on the operator body legs, chest (Right and left) and head, with the variable percentage at two types pesticides, followed by knapsack motor sprayer, electric battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone (Tx-6) and flat fan (Ss-83) nozzles and finely ULVA sprayer.

Introduction

Marrows plant is one of the most important vegetables in Egypt, Although it in all conditions, still not widely used by the food industry, squashes are consumed worldwide. Fruits are consumed as vegetables or dessert (Pie), seeds as nuts and, to a lesser extent, as cooking oil (Lazos, 1986 and 1992). *Aphis gossypii* (Glover) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and

the tomato whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), are considered the most common and dangerous insect pests which cause serious damage to plants, leading to the great reduction in the final yield (Hanafy, 2004).

The main aim of this work is studying the contamination with pesticides as an important problem which depends on the performance of

used technique and misapplication of chemical control. So, this work had to study the effect of some techniques with various spraying rates, in order to evaluate the level of contamination which occurred on applicator from the use of each technique.

The distribution of contamination over an operators protective clothing varied with sprayer type. Therefore, with non-motorized sprayers, the abdomen was the most heavily affected area. Contamination from electrostatic and spinning disc machines was more evenly dispersed. Using of air assisted sprayer with horizontal plastic tube distributor reduced the environmental pollution, increased spray swath width and field capacity (El-Gendy, 2000).

Evaluated the performance of certain, common-used ground spraying equipment on wheat and vegetables against weeds and aphid and whitefly respectively. The spraying and techniques tested are, knapsack motor sprayer Oleo Mac (AM 180) (Air atomization technique) with application rate 42.7L/fed., ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization technique) with 18.4L/fed., electric battery sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization technique) fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6) with 73.5L/fed. & flat fan nozzle (Ss-83) with 89.3L/fed. and the conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization technique) with 330L/fed. While, pesticides used were buprofezin (Applaud 25% SC (Suspension concentrate) with recommended rate 600cm/fed. and imidacloprid (Avenue 70%WG (Water dispersible granules)) with recommended rate 120gm/fed.

In general, results obtained showed that the contamination ratio of the applicator body occurred from high volume is higher than it from the lower volumes at same conditions operated

with two type pesticides (Imidacloprid and buprofezin) this may be due to the difference in the type of techniques.

Materials and methods

1. Equipment used:

1.1. Knapsack motor sprayer Oleo Mac (AM 180) (Air atomization technique):

It has tank capacity 14 liter, air velocity 120m/s, mist range horizontal 5m, flow rate 2.033 liters/min. and the rate of air discharge is about 16 m³/min.

1.2. ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization technique):

The sprayer has aluminum tube 1.30m long contains five batteries 1.5 volt located in the section of the tube and connected via an on/off switch to a 7.5 volt motor located at the rear of the tube. The sprayer has one liter plastic bottle concentrate liquid (Pesticide) which was fed by gravity to reach the spinning disc. The sprayer attached with back tank 10 liters and is leads to the spinning disc through plastic pipe (Food house) to increase performance.

1.3. Electric battery sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization technique):

It has a liquid tank capacity 20 liter, Batter 12 volts, operating pressure 3 bar, motor speed 2800- 3200rpm, diaphragm pump motor operated without air chamber and fitted with, hollow cone (Tx-6) or flat fan (Ss-83).

1.4. The Conventional Motor Sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization technique):

It has a liquid tank capacity 600 liters, fitted with spray gun, which connecting with the pump by 40 - 80m long rubber house, 5 hours power, reciprocating with air chamber and operating pressure 3 bar.

2. Pesticides used:

2.1. Buprofezin (Applaud 25% SC (Suspension concentrate) with recommended rate 600cm/fed.

2.2. Imidacloprid (Avenue70%WG (water dispersible granules)) with recommended rate 120gm/fed.

3. Protective clothes:

Overall to protect the body of operator, cap to protect the head, glasses and mask to cover the face, long gloves to protect hands and boot to protect legs.

4. Marrows crop:

This recommended variety of marrows in Egypt is (Yara) which used in this study and cultivate in ridges the distance between each ridge was 80cm and row spacing between the plants was 50cm. The experiment area divided into ten plots, area of each plot 1056m² (44x24m).

5. Measurements instrument:

5.1. Tape: For measuring the distance cut by operator of each replicate.

5.2. Stop watch: It used to calculate the average forward speed and flow rate with accuracy too sec.

5.3. Graduated Cylinder: Graduated Cylinder was used to calibrate the volume of the spraying solution.

5.4. Water Sensitive Paper: Ciba Geigy sensitive paper (76 x 26mm) to receive spray droplets from sprayers during their operation.

5.5. Wind meter: Wind meter was used to measure the wind velocity (m/s).

5.6. Strubin® lens (X15): This lens used to measure the number and volume of deposited droplets on sensitive paper. The hand lens (STROPEN®) field cited from Abou Amer (1993).

5.7. Thermometer: Used to measure the air temperature.

5.8. Hydrometer: Used to measure relative humidity.

6. Methods and Measurements:

6.1. Flow rate (L/min):

Flow rate is the first of determinant which use to determine the spray volume to the equipment used. Its measured by collecting the water in a graduated cylinder for one minute. The sprayer flow rate expressed in liters per minute. The calibration was repeated three times to obtain the average sprayed flow rate per minute.

6.2. Swath width of the sprayers (m):

Swath width is the second determinant which uses to determine the spray volume to the equipment used. The Patternation test determines the pass of ground spray with the use of water and sensitive cards Table (1).

Table (1): Laboratory technical data of sprayer techniques used by four sprayers evaluated.

Item	Knapsack motor Sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180)	ULVA sprayer	Electric Battery Sprayer		Conventional motor Sprayer
			Hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6)	Flat fan nozzle (Ss-83)	
Type of sprayer	Pneumatic	Rotary	Hydraulic	Hydraulic	Hydraulic
Spray tank (L).	14	10	20	20	600
Flow rate, (l/min.):	2.033	0.175	0.525	0.850	2.36
Rate of application,(l/fed.):	42.7	18.4	73.5	89.3	330
Spray height, (m)	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Swath width, (m)	5	1	0.75	1	0.75
Working speed, (Km/h.)	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4
Type of spray used	Target				
Productivity, (fed/h.)*	2.86	0.57	0.43	0.57	0.43
Rate of performance (fed/day).**	11.44	2.28	1.72	2.28	1.72

$$\text{Productivity, (fed/h.)} = \frac{60 \times \text{speed} \times \text{swaghwides}}{4200}$$

$$\text{Rate of performance/day} = \text{Productivity, (fed/h.)} \times 8 \times \frac{2}{3} \text{ Smith (1969)}$$

6.3. Description of sampling line:

Sensitive paper cards were fixed on the applicator (Head, thorax,

abdomen and legs (Right and left). As shown in Figure (1) for measuring of contamination deposit.

Figure (1): The position of sensitive cards on applicator.

6.4. Determination of spray deposit:

All cards were numbered, collected and transferred carefully to the laboratory for measurement and calculation of the deposited spectrum. Number and size spots (droplets) on sensitive cards will be measured with a special scaled monocular lens (Struben®), with a magnification of X15. This is a hand lens which gives a direct measurement because it magnifies both the spot and scale at the same rate, scales 6mm in 60 parts, and diameter 7mm. (Abu-Amer, 2005).

6.5. Weather conditions:

Temperature, relative humidity and wind velocity were measured during the experimental periods. At 2017 season, air temperature was an average of 24°C in laboratory and 27 in field while relative humidity recorded average of 68% in laboratory and 71% in field, while in 2018 season, the temperature was average 31°C in laboratory and 34 in field but the relative humidity was 68% in laboratory and 73% in field.

Measurements will be taken by the method described by (Barry, 1978). A simple has a pith ball which moves up at vertical tube according to the strength of the wind “Dwyer’s anemometer”. The anemometer must be, face the wind hold meter in front of you in vertical position and with scale side toward. Do not block bottom holes. Height of ball indicates wind velocity for high scale, cover hole at extreme top with finger.

Results and discussion

The data obtained from the field experiment with the purpose of evaluating some techniques (Air atomization, pressure or hydraulic atomization, centrifugal atomization) to apply pesticides in the field experiment and their effect on contamination of applicator, number of droplets on the operator body legs, chest (Right and left) and head were be determined.

1.The evaluation of techniques:

The evaluation of the contamination on the applicator operator body after spray techniques application was based on

number of droplets on the operator body legs, chest (Right and left) and head.

1.1. Effect using spray techniques on contamination of applicator of the operator's body with avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid):

Results obtained in Table (2) on the illustrated in Fig.1 indicated that, the highest average number of droplets/cm² operator's head was 21 and 5 No/cm² for conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) (Air atomization techniques) respectively, while ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization techniques) and electric battery sprayer with Tx-6, Ss-83 (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) recorded zero number of droplets/cm². Also, the results obtained and calculated per cm² on chest (Right and left) of operators during tests of three different types techniques were the highest average number of droplets/cm² operator's chest (Right and left) obtained from conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) was (32and 58 No/cm²). The second highest number of droplets per cm² were (11 and 20 No/cm²) right and left respectively from electric

battery sprayer with Ss-83(Pressure or hydraulic atomization). The knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) (Air atomization techniques) gave least number of droplets per cm² (7 and 13) No/cm² and respectively, but ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization techniques) and electric battery sprayer with Tx-6 (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) recorded zero number of droplets per cm².

Also, the results obtained should indicated that, the highest average number of droplets per cm² on the applicator legs, right and left were 72 and 68 droplets, by knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) (air atomization technique), electric battery sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) was the second highest and the number of droplets per cm² with Ss-83, Tx-6 were (Right 53, 57 and left 45, 40), respectively. The ULVA sprayer was the third highest and the number of droplets per cm² were (Right 35 and left 40), respectively. The least number of droplets per cm² were leg conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) (Right 30 and left 28) (Table 2).

Table (2): Contamination of applicator produced by spray different techniques with avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid) during (2017 and 2018) seasons.

Equipment		Spray Volume (L/fed)	No. droplet per cm ² (on head)	No. droplets /cm ² (on chest)		No. droplets per cm ² (on legs)	
				Right	Left	Right	Left
Knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180)		42.7	5	7	13	72	68
			3.03%	4.24%	7.88%	43.64%	41.21%
Electric Battery Sprayer	Ss-83	89.3	0.0	11	20	53	45
			0.0%	8.53%	15.50%	41.09%	34.88%
	Tx-6	73.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	57	40
			0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	58.76%	41.24%
ULVA sprayer		18.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	35	40
			0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	46.67%	53.33%
Conventional motor sprayer		330	21	32	58	28	30
			12.43%	18.93%	34.32%	16.57%	17.75%

1. 2. Effect using spray techniques on contamination of applicator of the operator's body with applaud 25 % SC (Buprofezin):

Results obtained in Table (3) on the illustrated in fig.1 indicated that, the highest average number of droplets per cm² operator's head was 15 and 8 No./cm² for conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic atomization) and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) (Air atomization techniques) respectively, while the other machines are zero No./cm².

On the other hand, the highest average number of droplets/ cm² operator's chest (Right and left) was (33 and 68 No./cm²) (0.0 and 11 No./cm²) and (7 and 11 No./cm²) conventional motor sprayer (Pressure or hydraulic

atomization) and electric battery sprayer with Ss-83(Pressure or hydraulic atomization), knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) (Air atomization techniques), respectively.

Also, results in Table (3) showed that, the highest average number of droplets per cm² on applicator legs, right and left were 57 and 63 droplets respectively by knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180), electric battery sprayer with Ss-83, Tx-6 (Right 48,66 and left 59,36No./cm²), respectively. In case of the ULVA sprayer (Centrifugal atomization techniques) (Right 44 and left 37No./cm²) and conventional motor sprayer (Right 31 and left 33No /cm²), respectively.

Table (3): Contamination of applicator produced by spray different techniques with Applaud 25 % SC (Buprofezin) during (2017 and 2018) seasons.

Equipment		Spray Volume (L/fed)	No. droplet/cm ² (on head)	No. droplets/cm ² (on chest)		No. droplets/cm ² (on legs)	
				Right	Left	Right	Left
Knapsack motor Sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180)		42.7	8	7	11	57	63
			5.5%	4.8%	7.5%	39%	43.8%
Electric Battery Sprayer	Ss-83	89.3	0.0	0.0	11	48	59
			0.0%	0.0%	9.3%	40.7%	50%
	Tx-6	73.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	66	36
			0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	64.7%	35.3%
ULVA sprayer		18.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	44	37
			0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	54.3%	45.7%
Conventional motor sprayer		330	15	33	68	31	33

Results obtained confirmed that all techniques used in this study gives contamination of the applicator. Less contamination on the applicator was ULVA sprayer, at 42.7 L/fed. followed directly with the electric battery sprayer fitted both 2 nozzles (Hollow con nozzle (Tx-6) at 73.5 L/fed. and flat fan nozzle (Ss-83) at 89.3 L/fed, The most contamination occurred with the conventional motor sprayer at 330

L/fed, then knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac at 42.7L/fed at used the Avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid) and applaud 25% SC (Buprofezin). Also, the results obtained during the two seasons showed that the spray with high volume was gave high contamination ratio on the applicator body if compared with low volume spraying at same conditions operated with two type pesticides (Imidacloprid and

buprofezin) this may be due to the difference in the type of techniques.

2. Comparison between spray techniques:

Results obtained in Table (4) indicated that, the highest percentage coverage marrows plants were 80.1, 76.8 and 66.7% for ULVA sprayer, hydraulic atomization (Electric battery sprayer (Tx-6)) and knapsack motor

sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180) respectively. Meanwhile, the lowest percentage of contamination was 19.9, 23.2 and 33.3% for ULVA sprayer, hydraulic atomization (Electric battery sprayer (Tx-6)) and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180), respectively.

Table (4): Show the percent of number of droplets /cm² on targets produced by ground sprayer with applaud 25 % SC (Buprofezin) insecticide against whitefly and aphid at (2017 – 2018) season.

Equipment	Knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180)		ULVA sprayer		Electric battery sprayer				Conventional motor sprayer		
					Tx-6		Ss-83				
Spray volume (L/fed)	42.7		18.4		73.5		89.3		330		
Dose rate	Recommended rate										
Target	Droplets spectrum	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N
	Plants	293	66.7	326	80.1	338	76.8	265	59.3	133	42.5
Contamination	146	33.3	81	19.9	102	23.2	182	40.7	180	57.5	

Results obtained in Table (5) indicated that, the highest percentage coverage marrows plants were 80.5, 76.7 and 63.9% for ULVA sprayer, hydraulic atomization (Electric battery sprayer (Tx-6)) and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180),

respectively. Meanwhile, the lowest percentage of contamination was 19.5, 23.3 and 36.1% for ULVA sprayer, hydraulic atomization (Electric battery sprayer (Tx-6)) and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180), respectively.

Table (5): Show the percent of number of droplets /cm² on targets produced by ground sprayer with avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid) insecticide against whitefly and aphid at (2017 – 2018) season.

Equipment	Knapsack motor sprayer Oleo mac (AM 180)		ULVA sprayer		Electric battery sprayer				Conventional motor sprayer		
					Tx-6		Ss-83				
Spray volume (L/fed)	42.7		18.4		73.5		89.3		330		
Dose rate	Recommended rate										
Target	Droplets spectrum	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N	N/cm ²	% N
	Plants	292	63.9	309	80.5	320	76.7	245	65.5	134	44.2
Contamination	165	36.1	75	19.5	97	23.3	129	34.5	169	55.8	

From the results, it can be concluded that the low volume spraying gives more satisfactory results when compared with the use of high volume. So, this study was recommended to use the low volume technique under suitable conditions to reduce the contamination as far as possible. In addition, it is very necessary to wear the protective clothes to protect the applicator from pesticide hazards.

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Biological studies of the citrus blackfly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) infesting *Citrus aurantifolia* in Lahej Governorate, Republic of Yemen

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to investigate the life cycle of the citrus blackfly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* Ashby (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) on *Citrus aurantifolia* seedlings during the period from December 2010 and continued until March 2011 in a private orchard in Al-Houta city, Lahej Governorate. The results of the study showed that the average duration of the incomplete stages from laying the egg until the exit of the adult insect (generation period) under field conditions at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative humidity of 66.75% was 70.6 days, and the average incubation period for eggs was 14.6 days, and the average duration of the nymph and pupa phase was 56 days. The average duration of the nymph and pupa phases (The four ages of the nymph) was 8.2 days, 8.2 days, 7.6 days and 32 days for the first, second, third and fourth ages (The pupa), respectively. The results showed the mortality rate in the incomplete stages from laying the egg until the exit of the adult insect, as it was 44.06% in the egg phase, in the nymph and pupa phase it amounted to 85.27%, and in the phase of the egg until the emergence of the adult insect (Generation duration) it reached 91.76%. The results also showed the mortality rate in the nymph and pupa stages (The ages of the four nymphs) as it was 35.13, 12.66, 7.5% for the first, second and third ages, respectively, and in the fourth age of the nymph (The pupa), the mortality rate reached 71.89%.

Introduction

The citrus blackfly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* Ashby (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is one of the important insect pests that infect citrus in the whole of the Republic of Yemen. Honey is a suitable environment for the growth of black mold fungus on the leaves, which causes them to blacken and attract dust, which affects the photosynthesis and nutrition process of

trees, so the fruits appear black, atrophic and small in size, and the combined action of sucking the sap with the presence of the black mold fungus leads to a severe decrease in production of the tree (Rajak and Diwakar, 1987; French *et al.*, 1997; Ministry of Agriculture, 2000 and Ba-Angood, 2008).

Approximately 5-10 nymphs/cm² of the leaf are sufficient

to reduce the nitrogen level to less than 22% necessary for the growth of fruits and caused losses ranging from 20-80% of the citrus crop. Research conducted in Mexico showed that the production of fruits decreased to more than 90% when the infection exceeded 5-7 nymphs/cm² of the leaf (De Lemos *et al.*, 2017). Asia is the original home of the insect, as it was first classified in the Caribbean countries in 1913 in Jamaica, and it is currently found in many Caribbean countries and Central America. It was first seen in Trinidad in 1997 and then spread on the island (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000).

It was recorded in South Africa in January 1959 (Bedford and Tomas, 1965), in America (Nguyen and Sailer, 1987), and the United States of America (Dowell and Steinberg, 1990) and in Nagpur in India (Satpute *et al.*, 1989). In the Arab world, it is found in Egypt, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, the Sultanate of Oman, Iraq, Syria and Yemen (Ba-Angood, 2008).

It is spread in Yemen in all citrus growing areas (Ba-Angood *et al.*, 1997). It was recorded in Yemen for the first time in 1970 (Ba-Angood, 1977). It affects other families in addition to citrus trees such as mangoes, bananas, guavas, papayas, pomegranates and dams trees (Ba-Angood, 2008), Indian cork (Al-Kaf, 1988), coffee (Ba-Angood *et al.*, 1997), okra and some types of flowers (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000) and in Lahj Governorate, it was recorded on 27 plant families that included citrus species (Murad and Ba-Angood, 2008), and it was found on more than 300 plant families (Nguyen and Hamon, 1993).

Many studies dealt with the life cycle of the insect, as it was mentioned (Ba-Angood, 2008) in a study of the life

of the insect. The female lays her eggs in the form of small circles on the lower surface of the leaves, and each female lays 2-3 circles, and in each circle there are 28-34 eggs during a period of 3-4 days after it exit from the last life of the nymph (The pupa) and at a temperature of 32°C, it completes her life cycle in about 40 day. He also pointed to a cluster in another study of the life of the insect, in which he mentioned that the egg takes 8-12 days to hatch, the first age takes 8-20 days, the second between 8-30 days, the third takes 6-20 days, and the last nymph (Pupa) age 16 - 40 days and the life cycle from the egg to the adult insect takes 46-122 days (Ba-Angood, 2008).

Al-Kaf (1988) indicated in a study of the insect's life on citrus species that the period from laying eggs until their hatching ranged between 10.5-11.5 days, while the phases of the nymph and pupa ranged between 54.7-55.8 days, and the period from laying eggs until the exit of the adult insect ranged Between 65.2-67.3 days at temperatures of 29°C.

Hassan (1989) found in a study on the life of the insect on seedlings of Baladi Lim and Valencia orange that the average period from the egg to the adult insect takes 72 days and 78 days, respectively. The period from laying eggs until hatching into nymphs is 19.0 days, 16.20 days, and the average period for the nymph and pupa phases is 52.9 days, 62.35 days for Baladi lime and Valencia orange, respectively, under an average temperature of 24.46°C and a humidity of 79%.

Dowell and Steinberg (1990) found that the female's ovaries are ready 36-24 hours after turning into a full insect at a temperature of 24°C - 27°C. In Venezuela, Boscan *et al.* (1981)

mentioned that the egg takes 12-26 days to hatch and the larva takes three ages ranging from 19-6, 7-6, 19-9 days, respectively, while the pupa stage takes 32-21 days and takes One generation has a period ranging between 103-54 days during the months from February to May. In Florida, Nguyen and Hamon (1993) concluded that the eggs hatch within a period ranging between 7-10 days, the first age takes 7-16 days, and the second between 7-30 days, and the third takes 6-20 days, while the pupa phase ranges between 16-50 days, and the life cycle from the egg to the whole insect ranges between 133-45 days, depending on the temperature.

French *et al.* (1997) added that one generation takes about 60 days at a temperature of 90°F, 75 days at a temperature of 80°F and 120 days at a temperature of 70°F. The Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation in Trinidad and Tobago noted that the period of the egg to the first nymph takes 7-10 days, the period of the first lifespan from the nymph to the second 7-15 days, the period of the second life of the nymph to the third 7-30 days, the period of the third life from the nymph to the maiden 6-20 days, while the period of pupa was 15 - 60 days, and the period from the egg to the adult insect was 43-150 days.

The short period occurs when temperatures rise (Ministry of Agriculture, 2000) and in India (Patel and Patel, 2001) found that when they studied the life cycle of potted plants on lime, the average incubation period was 15.27 days, the average nymph phase period was 24.32 days, and the average pupa period The one that turns into a male is 73.38 days, while the period of the pupa that turns into a female is 71.39 days at an average temperature of

25.9°C and a relative humidity of 52.5%.

Pena *et al.* (2009) in the study on the life of the insect, concluded that the average incubation period for the egg is 15 days, and the fourth age of the nymph (Pupa) takes an average longer than the three ages of the nymph, and the average period from the egg to the adult insect takes 70 days under an average temperature of 27.4°C and a humidity of 79.4%. The number of annual generations of the insect varies from one region to another, and some researchers have indicated this. In Venezuela, Boscan *et al.* (1981) stated that the insect has four generations per year.

In Florida, Nguyen and Hamon (1993) found that the insect has six generations per year. Weeks *et al.* (2012) indicated that the insect has three to six generations per year, overlapping in the year according to the local climate. The natural death rate varies in the different insect stages of the citrus fly, and Boscan *et al.* (1981) they found that the natural death rate for eggs was 58.26%, and for the three ages of the larva, the death rate was 59.07, 53.85, 76.71%, respectively, while the death rate reached in the pupal stage to 74.44%. Hassan (1989) concluded that the natural death rate of insects on lemongrass in eggs was 35%, and the death rate for nymphs and pupae was 67%, while the death rate for the stage from the egg until the exit of the full insect was 78%. Patel and Patel (2001) stated that the average hatchability rate for eggs is 75.61%. As for the number of insects that reach the full stage, its average reaches 16.9 / 100 eggs (Boscan *et al.*, 1981).

The number of annual generations of the insect varies from

one region to another, and some researchers have indicated this. In Venezuela, Boscan *et al.* (1981) stated that the insect has four generations per year. In Florida, Nguyen and Hamon (1993) found that the insect has six generations per year. And Weeks *et al.* (2012) indicated that the insect has three to six generations per year, overlapping in the year according to the local climate. The natural mortality rate varies in the different insect stages of the citrus blackfly, and Boscan *et al.* (1981) found that the natural mortality rate for eggs was 58.26%, and for the three ages of the larva, the mortality rate was 59.07, 53.85, 76.71%, respectively, while the mortality rate reached in the pupa stage to 74.44%. Hassan (1989) concluded that the natural mortality rate of insects on lemongrass in eggs was 35%, and the mortality rate for nymphs and pupa was 67%, while the mortality rate for the stage from the egg until the exit of the full insect was 78%.

Patel and Patel (2001) stated that the average hatchability rate for eggs is 75.61%. As for the number of insects that reach the full stage, it averages up to 16.9 / 100 eggs (Boscan *et al.*, 1981). and due to the importance of the insect, farmers resort to using many pesticides to combat this pest, some of which are harmful to vital enemies such as novacron 40% E.C. methidathion 40% E.C. The number of spraying times to combat this pest has increased to more than 4 times per year (By cluster) 2008.

Since the global trend today tends to rationalize the use of pesticides and implement the integrated pest management (IPM) program, which requires information about the insect, including its life, the current study targeted some biological studies on the

citrus blackfly, in order to benefit from them in the future program of integrated pest management.

Materials and methods

This field experiment was carried out in a private orchard in Al-Houta city in Lahej Governorate on lemongrass seedlings during the period from 13/12/2010 and continued until 2/3/2011 at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative humidity of 66.75%. Two seedlings of lemons placed in polyethylene bags were brought from the plantation management nursery to the private orchard. Four fresh and infested-free leaves were randomly selected from each seedling and numbered from 4-1, then the incomplete phases development period (Generation duration) was followed for a number of the egg rings that were laid within nine days, and the infection was natural, meaning that the females were not selected and placed in cages.

The readings were taken for the number of egg rings, the number of eggs in each ring, the number of the three stages of the nymph, the number of pupa and the number of adults with the naked eye. Females laid eggs on 7 leaves, while one leaf was not laid on it. The number of eggs on one leaf for nine days ranged from 28-145 eggs / leaf. Insect stages were identified, as the shape of the eggs is oval and their color at the beginning of laying is white, then turns to yellow, then to brown, then to black at the beginning of its hatching until the age of the first nymph, whose shape is elongated oval and its color is black. Then it turns into the second age of the nymph, which is slightly larger than it and its shape is oval-convex, and its color is pale black and there are

yellow spots and many thorns on the upper part of its body.

Distinguishing between the three phases of the nymph (First, second, third) through continuous observation of them and it is characterized by the fact that it sheds from one phase to another in the same place (Fixed), then the third nymph's life turns into the fourth nymph's life, which is called the pupa because it is static and from it the complete insect emerges and forms it Oval, shiny black in color, with many thorns, then gradually a white waxy layer appears around its edges. This waxy layer increases in density with the near exit of the full insect. With the exit of a honeycomb substance from the upper area (the area of exit of the insect It also shows the movement of the insect inside the virgin before the exit, and when the insect leaves a hole in the shape of the letter T on its back, and the whole insect at the beginning of its exit from the virgin, the color of its head, chest and stomach was red-orange, then gradually turns to brown, then to blackish blue, then to black, and its body and wings are covered with a thin layer of wax, and a distinction was made between the female and the male, the female is larger than the male, as the female has a transverse body in the middle, while the male has a thin body, and the examination was carried out daily from the beginning of laying eggs until the exit of the full insect.

The incubation period of eggs was calculated on the basis of the time between laying and hatching the eggs, and the duration of the first age of the nymph was calculated on the basis of the time period between the exit of the first age of the nymph from the egg until her transformation into the second age

of the nymph, and the duration of the second life of the nymph was calculated on the basis of the time period between the exit of the second age of the nymph from the first age of the nymph until her transformation into the third age of the nymph, and the duration of the third age of the nymph was calculated on the basis of the time period between the exit of the third age of the nymph from the second age of the nymph until her transformation into the fourth age of the nymph (Pupa), and it was calculated Duration of the three ages of the nymph on the basis of the time period between the exit of the first age of the nymph from the egg until immobility. The duration of the fourth age of the nymph (Pupa) was calculated on the basis of the period between the onset of the zygote until the exit of the adult insect. The mortality rate was calculated in the different incomplete stages of the egg to the adult insect (Generation duration). Then the incubation periods, the three ages of the nymph and the puparium were recorded and the arithmetic mean, and standard error were calculated for them (Al-Ani and Tabara, 1980).

Results and discussion

The results of the study (Table 1) showed the duration of the incomplete stages from the egg to the exit of the adult insect (Generation duration) on the lemon seedlings, as the incubation period for the eggs ranged from laying until hatching to nymphs between 14-15 days with an average of 14.6 ± 0.13 During the months of December 2010 and January 2011, at an average temperature of 25.65°C and a relative humidity of 67.5%. The duration of the nymph and pupa phases ranged between 51-61 days, with an average of 56 ± 0.91 at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative

humidity of 66.75% during the months from December 2010 to March 2011. As for the period of development of the incomplete stages (generation period) from laying the egg until the exit of the adult insect, it ranged between 65-76

days with an average of 70.6 ± 1.01 during the months from December 2010 until March 2011 at an average temperature of 25.83°C and relative humidity of 66.75%.

Table (1): The duration of the different incomplete instars from egg to adult (Generation duration) of the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* on lemongrass seedlings *Citrus aurantifolia* in a private orchard in Lahij Governorate.

	Range of 1 phase duration in days		
	Egg	The nymph and pupa	From egg to adult (Generation duration)
Range	14 -15	51 -61	65 -76
Average	14.6	56	70.6
Standard error \pm	0.13	0.91	1.01

The results of the study are consistent with previous results carried out by (Hassan, 1989), where it was found in a study about the life of the insect on the seedlings of the municipal lemon from November to February that the period from the egg to the adult insect takes 44-92 days with an average of 72 days, the period from laying eggs until hatching To nymphs 10-24 days with an average of 19.0 days, and the period for the nymph and pupa phases is 20-78 days with an average of 52.9 days, under average temperatures of 24.46°C and relative humidity of 79%. These results are similar to what was obtained (Murad, 2007), which found in a study on the life of the insect on lemon trees from December to March that the incubation period for eggs is 14-17 days, with an average of 15.9 days, and the duration of nymphs and pupae is 53-57 days, with an average of 55.7 days, and the duration from the egg. To the adult insect (Generation period) 67-74 days, with an average of 71.6 days, under average temperatures of 26.25°C and relative

humidity of 76%. These results are also consistent with what was found by Dowell *et al.* (1981), where he found that the egg period takes 9-97 days, and the life cycle from egg to adult insect takes 567-52 days at temperatures of 32°C and 16°C , respectively.

The results recorded in (Table 2) showed the period for the development of each stage of the nymph and the pupa (the four ages of the nymph). The three ages of the nymph ranged between 8-9 days with an average of 8.2 ± 0.12 , 7-9 days with an average of 8.2 ± 0.19 , and 7-8 days with an average of 7.6 ± 0.13 for the first, second and third ages, respectively, at an average temperature of 25.65°C and a relative humidity of 67.5% during the months of December 2010 and January 2011. The duration of the fourth lifespan of the nymph (the pupa) ranged between 29-35 days, with an average of 32 ± 0.56 , at an average temperature of 25.87°C and a relative humidity of 67% during the months from January to March 2011.

Table (2): Longevity of nymph and pupa of citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* on lemongrass seedlings *Citrus aurantifolia* in a private orchard in Lahej Governorate

	Range of 1 phase duration in days				
	The first age of the nymph	The second age of the nymph	The third age of the nymph	The fourth age of the nymph (Pupa)	The nymph and pupa
Range	8 - 9	7 - 9	7 -8	29 -35	51 -61
Average	8.2	8.2	7.6	32	56
Standard error \pm	0.12	0.19	0.13	0.56	0.91

These results are consistent with the findings of Dowell *et al.* (1981), where he showed that the period of the first nymph phase ranges between 7 - 37 days, the second 5 - 55 days, the third 6 - 70 days, and the fourth 25-272 days, all at temperatures of 32°C. 16°C respectively for each of the phases, and this corresponds to what was found (Ba-Angood, 2008) in a study of the life of the insect, where it was mentioned that the first lifespan takes 8-20 days, the second 8-30 days, and the third 6-20 days, while the last life of the nymph) It takes 16-40 days, and it is noted from the results (Table 1, 2) that the period from laying the egg until the exit of the full insect has been long due to the low temperatures during the study period, as the insect's life is affected by the temperature, and these results are

consistent with the results of Dowell *et al.* (1981) and Boscan *et al.* (1981).

The results showed (Table 3 and Figure 1) that the mortality rate in the egg phase was 44.1% at an average temperature of 25.65°C and a relative humidity of 67.5% during the months of December 2010 and January 2011. The mortality rate in the nymph and pupa phases reached 85.27% at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative humidity of 66.75% during the months from December 2010 to March 2011. As for the mortality rate of the incomplete stages from the egg until the exit of the adult insect (generation period) it reached 91.76% during the months from December 2010 until March 2011 at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative humidity of 66.75%.

Table (3): Mortality rate in the different incomplete stages of the egg to the adult (Generation duration) of the citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* on lemongrass seedlings *Citrus aurantifolia* in a private orchard in Lahij Governorate.

Phase	Number of episodes	Number that was followed from the mentioned phase	Number that completed its development	Number of mortalities	Mortality rate (%)
Egg	21	631	353	278	44.1
The nymph and pupa	21	353	52	301	85.3
From egg to adult (Generation duration)	21	631	52	579	91.8

These results are consistent with the findings of (Murad, 2007), where it was found that the mortality rate of the stage from the egg until the exit of the adult insect (Generation duration) was 88.1%, and the nymphs and pupae had the mortality rate of 79.1%, while the mortality rate in the egg stage was 42.8%. The results of the study are

close to the results of a previous study conducted by (Hassan, 1989), in which he explained that the mortality rate in the various insect stages of the citrus blackfly was 35% in eggs, and the mortality rate or nymphs and pupae was 67%, and the mortality rate for the stage from the egg until the exit of the full insect was 78%.

Figure (1): shows the mortality rate in the incomplete stages (Generation period) of the citrus black fly.

The results showed (Table 4 and Figure 2) that the mortality rate in the nymph and pupa stages was 35.13% in the first age of the nymph, and it was 12.66% in the second age of the nymph, and in the third age of the nymph it amounted to 7.5, and it reached 71.89 % in the fourth age of the nymph (the pupa) at an average temperature of 25.83°C and a relative humidity of 66.75% during the months from December 2010 to March 2011. These results are consistent with what was found by (Boscan *et al.*, 1981) that the mortality rate in the fourth age of the nymph (Pupa) was 74.44%, and close to what he also mentioned that the

mortality rate in the first age of the nymph was 59.07%. It was seen from the results (Tables 3, 4) that the death rate in the egg phases and the first age of the nymph increased due to their lack of tolerance to the surrounding environmental conditions such as the strong winds on 20/12/2010 and the continuous winds during the first week of January 2011 due to their small size and softness. The death rate in the fourth age of the nymph (virgin) due to continuous heavy rain and winds from mid-January to the end of February 2011, as well as the presence of natural enemies in the winter is relatively more.

Table (4): Mortality rate in the nymph and pupa of citrus black fly *Aleurocanthus woglumi* on lemongrass seedlings *Citrus aurantifolia* in a private orchard in Lahij Governorate.

Phase	Number of episodes	Number that was followed from the mentioned phase	Number that completed its development	Number of mortalities	Mortality rate (%)
The first age of the nymph	21	353	229	124	35.13
The second age of the nymph	21	229	200	29	12.66
The third age of the nymph	21	200	185	15	7.5
The fourth age of the nymph (pupa)	21	185	52	133	71.89
The nymph and pupa	21	353	52	301	85.27

Figure(2): Shows the mortality rate in the nymph and pupa phase of the citrus black fly.

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- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
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Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

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